

Structural Health Assessment of Steel Girder Bridge: A Case Study of Butibam and Bumbu Bridge in Lae City

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Master of Philosophy in Civil Engineering

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Statement of Originality

I *Grace McCoy Wantepe*, declare that the thesis entitled *Structural Health Assessment of Steel Girder Bridge: A Case Study of Butibam and Bumbu Bridge in Lae City* submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Master of Philosophy in Civil Engineering at the Papua New Guinea University of Technology contains original research based on:

- Employment of analytical and Finite Element Methods for evaluation of failure modes on bridge structural components and elements subjected to extreme loads and environmental conditions.
- Novel bridge health assessment procedures with computer assistance for condition assessment and evaluation of in-service steel girder bridge.

To the best of my knowledge the content of the thesis has not been submitted to any other University for the award of any degree or diploma. The thesis is inspired by the latest developments in civil engineering, but the approach is not encountered in any textbook or published paper in the field and as such it is original research effort.

Candidate: *Grace McCoy Wantepe*

Date: November 16, 2021

Signature:

Abstract

Bridge inspection and condition assessment is an essential element in any Bridge Management System (BMS) particularly for aged and deteriorated bridges, and a path way to condition rating. Majority of the bridges in Lae City and Papua New Guinea (PNG) have exceeded their design lives and are at risk of collapse according to one of the Technical Assistance Consultant's Report, Cardno Emerging Markets (Australia) Pty Ltd, in 2011. Almost about 152 bridges were inspected along the nominated five priority national roads in PNG. This indicates that effective bridges condition assessment and management is of crucial importance to maintain bridges in a sufficient condition and preserve them from deteriorating. A major part is bridge condition rating and simulation, which is an important aspect in their service lives to forecast bridge durability and their need for repair and maintenance.

In this pilot study, three levels of bridge inspection and condition assessment forms for steel girder bridge have been developed for Bumbu and Butibam Bridge of Lae City in the Morobe Province of PNG. The bridge evaluation and condition assessment emanate from visually recorded inspection data specifically on the two bridges. There are three main important factors considered in the evaluation of bridge element structural index condition assessment. They are structural importance, material vulnerability, and casual factors such as road class, age, environment and inspection. These parameters were adopted and incorporated for a more holism and objectivity to the current approaches. The casual factors are implemented as a coefficient to the overall structural index, which illustrates the capability of the developed forms. Moreover, the results obtained from the developed forms and stress analysis and displacements on bridge model using solid works complements the results.

Additionally, the forms developed and applied including simulation results has been used to evaluate the current stage of the steel girder bridges of Bumbu and Butibam of Lae City.

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List of Abbreviations

ACES	ACES Bridge Analysis Software
ARTC	Australian Rail Track Corporation
AS	Australian Standard
ASTM	American Society for Testing Materials
BAM	Bridge Asset Management
BIS	Bridge Inventory System
BSHM	Bridge Structural Health Monitoring
CM	Condition Monitoring
DOTs	Department of Transport(s)
DoW	Department of Works
DSP	Development Strategic Plan
DTMR	Queensland Department of Transport & Main Roads
GoPNG	Government of Papua New Guinea
GPS	Global Positioning System
NDE/NDT	Non-Destructive Evaluations/Testings
NICTA	National Information & Communication Technology Authority
NSW	New South Wales
PNG	Papua New Guinea
PNG DSP	PNG Development Strategic Plan
RL	Reduced Level(s)
RMS	Roads and Maritime Services
SHB	Sydney Harbour Bridge
SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
T44	44 Tonne Vehicle
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States
VicRoads	Victorian Roads

Chapter 1 : Introduction

1.1 Background

Bridges are an essential component of civil infrastructure in any modern transport system. It isn't easy to travel any distance without crossing a bridge structure. To visualize the importance of a bridge by comparing the two main components of a transport system, i.e., a road and the bridge itself. The in-service bridges constantly expose their members to destructive effects such as material aging, widespread corrosion of structural steel elements and components, including reinforcing bars in concrete structures, high traffic volume and heavy loading, or overall deterioration and aging. Combined with design defects and construction or damage due to accidents, these factors speed the deterioration of bridge structural components, resulting in the loss of load-carrying capacity (Kekare et al., 2014 and Dong, Song, & Liu, 2010). Thus, reliable methods are required to monitor them during their service life to determine the current condition and estimate the overall structure's safety, reliability, and efficiency.

Bridges are costly structures and plays a vital role in connecting the highway system of Papua New Guinea (PNG). PNG is a country known for its rugged physical topography, and majority of its population, approximately 85 %, reside in dispersed rural settlements that are highly in isolation to each other by rugged terrain and landscape. These rural settlements are connected by roads that make up most of the transport system and it is very difficult to travel any distance without crossing a bridge structure. As stated by Badran (2013), health and prosperity of transportation infrastructures are an important tool for measuring the national growth, where transportation network is playing a pivotal role in the movement of people, goods, and services. Hence bridges are very important structures that provide linkages for movement of people, goods, and services from production areas to markets, and ensure that there is efficient service delivery between centers.

Figure 1-1: Map showing the project study area in Lae City and major road network system in PNG

As shown in the map in Figure 1-1, the Highlands Highway connects Highlands Provinces to Lae and Madang's ports, while others have a lesser extent of a road system, including Port Moresby and Rabaul. These highway systems are significant for efficient consumer goods, and services flow from production areas to other towns, villages, and communities. According to Cardno Emerging Markets (2011), most of the bridge stock in PNG and along the national roads were constructed before Independence in 1975 by the Australian Government, including the Bumbu and Butibam bridge of Lae City. Even more new bridges have been built under the Yumi Yet Bridge Project after the Independence of the PNG Government. These bridges are comprised of standard types, including baileys, steel composite and trusses. According to the inventory and information kept by the Department of Works (DoW), the types of bridges on national roads, particularly in Lae City, are mostly steel girders with a few trusses and bailey. Table 1-1 illustrates brief information on some of the bridges in Lae City and PNG, and pictures of common bridge types for the first three bridges are shown in Figure 1-2. These steel bridges were widely constructed due to their dynamic functionality, effectiveness, sustainability, and affordable material compared to other construction materials. The Bumbu and Butibam bridge are similar to the Markham bridge shown in the picture.

Table 1-1-1: Brief Information of some bridges in Lae City and Papua New Guinea

Bridge Name	Length (m)	Type	Location/Province
*Anglimp Bridge	54	Bailey Truss	Anglimp, Jiwaka Province
Bumbu Bridge	49.4	Girder	Lae City, Morobe Province
Butibam Bridge	81.4	Girder	Lae City, Morobe Province
Cedar Bridge	35.7	Beam/Slab	Lae, Morobe Province
Daulom Bridge	36.6	Bailey Truss	New Ireland Province
Iruan Bridge	125	Bailey Truss	New Ireland Province
Kesuai Bridge	73.5	Bailey Truss	Lae, Morobe Province
Leron Bridge	?	Girder	Lae, Morobe Province
*Markham Bridge	515	Beam/Slab	Lae, Morobe Province
Mea Bridge	146	Bailey Truss	New Ireland Province
Menia Bridge	45.7	Bailey Truss	New Ireland Province
*Nebilyer Bridge	50	Warren Truss	Nebilyer, Western Highlands
Pine Tops Bridge	27.4	Beam/Slab	Wau, Morobe Province
Rumu Bridge	30	Beam/Slab	Lae, Morobe Province
Sausi Bridge	137	Bailey Truss	West New Britain
Surinam Bridge	49.5	Warren Truss	New Ireland Province
Waterbung Bridge	36.8	Beam/Slab	Lae, Morobe Province
Yalu Bridge	?	Girder	Lae, Morobe Province

**Pictures of these bridges are shown below.*

Markham bridge, the longest beam (steel girder) and slab bridge in Lae City and PNG.
(Source: <https://www.google.com/maps>)

Warren Truss bridge (left) and Bailey Truss bridge (right). (Source: Picture courtesy of DoW)

Figure 1-2: Shows an example of the common types (steel girder, warren truss and bailey truss) bridges in Lae City and PNG.

The bridge structures in PNG are deteriorating very fast due to environmental exposure, aging, exposure to chemicals, and increased traffic volume in the past recent years. It is evident that PNG has a large shortfall in bridge replacement, and a large number of bridges require urgent replacement to maintain the road network. Bumbu and Butibam bridges are among many others that require urgent attention as both are located right within the Lae City, which connects higher institutions and manufacturing industries situated on either side of the Bumbu River to the City Center. Bridge inspections and condition assessments of the bridge components are often neglected or overlooked until after signs resulting from fault accumulations are severe and evident enough. For instance, Figures 1-4 pictures show bridge failure and collapse due to a lack of condition inspection and assessment.

Pine Tops Bridge failure due to flood because of no proper embankment protection.
(Source: Holemba G.A.)

Bridge Deterioration

Same Bridge after Collapse

Kingston Bridge collapse due to heavy vehicle load in Kainantu, Eastern Highlands Province. (Source:<http://www.thepostsinpng.com/2014/08/photo-journal-bridge-collapse/>)

Figure 1-3: Examples of bridges with issues which eventually lead to damage by flood or collapse.

There is no guarantee of maintaining the road network due to fragile road structures such as bridges. Bridge structural monitoring and safety evaluation

assessment is a central bridge that provides linkage for smooth movement of people, goods and services in Lae City and PNG.

Lae City is undergoing increased infrastructure developments due to the operation of mine sites, the establishment of significant mackerel and tuna manufacturing plants, the recently completed new Lae Port (Tidal Basin), and the construction of the four-lane road from Lae to Nadzab Airport. About 3.5 billion Kina worth of goods moving every day at the Lae Port. Industrial activities in Lae City are high, and the province is leading in PNG with many industries and manufacturing companies. These projects significantly impact the existing road system, and there is increased use of heavy commercial vehicles on roads and bridges. Employment in Lae is 10% from freight transportation and warehousing and 30% including manufacturing (Konzang, 2013). According to Konzang (2013), every day, more than 600 vehicles cross the Bumbu and Butibam, including heavy vehicles with six axles. Moreover, the recent developments are having a significant impact on the road network system, with traffic congestion due to the increasing number of people in the city. Bumbu and Butibam bridge are on the primary road network of the city and links major residential, industrial, commercial and university to the city Centre. Hence monitoring the safe performance of the Bumbu and Butibam bridge is vital for the smooth and effective movement of people, goods and services.

Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) is a methodology for assessing the 'health' of a structure by evaluating the degree of deterioration and remaining service life of civil infrastructures systems. SHM is generally in two parts: application of SHM technologies and data analysis. According to Karbhari VM (2009), SHM of civil infrastructures involves various technologies, including piezoelectric impedance transducers, wireless sensors and networks, vibration-based damage detection, fibre optic sensors, etc., application to infrastructures such as bridges and buildings. SHM of civil infrastructures is an essential source for asset owners because of its advantages over traditional methods. SHM improves understanding of structural field behaviour. It detects damages at an early age of problem initiation, reduces inspection and repair time, and encourages the usage of innovative materials. It helps develop rational

management and maintenance strategies for the safe movement of people, goods and services. Although SHM is important, it also has some disadvantages, including the high cost of installation, vulnerability to ambient noise corruption, and earthquake conditions. Furthermore, the challenges lie with the application of SHM like bridge accessibility, manipulating the vast amount of data generated by sensors, environmental conditions, and the size and complexity of large structures that need a significant number of sensing points to be installed.

Bridge Health Monitoring (BHM) implements a mechanism for identifying bridge components and infrastructures' damaged and deteriorating state for asset management purposes. Bridge Structural Health Monitoring (BSHM) has been an active research area where over the years, designers and researchers are enhancing the safety and durability of bridges by monitoring through advanced systems in science and technology. Many researchers are developing various techniques for BSHM, such as fuzzy pattern recognition by M. Reda & J. (2005), application of networks for structural health monitoring (Efstathiades et al., 2007), diffused ultrasonic waves techniques for detecting structural damage in the presence of measuring temperature changes (Lu & Michaels, 2005), vibration response detection-based strategies (Ghoshal et al., 2000 & M.A. Rumsey & Paquette, 2008). More recently, the development of quantifiable BSHM approaches has been closely joined with the advancement, efficiency and cost reductions of digital computing hardware. The civil engineering community have studied vibration-based damage assessment of buildings and bridge structures since the early 1980s (Farrar & Keith, 2007). Modal properties and quantities derived from these properties, such as curvature of mode shape and dynamic flexibility matrix indices, have been the principal features used to identify damage in bridge structures. However, challenges lie in the inconsistency of environmental and operating conditions of bridge monitoring applications. For vibration-based damage assessments, the physical structure's size also presents many practical challenges.

In recent years, the application of BSHM to existing bridges in performing a controlled extension of bridges with known problems has been dramatically increasing. Conducting visual inspection regularly and assessing the condition

of structural component damages such as cracking, spalling and deformations are also viewed as BSHM (Brown John, 2007). Bumbu and Butibam bridge are constantly exposing their components to destructive effects in the service life that eventually deteriorate the structural elements. That includes corrosion deterioration of the steel structures, fatigue-sensitive details including vehicle impacts, and lack of proper maintenance. This research is aimed to develop an effective and reliable approach to collecting data, managing, integrating and interpreting the performance of structural data for maximum helpful information at a reduced cost. However, the decision for a reliable remediation strategy for funding allocation also depends on the exactness of the condition assessment and diagnosis process (Rashidi and Gibson, 2011). This research, however, formulated and applied an SHM system to three different levels via visual inspection and condition assessment forms and integrating structural element condition ratings on the two bridges during the study period. The data was then complemented with the solid works software analysis.

Many bridges in developed countries apply innovative monitoring practices to their bridge infrastructures. However, Bumbu and Butibam bridges did not involve the SHM for various reasons. Firstly, even though the bridges have shown signs of deterioration, it is expensive to purchase sensors for the damages identified. SHM incorporates more than a single sensor and must have distributed data processing, extensive network communication, machine learning data diagnostics, web-based user interfaces and alerting. Secondly, compared to size, SHM is more appropriate to use on enormous and significant bridge structures, unlike Bumbu and Butibam bridges. Therefore, the methodologies identified and used on Bumbu and Butibam bridges are less costly and more effective and reliable for steel girder bridges, particularly for the case study. The results indicated that maintenance of steel girder bridges contributes to the overall condition assessment and rating. However, the safety and performance of the bridges rely primarily on the capacity of the steel girders.

1.2 Problem Statement

Better inspection and monitoring techniques are a need in PNG today for our deteriorating bridge infrastructures. Given its rugged terrain, PNG is connected by road networks, and bridge structures link most or all the centres. These bridge structures deteriorate over time as they are continually exposed to harsh environmental conditions. Most of the country's bridge infrastructures are significantly aged and need attention. This growing issue of aging infrastructure needs to be addressed, and one of the ways engineers are doing so is through structural health monitoring. That is why structural health monitoring of steel girder bridges under this case study applied the SHM system to three levels via visual inspection and condition assessment forms and integrated structural element condition ratings on the bridges. And these results were complemented by solid works modelling and analysis.

1.3 Objectives of the Research

It is a need for bridge owners and stakeholders to effectively monitor and inspect in-service bridge assets to continuously monitor bridge movements, vibrations and structural changes to identify potential failure modes. The information provided from monitoring are very useful for decision making about the current and future expenditure regarding maintenance requirements and the levels of service required on national road network. Therefore, the primary objective for this study is to develop condition assessment system for steel girder bridges to identify defects and deterioration, changes in structural behavior, and for tracking usage.

The specific tasks necessary to accomplish the primary objective for this case study are as follows:

1. To develop steel girder bridge condition assessment system
2. To apply the proposed assessment form in evaluating the condition of Bumbu and Butibam bridges of Lae City as pilot study.
3. To conduct finite element analysis on the two (2) pilot bridges as supplement to the proposed assessment system.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Most of the bridges in PNG constructed before Independence in 1975 by the Australian Government and on the main roads were generally permanent single-lane, concrete-deck, and composite steel girder bridges. These permanent bridges, such as Bumbu and Butibam, remain in service and are usually in good condition; nevertheless, the change in load-carrying capacity or resistance of the steel girders requires answers as they may not be suitable for the heavier and faster traffic. Therefore, monitoring a bridge improves knowledge and understanding of in-situ structural behaviour, detects damage at its onset, assures owners of the structure's strength and serviceability, reduces downtime, and improves maintenance practices and management of limited resources. According to Sikorsky et al. (1999), these questions regarding the change in load capacity or resistance of the structure (serviceability), the probability of failure of the system (reliability) and the duration to function continually as designed (durability) requires answers in precise terms. Also, given the current demand for the use of national roads and highways for the nation's economy and the country's well-being, the degree of safe mobility of the system needs to be maximised.

Steel Girder Bridge is typical on national roads and highways of PNG, and the girders are designed and constructed to carry the maximum T44 (44 tonnes) vehicle load (AS 5100 (2004)). However, in the remote areas and districts of PNG, depending on-road use, bridges are designed for the appropriate loading condition (vehicle loads). However, due to lack of proper maintenance, steel girders of bridges suffer a different degree of damage to varying bridge positions as they are exposed to environmental influences. And the steel girder affected by fatigue due to corrosion remains a significant concern for safety and durability, especially for those located close to marine environments. For example, Bumbu and Butibam bridges are located at a lower altitude and very close to the sea, which requires constant monitoring of bridge steel components.

Figure 1-4: Satellite view showing location of Bumbu and Butibam Bridge of Lae City.

Figure 1-4 shows the Bumbu and Butibam bridges located in the heart of the industrial city of Lae, PNG, at an altitude of 55m and close to the sea. These bridges were constructed in 1973 and 1997, respectively, and Bumbu Bridge is the oldest at 49 years.

According to Holemba G.A. (2011), the field investigations on the 21 flood-damaged bridges in PNG identified the resultant factors associated with a flood that caused the damages, such as scouring, bank erosion, debris impact, and blockages. The leading cause of the bridge damage was flooding. However, other factors were also identified as the root causes of the bridge damages made possible by flooding rivers. This research is essential as it will look more closely at the bridge's structural components to identify the problems at the earliest stage possible. The Department of Works will provide the necessary maintenance. Also, the bridge monitoring and condition assessment levels used in this pilot study and the condition rating used will significantly help improve inspection procedures and assist in prioritising bridge inspection and maintenance techniques. It will also assist in more scheduled maintenance, resulting in optimising maintenance costs and finally increasing the structure's reliability.

1.5 Scope of Study and Limitation

This case study is limited to the steel girder bridge of Bumbu and Butibam Bridge and covers:

- A desktop study collates all relevant data for Bumbu, and Butibam bridges, including bridge site visits and collecting bridge information and as-built specifications - no bridge data, drawings, and specifications are available in Department of Works archives.
- Complete a literature review of the common problems in steel girder bridges and their influence on load-carrying capacity. This study also reviewed measuring the bridge deflections methodology, including visual monitoring, condition assessment and rating techniques, including VicRoads Road Structure Inspection (VicRoads, 2011) to develop condition assessment forms. Develop a bridge inspection and condition assessment form for visual assessment and condition rating of the defects in the bridge structural elements.
- Conduct visual inspections and assess the structural components of the in-service Bumbu and Butibam Bridge of Lae City using the forms developed for this study and rate the overall condition of the bridges.
- Assess the load-carrying capacity and serviceability (deflection) of the in-service Butibam and Bumbu Bridge as part of the assessment under level 3 engineering investigation.
- Evaluate and verify the use of an assessment system by theoretical modelling and analysis using structural analysis tools and software, and make suggestions for future research and conclusions.

The research is limited to the study of composite steel girder bridges of Bumbu and Butibam. Mid-span deflection of the Bumbu Bridge was assessed for excessive vibrations under normal traffic load by a direct levelling survey. The load assessment for Butibam Bridge was considered part of this study for the load assessment of the two bridges. Some other limitations encountered in this study are limited finance and resources. Moreover, initial construction documents, including design and construction drawings of the two bridges, are not available to compare the as-built and condition measurement and assessment.

1.6 Conceptual Framework

The condition assessment forms in this study resulted after an extensive literature review of current practices in developed countries, especially Australia. The framework used to conceptualise this research is the comprehensive guide to the work implemented under this study, which is very important for the inspection and condition assessment of steel girder bridges in PNG. The application of the forms was used for the three levels, as shown in the conceptual framework in Figure 1-4. Further discussions on the framework, the three levels, and parameters involved in condition assessment are found in Chapter 3 Materials and Methodology.

Figure 1-5: Conceptual Framework for the Case Study.

1.7 Materials & Methods

Bridge condition assessment forms were the main instruments used in evaluating the condition of the steel girder bridge. Under an extensive literature review on current bridge monitoring and assessment techniques and procedures available in countries like Australia, the United States (US), some European countries, Japan, Hongkong, and China, the bridge condition assessment forms resulted in this study. According to Rashidi and Gibson (2011), various bridge health monitoring methodologies exist, and engineers usually follow procedures that best suit the monitoring purpose. The decision to develop and use the assessment forms is in line with the aims of this study which is to create a condition assessment system for steel girder bridges in Lae City to identify defects and deterioration, including changes in structural behaviour. This study adopted three levels of inspection and condition assessment. The idea of assessing the bridge in three levels is adapted from VicRoads Australia, which extracted the bridge inspection methods from the American Association of State Highway and Transportation (AASHTO) with slight changes in the structural condition rating. The three levels of bridge inspection and condition assessment are mostly unique because of the structural significance and material vulnerability factors, explained further in Chapter 3 Research Methodology and Materials. The three bridge condition assessment and rating levels are further discussed in Chapter 3.

However, other qualitative methods are used mainly in the third level of condition monitoring and assessment. The third engineering investigation level is by a qualitative method where it provides improved knowledge on the condition of the bridges, their load-carrying capacity, and their in-service performance that are not obtained from level 1 and level 2 monitoring. It was done using structural analysis tools and software such as Solid Works in evaluating applied load and vibrations, which are imperative to identify possible failure modes in the structure and supplement the results obtained from the new forms. The equipment, tools, structural analysis, and modelling software used to evaluate and validate the data collected in Level 1 and Level 2 are elaborated in Chapter 3, subsection 3.3.1.

Chapter 2 : Review of Related Literature

A bridge's primary purpose and function are to carry a service such as a highway or a railway traffic, footpath or public utilities, etc., over an obstacle and transfer the loads from the service to the foundations at the ground level. The relative importance of a bridge structure varies from project to project; however, all bridges are designed to satisfy specific bridge performance requirements, as noted by Ghasemi et al. (2009). Existing civil engineering infrastructures, including bridges, are significant in any transportation system and must be inspected and monitored at a particular frequency depending on their purpose and location. This chapter reviews related literature on structural health monitoring, common problems or defects in existing steel girder bridges, causes of bridge failures, bridge data collection and monitoring practices from a global perspective and a local perspective, and the risk and criticality assessment of bridge structures. Finally, this chapter also summarises the reviewed pieces of literature and their implications in this case study.

2.1 Structural Health Monitoring - Steel Girder Bridge

Structural Health Monitoring SHM is a development process of implementing a damage detection and classification approach for engineering structures. It is a powerful tool to ensure structural integrity and safety. SHM is a term used to describe a range of systems implemented on full-scale civil infrastructures to help inform engineers and asset owners regarding the 'fitness for purpose' of civil structures such as bridges and has become very popular over the recent decade. Moreover, in the current decade, various methods of SHM have been used to monitor changes in the state of in-service or existing infrastructures to learn about load and response mechanisms with timely information for safety and economical operation.

The literature reviewed shows that SHM happened a long time ago when engineers, architects and artisans were keen on observing the behaviour of built structures, discovered signs of damage or deterioration in extending knowledge, and improved the design of future facilities. Moreover, in the 1800s, tapering was done on train wheels to evaluate if the damage was present using the sound of a striking hammer. For instance, ancient builders observed and

recorded crack patterns in stone and masonry bridges. Longer spans and more slender arches sometimes fail during construction or after a short time (Levi & Salvadori, 1992). Evaluating and analysing the causes of the failures have led to new and improved design methods for future structures. Engineering curiosity and economic considerations drive the continuous improvement of the systems (Inaudi & Glisic, 2008).

Chang et al. (2003) define structural health monitoring as determining the location and severity of damage in buildings and bridges as they happen in real-time. SHM is defined by Dong & Song (2010) as a non-destructive in-situ structural method that uses a variety of sensors attached for sensing and evaluation or embedded. It is a structure in monitoring the structural response, analysing the structural characteristics in estimating the severity of damage/deterioration, and evaluating the structure in terms of response, capacity, and service life. A simple illustration of a wireless connected multi-sensor system for monitoring deflection, vibration and strain of a bridge element is shown in Figure 2.1. The data from these sensors are collected either continuously or periodically. They are stored, analysed, and sent to those in authority to inspect for maintenance and repair damaged components or future reference. In addition, the long-term process of SHM occasionally updates information regarding the structure's ability to perform its intended function under an operational environment.

Figure 2-1: Sensor Placement and data collection on bridge elements (Source: <https://www.concreteshowindia.com/blog/a-cost-effective-structural-health-monitoring-system-using-multi-sensing-approach/>)

Techniques for structural health monitoring can be physical or non-physical. Some use a modelling system to observe physical structure to predict responses, such as probabilistic, non-parametric and autoregressive methods. However, the former is where damage identification is likened to natural frequencies and mode shapes data between the healthy and damaged structural model (R.P. Bandara et al., 2014). Examples of this are vibration-based damaged identification, frequency response, mode shapes and modal flexibility, and modal stiffness methods. The application of SHM to existing bridges to detect damage to extend their life is increasing significantly in recent years (Kekare, Huddedar, & Bagde, 2014). The main reason for monitoring bridge structures is to obtain quantitative data about structural behaviour to confirm design assumptions and provide real-time feedback when assessing the current condition of existing bridges. The main stages in SHM systems are summarized in the flow chart in Figure 2-2, where damage identification diagnosis is paramount.

Figure 2-2: SHM System - A general flow chart (Source: Claudia Neves, 2017)

Monitoring of civil infrastructures assists engineers in making informed decisions for planning future maintenance or repair actions for existing bridges. In the latter, the monitoring system increases the structure's safety and provides early warning of a known deterioration. There are certain stages in SHM that consist of implementing a strategy to detect damage in bridge structures and incorporating sensing technologies. Thus, the primary step to identifying

damage in structures is to diagnose damage in structural systems. The diagnosis of a structural system to identify damage falls under the following levels (Claudia Neves, 2017):

- Level 1: Is the damage present in the structure? Where it provides information concerning the possible existence of damage in the structure.
- Level 2: What is the geometric location of the damage? It is where it adds to the knowledge in Level 1 by determining its location, and a structural model may be usually used for this.
- Level 3: What is the type of damage? It identifies the nature and type of the damage, e.g., crack, corrosion, etc.
- Level 4: What is the severity of the damage? This level allows the estimation of the size of the damage, and a model can describe the effect of damage, for instance, crack length or stiffness reduction.
- Level 5: What is the prediction of the remaining service life of the structure?

2.1.1 Bridge Structural Health Monitoring

Bridge Health Monitoring is a type of SHM and inspection technique to bridge structures. Bridge Structural Health Monitoring (BSHM) is the primary tool for detecting damage in an existing bridge structure and assessing its functionality. In bridge health monitoring, damage refers to the change in the material and the geometric properties of the structural components, including changes in the connections and details that adversely affect the bridge's current or future performance. Bridge health monitoring techniques and methods have increased in the recent decades with significant developments in sensing technologies, from conventional sensors of electrical resistance strain gauges to novel sensors of fibre optic gauges. This "smart" system used in monitoring bridge structures' health significantly applies to large bridge structures with significant strategic importance. The essential benefits of BSHM include:

- Understanding the in-situ structural behaviour of the structure
- Detecting the damage at its onset to prevent the structure from failure

- Giving assurance of a structure nearing the end of its service life
- Reducing the downtime in repair or upgrade works
- Improving maintenance and management strategies for better resource allocations.

Some technical review of literature outlined by Doebling et al. (1996) and Sohn et al. (2003) shows that studies related to damage identification of engineering structures are increasing in number. In the process of applying the SHM systems, researchers have identified many technical challenges, which include:

- Development of techniques in optimally defining the number and location of the sensors
- Identifying features that are sensitive to small levels of damage
- Ability to distinguish changes in these features caused by damage and those caused by changing environments, including the test conditions
- Progress of statistical methods to classify features from undamaged and damaged components
- Performance of comparative studies in identifying various damage methods to standard datasets

These topics are currently the focus of many industries in different research efforts, where the capabilities of SHM and Condition Monitoring (CM) are advancing. For instance, in bridge health monitoring, these systems are being designed to help bridge owners with up-to-date information on the bridge components deteriorating in their service and their continued safe performance and smooth operations for economic activities.

However, the primary step necessary in monitoring the health of a bridge is the 'traditional method' of visual inspection. Being the oldest, it is a simple method that is intuitive and straightforwardly provides components defect information, based solely on observation and conducted on a pre-set schedule. Matsumoto, Yamaguchi, & Yoshioka (2010) confirm that visual monitoring is the principal technique and is regarded as one of the basic techniques for assessing the condition of in-service bridges. Moreover, the visual monitoring technique is innate, thus providing information directly upon observation. However, due to

the complexity of modern design structures and know-how in construction, a visual inspection may not be practicable given accessibility restrictions. This method seemed to work fine back in the centuries, but that was when built structures were more straightforward than the ones made today.

This study considered visual inspection and monitoring defects in simple steel girder bridge components and applied other non-destructive techniques before using engineering analysis software. In PNG, “smart” monitoring systems are not in place for the health monitoring of bridges because the vast majority of the bridge stock comprises standard types (baileys, steel composite and trusses). They are simple structures with single structures or less than five spans. There are also various reasons why PNG cannot implement such systems, as they cannot afford them due to increasing theft and vandalism problems. The common issues affecting the service life of bridges are similar to most of the bridges in countries throughout the world.

2.2 Common Causes of Material Defects in Steel Girder Bridge

Deterioration in the components of bridge structures affects the overall safety and reliability of in-service bridges. Existing bridges in most developed countries are nearing their initial service design life. For instance, according to National Research Council Canada, one-third of Canada’s highway bridges have some structural or functional deficiencies and short remaining service life. Similarly, the bridges in the United States are no different, according to the ASCE Infrastructure Report Card (2017), where almost 4 out of 10 bridges in the U.S are 50 years or older of the total 614, 387 bridges, and 9.1% (56,007) were recorded to be structurally deficient in 2016.

Inspecting and maintaining defects, especially in bridge infrastructures, is very important because various deterioration mechanisms can lead to major defects and structural failure. For example, the collapse of Ponte Morandi in Genoa of Italy on 14 August 2018 killed 43 people, leading to a state of emergency in the Liguria region and extensive structural failure analysis. The bridge collapse was

due to concrete cracks, water intrusion, and corrosion of the internal steel of the cable-stayed bridge. Figure 2-2 shows the collapsed part in red.

Figure 2-3: The collapse part (shown in red) of the Ponte Morandi bridge in Genoa, Italy. (Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ponte_Morandi#cite_note-giorn-13)

According to Tavakkolizadeh & Saadatmanes (2003), the common problems affecting the performance of bridges in their service life are due to different factors on the steel, and concrete material relating to fatigue-sensitive details increase in vehicle loads, corrosion deterioration, and lack of proper maintenance. Although many factors affect bridge structures' structural integrity and safety, this study reviewed only fatigue-sensitive details, increase in vehicle loads, corrosion deterioration, and lack of proper maintenance.

2.2.1 Fatigue

In steel bridges, fatigue is among the most critical forms of damage. The accurate assessment or prediction of the steel bridge's fatigue damage status is still a challenging study (X.W. Ye et al., 2014). Fatigue is a localized and progressive process in which structural damage accumulates continuously due to the repetitive application of external loadings such as vehicles for steel bridges. The application of the load would not create any abnormal effects; however, over a long period, the strength and serviceability decrease, thus requiring novel methodologies and advanced technologies to seize the fatigue phenomenon and conduct reliable fatigue assessment methods. The common problems to all-steel bridges are fatigue and corrosion, and So K.L. et al. (2012) identified damages in steel girder bridges and proposed ways to manage better the issues. In the study, So K.L. et al. (2012) integrated the life-cycle management (LCM) concept on steel girders to map corrosion deterioration and fatigue damage prediction models with girders, as extending the life of the in-service bridge is becoming a concern worldwide in recent decades. The

integrated LCM due to corrosion and fatigue on steel bridge girders is shown in Figure 2.4.

Figure 2-4: The integrated Life Cycle Management due to corrosion and fatigue on steel bridges (Source: So K.L. et al. (2012))

Fatigue causes a significant problem in reducing a steel girder bridge's load-carrying capacity and increasing the remaining life of existing structures. It is important to identify the fatigue-prone details in a bridge to incorporate well-planned monitoring routines and better strengthening and repair schedules to maintain satisfactory performance in the service life. Thus, information about fatigue performance in existing bridges is vital for bridge owners and is helpful for bridge engineers and designers (Haghani, Al-Emrani, & Mohsen, 2012). Fatigue occurs due to the increase in traffic volume and axle weight of trucks where the load exceeds the maximum designed load. Fatigue depends on three parameters, as stated by Pipinato et al. (2012), and they are:

- The stress range due to traffic loads
- The geometry of the construction details
- Accumulation of stress cycle due to traffic over the years.

Fatigue damage cases have been investigated and reported for various bridge types, and the performance details of the existing steel and composite bridges by Al-Emrani (2006). More than 100 damage cases were studied and classified depending on the type of detail or mechanism behind the observed fatigue cracking. More than 90% of the reported cases had cracks induced by secondary effects from the study. This type of fatigue damage is often due to secondary restraining forces produced by unintentional and overlooked interactions of different members in the bridge. Fatigue cracks result from poor detailing, unstiffened gaps, and unexpected stiffness changes at various members' connections.

In steel bridges, fatigue cracks are induced by various factors such as defects in welding, changes in section details, the connection between floor beams and the main members that carry loads, including diaphragms and bracing connections. Both primary and secondary load effects cause fatigue cracks. Some bridges in the United States and Japan experienced fatigue cracks, according to Chajes, Mulderrig, Roexker, & Milius (2004), Fisher (1984), International Institute of Welding (1996) and Miki, Ito, & Sasaki (2003). For example, figure (2-4) illustrates fatigue from the interaction between stringers and floor beams, resulting in secondary out-of-plane bending of the floor beam. It also shows typical fatigue cracking in a floor beam welded to the primary girder connection.

2.2.1.1 Fatigue Evaluation

For existing bridges, fatigue analysis may not be a component of structure load rating. However, fatigue has a significant effect on bridge durability. There are two types of fatigue that can affect in-service bridge performance: load-induced fatigue and distortion induced fatigue. More information on fatigue evaluation is available in AASHTO's The Manual for Bridge Evaluation.

- **Load-Induced Fatigue**

Load-induced fatigue is the in-plane fatigue that occurs due to the repetitive variations of stress that may occur within a structure due to applied loads or environmental factors. Calculated stresses are compared to threshold limits for specific details to identify elements that may be subject to advanced deterioration. A typical threshold limit is available in Section 6 of the AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications (8). The stresses utilized in the evaluation can be fine-tuned through actual field measurements, which reduces the partial load factors used in the analysis or material testing. It determines the toughness characteristics of undocumented steels to better assess the susceptibility of detail to crack initiation/propagation. Suspicious fatigue information can either be remediated or be identified for evaluation during routine or special inspections.

- **Distortion-Induced Fatigue**

Distortion-induced fatigue is the fatigue that takes place due to out-of-plane distortion that occurs near unrestrained connection details. Identification of more information susceptible to distortion-induced fatigue is performed by evaluating details shown in the structural steel shop drawings for the existing bridge. While distortion-induced fatigue usually occurs early in the life of structures, an inspection to identify signs of distortion or cracking, no matter the bridge's age. Suspect information of distortion-induced fatigue can either be remediated or identified for evaluation during routine or special inspections.

2.2.2 Increase in Vehicle Loads

One of the main variables that affect bridge structures is traffic load. Bridges are designed based on standards or conservative assumptions regarding the intensity of applied loads and the bridge's structural response to these loads. According to (Kim, Sang-Hyo; Heo, Won-Ho; You, Dong-woo; Choi, Jae-Gu, 2017), bridge designs on safe and economical bridge infrastructure systems have served the public very well are not the most optimum approach to the

safety of existing bridges assessment. The design criteria to assess the protection and the nominal reduction of bridge load capacities for long service systems indicate that many need upgrading. The traffic loads on existing bridges are quite different from those of designed live loads because of the various traffic environments. Therefore, an existing bridge should get the required load capacity according to the extreme load effects that the bridge will experience from the actual traffic environment during its remaining service life for more rational infrastructure maintenance.

2.2.3 Corrosion

Corrosion is common to both steel and concrete components of a bridge structure and is one of the leading causes of deterioration in steel bridges. Corrosion in steel is the deterioration by chemical or electrochemical reaction resulting from exposure to air, moisture, industrial fumes and other chemicals and containments in the environment in which it is located. According to Queensland Bridge Inspection Manual (2004), corrosion only occurs when a steel component is not protected or if the protective coating wears or breaks off. A consequence of surface corrosion is deterioration in particular properties of the member cross-section, such as the section modulus or slenderness ratio. Such properties are critical in a member's ability to resist bending moments or axial forces.

Monitoring corrosion damage is critical as it affects the steel girder members. Since the use of steel has progressed from cast iron, wrought iron, rivet steel and plain carbon steel to notch tough low, temperature steel, thus decreasing the load-carrying capacity of the steel girders. As a result, buckling may occur with a load lower than the design load. For instance, uniform corrosion is a dominant type of corrosion in bridges, and its effects determine the remaining life of steel girder bridges under different environmental conditions (Sarifi and Paik (2010)). The study showed that generally, uniform corrosion decreased the thickness of both sides of plates in a steel box girder and the bottom flange of the box girder section, as can be seen in Figure 2-6, and an example calculation of loss of thickness of steel I-sections due to continuous deterioration is illustrated in a paper by Kulkarni SR (2004).

Figure 2-5: Model of corroded steel box girder cross-section. (Source: Sharifi and Paik, 2010)

Among typical types of damages, corrosion deterioration and fatigue damages in steel girder bridge structures are most common. Influenced mainly by environment and vehicle loadings and stress ranges over the years in operation. On the other hand, corrosion in concrete elements of a bridge structure is affected by the deterioration of reinforcement by electrolysis or oxidation. Figure 2-6 shows corrosion of reinforcement where the concrete surface above the reinforcement can crack, delaminate and spall off exposing the underlying reinforcement. The alkali content in concrete protects the reinforcement from corrosion, then moisture; oxygen or chloride ions above a particular concentration are dissolved in water and penetrate through the concrete to reinforcement. This protection breaks down, and corrosion starts.

Figure 2-6: A typical corrosion of reinforcement in concrete (Source: VicRoads, 2011)

According to VicRoads Road Structures Inspection Manual (2011), the defects common in steel are corrosion, permanent deformations, impact damage, cracking and loose connections. However, So K.L. et al. (2012) identified effective planning to maintain the bridge asset at a minimal cost by modelling corrosion deterioration and fatigue damage. The structure's remaining life is estimated. Lastly, lack of proper maintenance can also deteriorate steel structural components.

2.2.4 Lack of Proper Maintenance

Physical distress or damage and chemical deterioration of critical components affect the integrity and stability of composite steel girder bridge structures. Bridges function to transfer the load from the concrete deck to the steel girders. Then, the supports (piers and abutments) via connectors such as bolts and bearings carry the burdens and into the foundation. However, improper maintenance also leads to defects in steel and concrete structures. The critical signs of distress or damage and deterioration are included in inspection reports to identify any urgent concerns about the structural integrity when monitoring.

The pictures in Figure 2-7 shows typical elevation of a bridge and components, and maintenance of bridge structures is very important in extending life span of the bridge as well as for safety reasons.

Figure 2-7: Typical Elevation of Girder Bridge with main components.
(Source: <http://fgg-web.fgg.uni-lj.si/~pmoze/ESDEP/master/wg15b/10100.htm>)

Bridge structures are constructed with different materials, and the two common construction materials in the construction of highway bridges, of composite steel Girder Bridge, are steel and concrete. A typical cross-section of a single lane highway bridge is shown below. The deck must be strong enough to distribute the design or local load to the main girders.

Figure 2-8: A typical cross-section of a single carriageway highway bridge.
(Source: <http://fgg-web.fgg.uni-lj.si/~pmoze/ESDEP/master/wg15b/10100.htm>)

The issues relating to the structural integrity and failure of steel girder bridges deal with the ability of the structure to support a maximum designed load without breaking, tearing apart, or collapsing. In monitoring steel girder bridge infrastructures, identifying and knowing the material defects is the first and foremost step that is essential in assessing the condition of bridge infrastructures. Lack of maintenance or improper maintenance can lead to the following defects in both steel and concrete structures, as shown in Figure 2-9.

Figure 2-9: Typical types of damages in steel girder bridges. (Adapted from So K.L. et al. 2012)

2.3 Bridge Data Collection and Monitoring Practices

Inspecting a bridge and collecting data is essential in any Bridge Monitoring System (BMS), particularly for aged and deteriorated bridges. It is a pathway to condition rating, and the condition rating assessment and its accuracy are dependent on the quality of the inspection (Rashidi and Gibson, 2011). There are various bridge health monitoring and data collection practices worldwide, and engineers usually follow the procedures that best suit the monitoring purpose.

This study reviewed bridge monitoring to achieve the objective of visual monitoring and condition assessment of the bridge structures and components. It includes inspection practices and procedures of developed countries like Australia, the United States (US), some European countries, Japan, Hong Kong, and China. The study noted that most of these nations have road agencies at three levels of administration, namely, national, state and local. Most of the inspections are delegated to the state Department of Transports. In the US, few inspections are done at the national level or delegated to inspection consultants, other countries, and federal states and departments in Germany and France. Countries including Denmark, Finland, Germany, Norway, the United Kingdom and Canada have inspection manuals. Their road agencies carry out routine inspections at intervals of 1 to 3 years or detailed engineering inspections at 5- or 6-years intervals. However, according to federal regulations, the US has defined eight types of bridge inspections; where three of them are periodic, i.e., routine inspection, a fracture-critical inspection of structural members, and underwater inspection. In Germany, the federal standard for bridge inspection applies to federal roads, and local agencies do inspections of bridges on state roads or those on municipal roads (Consultant, University of Colorado, 2007). In the US, after the I-35W Mississippi River Bridge catastrophe, visual monitoring is slowly replaced by 'smart' monitoring systems where the structural members of the bridge are remotely monitored to extend bridge life and prevent catastrophic failures.

Others have their ways of monitoring bridge infrastructures. However, the majority of these countries, including the United States (US), Japan, Hong Kong, and China, have implemented 'smart' monitoring technology in most of their significant and complex structures as they can afford them. This study, however, will focus more on the visual bridge inspection and monitoring process of Australia because PNG adopts Australian Standards (AS) in the design of bridge structures. In addition, identifying the defects and rating the condition of bridge components done by VicRoads in Australia is suitable for PNG, except that the bridge structures in Australia are of different types. The following subsection will look more closely at Australia's roads and bridge asset monitoring practices. The road authorities in Australia have extracted bridge inspection methods from the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (Rashidi. However, M and Gibson P (2011), many agencies use their bridge inspection and condition rating strategies. Overall, element-based inspection is regarded as the most reliable technique for condition assessment.

2.3.1 Bridge Assessment by Visual Inspection

Bridge assessment and data collection by visual inspection are common and the only cost-effective way to detect potential problems. The first action to identify the defects and quantify the extent and severity of the defects is by visual inspection. Visual inspection also serves as the baseline to compare many other non-destructive evaluation techniques. In most cases, especially for in-service structures that do not have sensors installed during construction, visual inspection and assessment are vital to locating the possible damage before further assessment.

A detailed visual inspection is an element-by-element and "close-up" assessment of material defects, performance deficiencies and maintenance needs. Close-up means a distance that is close enough to determine the condition of the bridge structural element. The visual inspection, in most cases, is carried out within the arm's length of the element, which may involve making measurements by hand or tapping with a hammer. The equipment used to carry out this assessment is very appropriate and special.

Visual inspection and assessment are usually carried out by a professional engineer or technician with bridge inspection experience. In the process, the engineer identifies the different defects and deficiencies in materials and structural elements, where the data is then used to determine its Bridge Structure Condition Index (BSCI) (Ontario Bridge Inspection Manual (OSIM)). The bridge condition index is then used to determine if the structure needs further evaluation or if repair or maintenance is immediately required. Visual inspection of bridges is typically scheduled on a routine basis or biannually. For instance, bridges with spans more than 3 meters are inspected biennially (every two years) in Ontario, Canada. Based on the extent of the deterioration, the structural defects in the bridge are marked and recorded, and then the engineer can recommend additional testing (condition survey). A comprehensive approach to the close-up visual inspection and monitoring of bridge structures in Ontario is provided in OSIM (2008).

2.3.2 Bridge Assessment by Non-destructive Evaluation

More bridge inspection technologies have increased in the last decades, and most of these methods are used in inspecting bridge decks, abutments, and main reinforced concrete girders. NDE is a term used to describe measurements that are more quantitative and is used to determine properties of materials, such as fracture toughness, formability, and other physical characteristics. A classic example is the Schmidt/rebound hammer test, which measures the concrete surface hardness, and ultrasonic testing. NDE is included in bridge inspections as a means of structural condition assessment and is the most appropriate method to estimate the present condition of structural and non-structural components in bridges, thus identifying the location and extent of defects. The main advantage of NDT for bridge inspection is that it monitors a broader area in a relatively short time. The methods are repeatable, which means they are ideal for a periodic routine inspection of bridges. Another significant advantage of this group of tests is that they can be conducted with minimum intervention and damage to the structure.

2.3.3 SHM Systems in Bridge Health Monitoring

SHM system or smart technology is the process of implementing monitoring systems to measure or detect damages and structural responses in real-time. Incorporating SHM in bridge condition assessment and monitoring is imperative due to the subjective nature of visual inspections, where they are insufficient for providing a complete picture of the condition of a structure. Thus, researchers and bridge owners nowadays are more interested in monitoring the condition of structures to detect damage at early stages using ideal non-destructive damage detection 'smart systems.' The SHM or 'smart systems' for bridge health monitoring was developed and is constantly modified and optimized to generate objective measurements that aid in the decision-making process of infrastructure owners for maintenance and cost planning purposes.

A typical SHM system for bridges is given by the general layout depicted below.

Figure 2-10: General layout of permanent SHM system
(Source: <http://www.vce.at>, on 13th of May, 2013)

While the sensor technology has existed for many years, only recently has the supportive technology advanced far enough to develop further and implement such systems. The collapse of the I35W Mississippi River Bridge in Minnesota in 2007 raised the alarm, which killed 13 and injured 145 people. Other events of bridge collapses include a bridge in South Korea, killing 32 in 1994. The most

noted bridge collapse in 1967 was Silver Bridge in West Virginia, killing 46 people (Structural Integrity Systems, 1996) and recently, the collapse of the Ponte Morandi Bridge in Genoa, Italy, which killed 43 people (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ponte_Morandi, 2018). After these collapses, there has been a significant improvement in the methods and techniques, from conventional sensors of strain gauges resistant to electricity, strain gauges with vibrating wires, deflection transducers, anemometers accelerometers, etc. to new fibre optic sensors. A typical health monitoring system includes a sensor system, a data processing system (data acquisition, transmission and storage), and a system in evaluating the health of the bridge, which includes diagnostic algorithms and information management.

The first figure below shows a typical SHM data collection system and the second one outlines complete stages in bridge monitoring data collection systems.

Figure 2-11: A typical data collection SHM system (Source: www.scsolutions.com)

Figure 2-12: An overall schematic of SHM system showing office and field components
(Source: Lee, Yoon-Si, 2007)

Moreover, in the past, it was also recognized that conventional visual inspection-based methods get more objective by incorporating dynamic behaviour evaluation of an analyzed bridge structure, where tailored dynamic measurements based on structural mechanics principles are combined with numerical simulations. While the structural analysis in the first instance mirrors full-scale experimental monitoring, a finite element calculation complements the measured data and deepens the understanding of structural integrity. It leads to a decisive interpretation of results from an analyzed structure. For example, the key performance indicators used in dynamic monitoring, analyzing structural behaviour, performance and integrity, and determining the load-bearing capacity are outlined and explained in Figure 2-13 with their relevance in the civil engineering context.

Figure 2-13: Extraction of measured dynamic state variables according to BRIMOS - Analysis with regard to structural performance KPIs (Key Performance Indicators). (Source: Figueiredo, E et al, 2013)

Monitoring dynamic behaviour in bridge structural performance under ambient (environmentally excited vibrations) or typical operational loading conditions in existing bridge structures is critical to detecting any load-bearing capacity anomalies. Smart technology serves a wide range of applications for every phase of structural service life, and it is independent of the structural type of material.

2.4 Visual Inspection & Condition Assessment of Bridges in Australia

The study reveals that councils, rail operators, and state road authorities manage most bridges in Australia. The largest asset owner of bridges and culverts in Australia is the Australian Rail Track Corporation (ARTC), which manages 20,000 plus structures covering from Queensland to Perth. About

eight regional road authorities manage bridge and culvert structures, and they are ranked according to the number of bridges (and culverts) managed. The first three largest asset owners are VicRoads, Queensland Department of Transport and Main Roads (DTMR) and New South Wales (NSW) Roads and Maritime Services (RMS) (Sonnenberg, 2014). The inspection process helps the asset owners review and audit to build an accurate and up-to-date inventory of their structures. Also, to plan proactively for preventive maintenance, repair or replace deterioration members or assets, and, most importantly, identify work requirements. The inspections also audit past inspections. To ensure whether defects identified from the previous inspections have been addressed or not, and if it comes to deterioration.

The bridge inspection process for each state road authority's inspection manuals essentially has the same objective: to manage the risks associated with the assets. However, the extent and type of information that is collected differ. This study reviewed inspection manuals of the three largest state asset owners that the manuals reviewed have all evolved from the PONTIS system developed by American State Road Authorities (Sonnenberg, 2014) and are summarized in Table 2-1.

The manuals differ in terms of content, application, and approach. These cover structures, inspection levels, frequency and scope of the inspection, data collection requirements and condition state definitions, and recommended repair treatments. Each state's asset owners are responsible for the bridge, including culverts and roadside infrastructure associated with the roads under its control. VicRoads roads inspection has the most recent manual, including all significant assets to the scope of the manual, plus sign structures, retaining walls, weighbridges and lighting masts. The inspection manuals of Victorian and Queensland contain three levels of inspection, while in NSW are four. The manuals divide the levels of inspections into Routine Inspection, Condition Assessment and Detailed Engineering Inspections.

Table 2-1: The three largest state asset owners' inspection manuals (Adapted from Sonnenberg, 2014)

Road Asset Owners / Manuals	
VicRoads – Road Structures Inspection Manual - April 2011	This is the only inspection manual that covers all main structures along the roadside, including noise walls and lighting poles to complex bridges. It also contains relevant information with regard to policy, procedures and condition ratings associated with all types of routine inspections.
DTMR Bridge Inspection Manual - June 2004	The DTMR manual covers all bridge assets and large culverts and contain information relating to policy, deterioration mechanisms and inspection procedures for all types of routine inspections.
RMS RTA Bridge Inspection Procedure Manual - June 2007	This manual contains information relating only to inspection procedure and condition rating for bridges and large culverts. For information relating to policy, RMS refers to its RTA Bridge Inventory, Inspection and Condition Rating Policy as of 2011.

Table 2-2 below shows the inspection levels and inspection type, while Table 2-3 shows the frequency of bridge inspection in each state, almost the same as the three manuals reviewed. Queensland intends to extend the frequency of level 2 inspections. Depending on the location of components and condition of the structure to be inspected.

Table 2-2: Australian State Bridge Inspection Levels Adapted from Sonnenberg, 2014

Inspection Level	State	Inspection Type
Level 1	Victoria Queensland New South Wales	Visual inspection for routine maintenance issues and possible further inspection.
Level 2	Victoria Queensland New South Wales	Visual inspection to assess the condition rating of the structure and its components.
Level 3	Victoria Queensland New South Wales	Detailed engineering inspection to target specific issues and assess load-carrying capacity of a structure or group of structures Detailed engineering inspection to identify and quantify deterioration and provide a load rating if required. Structural safety inspection of full structure or specific elements to identify and quantify structural issues.
Level 4	New South Wales	Load capacity assessment to determine the load capacity of the bridge.

The inspection procedure differs slightly from state to state in its scope of work and asset databases used by the Australian authorities. The predominant local factors such as structure and waterway types influence the scope of inspection from state to state. For all states, the scope for a level 1 inspection is identifying obvious vehicle damages, deformations and other safety issues or signs required for maintenance and further inspection. The data collected in the level 1 inspection is similar in Queensland and Victoria, while in NSW, recording is only for primary defects. An inspector must record information on maintenance problems and other apparent signs of damage or deterioration of structures in both Victoria and Queensland. The inspectors then recommend maintenance works or further inspection and verify generic set data contained in the database.

Table 2-3: Frequency of Inspections Adapted from Sonnenberg, 2014

Inspection Level	State	Frequency
Level 1	Victoria	6 months maximum
	Queensland	6-12 months
	New South Wales	According to road maintenance
Level 2	Victoria	2 years – (1-5 years) *
	Queensland	2 years – (1-8 years) *
	New South Wales	2 years – (1-4 years) *
Level 3 &4 (NSW only)	Victoria	When required
	Queensland	When required
	New South Wales	When required
* The absolute maximum duration between level 2 inspections of structures.		
* This is dependent on structure type, condition and location.		

The data collection is similar in NSW and Victoria for level two inspections, while collecting the data in Queensland is more specific to each part of the structure. However, the generic asset and component data are verified in all three state authorities and component or structure condition ratings are also

provided. There are differences in how the bridge condition data is collected and recorded, as well as in the way they record the generic data.

Table 2-4: Level 2 Inspection Scope (Adapted from Sonnenberg, 2014)

Task	Vic.	Qld	NSW
Condition rating of components	X	X	X
Condition rating of whole structure	X	X	X
Identify structural defects	X	X	X
Identify structures/components for further inspection	X	X	X
Identify structure/components	X	X	X
Identify supplementary testing	X	X	X
Obtain photographic record	X	X	X
Sounding of timber members using hammer			X
Timber drilling to test deterioration		X	*
Sounding to measure waterway profile		X	
Underwater inspection		*	*
Recommend maintenance/repair	X	X	X
Recommend timeframe for maintenance/repairs	X	X	X
X This item is part of the scope of every level 2 inspection * This item is part of the scope of some level 2 inspections			

Generic data includes recording the structure's GPS location, taking photographs and recommending actions for defects. GPS coordinates of structures are required in Victoria and NSW, while not in Queensland. The level 2 scope of work for an inspection varies significantly across the authorities (Table 2-4). The level 3 inspection scopes are similar in all states, except for Victoria, where an assessment of load capacity forms part of the scope of work. A load assessment specification is not part of the standard scope for Queensland. Still, for NSW, a level 3 inspection is not inclusive of load assessment as this is the entire scope of inspection in the fourth level (level 4).

The requirements for photographic records are different for each state. In Victoria, a photograph is required for condition state 3 or 4 defects, while in Queensland, photos are required for state 4 defects. In NSW, there is no requirement for obtaining a photographic record of defects. The data recorded for levels 3 or 4 inspections are based on the scope of the inspection and the discretion of the engineer that carries out the inspection. VicRoads, DTMR and RMS provide paper-based inspection where forms are completed on-site and entered later into the bridge asset database. Also, there are guidelines for each inspection in rating the condition of the structural members and components.

This study adopted some of the VicRoads Bridge monitoring processes. The Bridge Inspection Manual for VicRoads was developed in 1995 and was based on the US "PONTIS" Bridge Management System. It uses the Road Asset System (RAS), a computerised inventory system to store structural inspection and inventory data.

There are three parts to the manual. Part one is the Road Structure Inspection Policy, followed by Part Two – Road Structure Inspection Procedures and Part Three- Condition Rating of structure components. VicRoads has its road structures inspection policy established where systematically monitoring the condition of all structures to ensure structural integrity and safety of users. The information from the inspection provides data for maintenance programs or load capacity assessment activities which include all bridge structures. The VicRoads Roads Structure Inspection program comprises:

- Routine maintenance inspection Level 1 is carried out for all road structures to check for structural integrity and general serviceability of the structures for road users;
- The Road structure condition inspection Level 2 is managed on a State-wide basis to provide a consistent visual assessment of the condition of each structure and its principal components.
- Detailed Engineering inspection Level 3 is conducted on an as-requested basis to respond to observation of a vital defect by a level 1 or 2 inspection or other sources.

There are three parts to the VicRoads Road Structure Inspection Manual. The forms or data sheets used by VicRoads for bridges and culverts are; Inventory and photographic bridges record sheet, Bridge inspector's sheet, Condition rating sheet, Structure defect sheet, Structure information sheet, and Sketch sheet.

2.5 Current Conditions of Bridges in PNG and Inspection Practices

Bridge design in PNG is according to design procedures as set out in bridge design codes of PNG, which incorporates Australian Standards (AS) too. According to the standards, the current maximum designed load for the bridge is T44 (44tonnes) with 6-axle wheels for national roads and highways. Bridges constructed on main roads before Independence in 1975 were generally permanent single-lane, concrete-deck, composite steel girders. However, bridges on rural roads were mostly constructed with timber decks. As pointed out by a Technical Assistance Consultant's Report by Cardno Emerging Markets (Australia) Pty Ltd (2011), most of these permanent bridges remain in service and are generally in good condition.

Nevertheless, these bridges now require replacement as they are not suitable for heavier and faster traffic on the sealed upgraded roads. Moreover, many Bailey bridges were constructed before and after Independence, initially using Super Bailey and later Compact 100 Bailey. All are designed for a maximum load of T33 (33 tonnes) along national highways and provincial roads, T22 (22 tonnes) for less important roads and T11 (11 tonnes) for secondary roads. At the same time, bridges on roads that were upgraded to sealed standards were replaced by two-lane permanent bridges as funding permitted. For example, most bridges on the Highlands Highway between Nadzab and Kassam Pass were replaced by two-lane bridges in about 1978, except for the larger single-lane bridges.

Even though the national highways and main roads have now been upgraded to sealed standards resulting in increased vehicle traffic and higher vehicle speeds, those rehabilitation projects did not include the replacement of the Bailey bridges. Hence many Bailey bridges on essential roads are approaching

their effective life, and combined with the damage from the inevitable vehicle impact accidents, require replacement. All these bridges, including others, are adversely affected by fatigue, increased service loads on the bridge, corrosion deterioration due to exposed weather conditions, hydraulic related causes and lack of proper maintenance. Moreover, bridge inspection and monitoring are often overlooked where corrosion deterioration and fatigue are familiar sources of structural failures. Nevertheless, the common cause of bridge failure and collapse in PNG is heavy rain and flooding or issues relating to hydraulics such as scouring. Almost 782 bridges were identified on National Route and Main Roads in PNG, according to Cardno Emerging Markets Pty Ltd (2011) technical report. However, it is indicated that the Bridge Assets Management System (BAMS) is incomplete. In many cases also unreliable where the data describing each of the 728 bridges are incorrect – bridges in actual “poor” conditions were designated as “good”, and vice versa. Table 2-5 provides general information on the main issues of structural and physical damages found on bridges in Lae City and PNG.

Table 2-5: General information on main issues of structural and physical damages found on bridges in Lae City and PNG

Bridge Name	Length (m)	Bridge Type	Types of damages
Anglimp Bridge	54	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion
Bumbu Bridge	49.4	Girder	Deformation, collision, steel corrosion, fatigue, cracking, scouring, spalling
Butibam Bridge	81.4	Girder	Collision, steel corrosion
Cedar Bridge	35.7	Beam/Slab	Steel corrosion, concrete cracking
Daulom Bridge	36.6	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Iruan Bridge	125	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Kesuai Bridge	73.5	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Leron Bridge	?	Girder	Steel corrosion, concrete cracking, scouring
Markham Bridge	515	Beam/Slab	Steel corrosion, concrete cracking
Mea Bridge	146	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Menia Bridge	45.7	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Nebilyer Bridge	50	Warren Truss	Steel corrosion, deformation, steel corrosion
Pine Tops Bridge	27.4	Beam/Slab	Scouring, deformation, steel corrosion
Rumu Bridge	30	Beam/Slab	Steel corrosion, concrete cracking

Sausi Bridge	137	Bailey Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Surinam Bridge	49.5	Warren Truss	Steel corrosion, collision, deformation
Waterbung Bridge	36.8	Beam/Slab	Steel corrosion, concrete cracking, scoring
Yalu Bridge	?	Girder	Steel corrosion, concrete cracking, scouring

From literature and other related resources in PNG, almost all the bridge collapse in the country's history is mainly due to inadequate hydrological assessment in the first place and subsequent climate change impacts. For instance, the Gusap and Bora bridges along the Ramu Highway of Lae and Madang have collapsed due to heavy rain and flooding, while four bridges in the Milne Bay Province collapsed due to cyclone. The bridge collapse is also due to flood and hydraulic effects such as scouring pier and abutments supports. Scouring is the removal of sediments such as sand and rocks from around bridge abutments or piers caused by fast-moving water, which creates holes compromising the structure's integrity. For example, the Ok Tedi River Bridge in the Western Province collapsed many times due to the scouring effects of the bridge abutments.

The principal agency responsible for infrastructure inspection and maintenance in PNG is the Department of Works. It is one of the oldest PNG government organizations, with offices in almost all provinces in the country. According to 2007 DOW data, the agency is responsible for maintaining approximately 8738.46 kilometres of roads throughout the country. Within this sketch of road networks, there are road infrastructures such as bridges and culverts, which DOW is responsible for maintaining to ensure that existing road and bridge networks are trafficable and safe. However, Bridge inspection in PNG is mostly carried out when there is a significant collapse due to corrosion or flood or when there is a particular need, for example, to transport a heavy load more than the designed load. Scheduled inspection and maintenance are mostly neglected. The DOW Consultants, however, use a bridge inspection form, and this form is available in the Appendices 3.

2.6 Overview of Structural Analysis and Modelling Software

2.6.1 Micro-Strand Structural Analysis Software

Micro-strand is a powerful general-purpose structural analysis package with built-in steel members and connection design. It features nonlinear and buckling analysis, integrated steel connection design and allows engineers to export to other engineering formats. The overall purpose of Micro-Strand structural analysis software is to efficiently model any structure, including bridges, which makes time-consuming analyses relatively simple. All that is required to complete an analysis is to define the vital bridge parameters. Also, to maintain an accurate as-built record, Micro-strand reality modelling solutions allows engineers to leverage and rapidly create detailed and precise geometry.

- **Capabilities**

Micro-strand capabilities include analysing gravity and lateral load, where structures are analysed for various loading conditions. It contains dead and live loads, including skip conditions, combined with lateral loads, including wind and seismic. Moreover, it complies with seismic requirements, design and analyse with finite elements, design cold-formed steel members, design lateral resisting frames, design to international standards, produce structural design documentation, and share structural models.

Generate design loads and load combinations

The built-in load generators apply the code-prescribed wind and seismic loads to the structure. Then the relevant loading parameters are automatically calculated based on the structural geometry, mass, and selected building code provisions without the need for separate hand calculations. These load combination generators combine these lateral load cases with gravity and other load types.

Integrate steel connection designs

Integrated steel connection design is a design of structural steel connections within a single integrated environment. It provides a transfer of load to joint geometry, member sizes, and joint forces from the 3D analysis directly to the steel connection design application. It allows for the efficient reuse of information and reduces the rework required when the structure changes.

Figure 2-14: General flowchart illustrating the overall operation of Micro-Strand Analysis

2.6.2 SolidWorks Modelling & Simulation

SolidWorks is modelling computer-aided engineering and design software. It is essentially a three-dimensional solid model component system and is an upgraded version of the computer-aided design software modelling system developed by the Windows operating system. Built-in parametric approach, SolidWorks comes with powerful modelling functions and efficient algorithms, making it an accepted leader among many 3D modelling tools. There are unique modular features in SolidWorks. For example, the sketch drawing is the starting point for complex building models, which simplifies and outlines the most compact, clear 2D line drawings. In the 3D modelling section, sketching, 3D modelling and drawing at both component and assembly levels are seamlessly integrated. These modules can be switched and modified, and their parts models, drawings, and assemblies are fully associative. As such, modifications to the model enable simultaneous updates and redesign.

SolidWorks Simulation stores and organises the entire data associated with a structural analysis. The study is also used to specify the type of analysis, including static, frequency, buckling, thermal drop test, fatigue, nonlinear linear dynamic and pressure vessel design. However, for bridge analysis, static analysis is of extreme importance.

Figure 2-15: Typical bridge stress analysis in SolidWorks

2.6.3 Finite Element Modelling

- Basic Concepts

The finite element method is also an approximate structural analysis method. In this method, structures are generally subdivided into many small finite elements. The deformation within each finite element is represented by approximate displacement functions, typically simple polynomials. The model is assembled by considering the nodes' equilibrium and displacement compatibility conditions. The accuracy is generally increased by increasing the number of elements of the finite element solution, the finite element mesh density. Engineers should realize that using too few finite elements in bridge analysis may induce a significant error. There are several different applications of the finite element method used in bridge analysis; these include 2D grid analysis methods, plate and eccentric beam analysis methods, generalized grid analysis methods, and 3D FEM analysis methods. Each is described in subsequent sections of this document.

- 2D Grid Analysis Method

2D Grid Analysis Method is the plane grid or grillage analysis method. This method is often used in steel bridge design and analysis. In this methodology, the structure is divided into plane grid elements. These elements often feature three degrees of freedom at each node (the vertical displacement and about the longitudinal and transverse axes is the rotation angles). If a 2D grid analysis is performed using general FEM software, the elements may feature six or more degrees of freedom at each node (see also Section 1.2.4). However, the primary response to gravity loads in a plane grid analysis is addressed by only the three degrees of freedom mentioned above. Modelling parameters are often set following simplified guidelines such as those provided in Articles 4.6.3.3.1 and C4.6.3.3.1 of the AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications (8). Live load distribution typically involves using live load distribution factors (as provided in Section 4 of the AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications).

See also Section 3.11 and Section 3.12 of this document for further discussion of recent and future developments in 2D grid modelling.

2.6.4. Plate and Eccentric Beam Analysis Methods

It is a variant of a 2D grid/grillage analysis model. The deck is modelled using plate or shell elements. In contrast, the girders and cross-frames are modelled through the representation of the offset of the neutral axis of the girder to the beam elements offset from the plate elements or cross-frame from the neutral axis of the deck. This approach is discussed in Article C4.6.3.3.1 of the *AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications (8)*. The length between the centroids of the girder and deck sections is called the offset length. The method is somewhat more refined than the traditional 2D grid method in terms of both the stiffness model and the ability of the model to distribute the live load based on relative stiffness rather than through live load distribution factors. For this modelling approach the beam and plate element internal forces must be eccentrically transformed to obtain the composite girder internal forces (bending moment and shear) used in the bridge design.

2.6.5 Generalized Grid Analysis Method

It is a 2D grid analysis modification, where more degrees of freedom are modelled for the analysis. These include modelling of cross-frames or diaphragms with consideration of shear deformation and flexural deformation, modelling of girder supports, its lateral bracing, the diaphragms at their physical elevation within the structure or cross-frames, or combination thereof. The warping of open cross-section members (such as I-shaped girders) is included explicitly in the derivation of the element used to model the girders in the analysis. This type of analysis is vital, particularly for studying structures where torsion is a significant consideration (such as curved and skewed I-girder bridges). At this time, the Generalized Grid Analysis method is used only for academic research projects.

2.6.6 3D FEM Analysis Method

The category 3D FEM Analysis methods are meant to encompass any analysis/design method that includes a computerized structural analysis model where the superstructure is modelled fully in three dimensions. It includes: modelling of girder flanges using line/beam elements or plate/shell/solid type elements, modelling of girder webs using plate/shell/solid type elements; modelling of cross-frames or diaphragms using line/beam, truss, or plate/shell/solid type elements (as appropriate); and modelling of the deck using plate/shell/solid elements. However, this method is the “most accurate” analysis method available to most practising bridge design engineers. It is also typically time-consuming and complicated and is most appropriate for complicated bridges (e.g., bridges with severe curvature or skew, or both, unusual framing plans, unusual support/substructure conditions, or other complicating features). 3D analysis methods are also helpful in performing refined local stress analysis of complex structural details.

Also, there are some complicating factors associated with 3D analysis methods. For instance, in a 3D analysis, girder moments and shears are not directly calculated. The model shows stresses in flanges, webs, and deck elements. If the designer wishes to consider girder moments and shears, some conversion/integration is needed to get the stresses over the depth of the girder cross-section. It can be a significant undertaking, particularly concerning proper proportioning of deck stresses and deck section properties to individual girders.

When and how to refine a 3D FEM analysis for engineering design is a controversial issue, and such an approach has not been fully incorporated into the AASHTO specifications to date. The typical AASHTO methodology for design is generally based on the assessment of nominal (average) stresses calculated by simplified methods, such as P/A or Mc/I , and not localized peak stresses obtained by shell- or solid-based finite element models. Refined analysis can provide substantially more detailed and accurate information about the stress state of the structure and allow for more cost-effective and reliable design, but this often comes with increased engineering effort and increased potential for error. The results are usually more sensitive to the input

parameters and the mathematical assumptions employed by the software. For instance, a given element will have a unique formulation, interpolation, integration and software implementation, all of which will affect results. The engineer must understand the assumptions and limitations to ensure correct application. These results are often difficult for the engineer to verify directly by independent calculations, so special procedures must often be employed to verify the accuracy of modelling.

Chapter 3 : Research Methodology and Materials

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the research methodology applied with the assistance of a study workflow diagram. It outlines the development process of the Steel Girder Bridge Condition Assessment Forms (SGBCAF) with the guidance of a schematic diagram, the design that this study adopted, and how the forms were created and applied in this case study to accomplish the objectives stated in the first chapter. The chapter also presents the three different levels of steel girder bridge condition assessments designed for this case study. It discusses monitoring individual bridge structural components concerning the structural significance, material vulnerability, and casual factors to determine the overall condition rating of a steel girder bridge. The forms, equipment, tools and structural analysis and modelling software used to evaluate and validate the data collected in the three (3) levels are also discussed in this chapter.

This case study of SGBCA for Butibam and Bumbu Bridge applied both qualitative and quantitative analysis methods. Qualitative analysis is especially done in the visual observation and condition rating of the bridge structural elements from newly developed forms. The condition assessment forms were developed and applied after an extensive literature review on related monitoring methodologies and practices around the globe, mainly in Australia. The new forms developed were categorized into 3 Levels of condition assessment. The 1st and 2nd levels applied qualitative analysis by visual observation using and condition rating of the structural elements, while the 3rd engineering investigation and evaluation level used qualitative methods. It shows the structural analysis modelling and simulation software's, that provided improved knowledge on the condition of the bridges, their load carrying capacity, and service performance.

After a thorough understanding of the literature reviewed, a method of steel girder bridge condition assessment system was developed and applied to this pilot study. The conceptual framework in Figure 3-1 shows the guiding concept

used for the Steel Girder Bridge Condition Assessment (SGBCA) Method and outlines the main activities undertaken in the case study to achieve the objectives of the study.

Figure 3-1: Study workflow diagram for the Steel Girder Bridge Condition Assessment

Level 1 Routine Inspection and Condition Assessment is the initial stage for identifying the structural condition and features of a bridge. In this stage of inspection, bridge components are visually inspected to check the general

serviceability of the structure for apparent signs of defects and damages, which may affect the immediate safety of road users. The Level 2 Detailed Inspection and Condition Rating is to verify and validate in more detail the deficiencies or defects noted during the Level 1 inspection and condition assessment. The detailed purpose of the second level was to assess and rate the condition of each bridge structural component to determine its condition index and to obtain the Structural Health Index (SHI) and the Overall Structure Condition Index (OSCI), including the Priority Index (PI). Various methodologies may be considered as third-level evaluation for bridge condition assessment. However, for this case study, the Level 3 procedure refers to using available tools and software to conduct structural analysis and validate the results obtained in the first and second levels. The outcome of this analysis and evaluation is the determination of the structural capacities of the bridge structures.

In line with the research problem statement, aging or deteriorating infrastructures require attention for mitigation and rectification of the common problems and factors contributing to the deterioration of the steel girder bridge in Lae City and PNG. Consequently, this study identified common factors contributing to the deterioration of structural components and how a monitoring system or procedure may assess and determine the SHI, OSCI, and PI for planning and maintenance purposes.

Moreover, this study's Level 1 and Level 2 stages realised the 'traditional method' of visual inspections and condition assessment of the structural components. After applying the first and second Level of SGBCAFs, the results were validated and synthesised with results obtained from the third Level of evaluation using Micro-Strand and SolidWorks structural analysis and modelling simulation software. Nevertheless, deflection of the Bumbu Bridge was also monitored by direct level surveying method.

3.1.1 General Bridge Information for Bumbu and Butibam Bridge

The study utilized the general bridge data information from Department of Works form and gathered the following information for the Butibam and Bumbu Bridge.

Table 3-1: General Bridge Information – Bridge geometry and parameters for Bumbu & Butibam

General Bridge Data													
No	Bridge Name	Road Name	River Name	Bridge Geometry									Est. Average
				No. of Lanes	No. of Walkways	No. of Spans	Span Length (m)	Overall Length (m)	Vertical Overhead Clearance (m)	Water Way Clearance (m)	Kerb to kerb width (m)	Clear vehicle width (m)	Vehicles per day
1	Butibam	Butibam	Bumbu	2	2	3	24.7	81.4	N/A	9.4	12.1	10.8	201-1000
							32						
							24.7						
2	Bumbu	Milford Haven	Bumbu	2	2	2	24.7	49.4	N/A	7.3	8.2	7.5	201-1000
							24.7						

The Butibam and Bumbu Bridge are two lanes on the same Bumbu River. Butibam Bridge is in its seventeen-year service and is 81.4 metres long with three spans supported by triple column piers. The Bumbu Bridge is 24.7 meters on each side of the mid-span support, and the deck slab is not continuous.

Figure 3-2: The cross-sectional view of Butibam Bridge

Figure 3-3: The Cross-sectional view of Bumbu Bridge

The total length of the bridge is approximately 50 meters. Both bridges are at skewed angles and estimate vehicles per day of more than 600. The last maintenance dates for the bridges are not known. The location readings, easting and northings are presented in the figure shown below, with Butibam's Easting and Northing of 501692 and 9256230 taken on the North abutment end. Likewise, Bumbu is 499838 and 9258711, easting and northing respectively. Butibam Bridge was constructed in 1997, while Bumbu Bridge was built in 1973 and is in 42 years of service. Bumbu was the oldest bridge compared to Butibam.

Table 3-2: General Bridge Information – GPS Location and Bridge History

General Bridge Data												
				GPS Data			Bridge History					
No	Bridge Name	Road Name	River Name	Eastings	Northings	Altitude (m)	Type of Bridge	Year of Construction	Year of last major	Terrain crossed	Bridge deck construction from	Bridge construction type (BTC)
1	Butibam	Butibam	Bumbu	501692	9256230	55	Standard	1997	?	River	Continue	Bracings
2	Bumbu	Milford Haven	Bumbu	499838	9258711	55	Standard	1973	?	River	Not continue	Bracings

Table 3-3: General Bridge Information – Span Data

Span Data										
No	Bridge Name	Parapet	Deck Wearing Surface	Deck Material	Deck Drainage	Expansion Joint Type	Main Member Type	Main Member Material	Secondary Member Type	Other Member Type
1	Butibam	Rails	Bitumen	Concrete/Steel	Deck Crossfall	Bitumen Filled	Beam	Steel	Steel	Bracing
2	Bumbu	Rails	Bitumen	Concrete/Steel	Scuppers	Air (open) gap	Beam	Steel	Steel	Bracing

The prominent members of the bridges are steel beams (girder) with cross beams and channel bracings. The surfaces are bitumen with deck drainages and rubber or bitumen expansion joints. Bumbu Bridge has an open gap for the non-continuous deck slab, and both have kerb and rail barriers and monorails on both upstream and downstream footways. The figures below show the abutment, pier and miscellaneous data, respectively. Bumbu Bridge drawings are not available.

Table 3-4: General Bridge Information – Abutment Data

Abutment Data								
No	Bridge Name	Abutment Type	Abutment Material	Abutment Foundation	Bearing Type - Abutment	Restraint Type - Abutments	Scour Protection - Abutments	Bank/Slope Protection
1	Butibam	Standard	Concrete/Gabions	Piles	Elastomeric	Lateral	Gabions	Gabions
2	Bumbu	Standard	Concrete/Gabions	Piles	Elastomeric	Lateral	Concrete segments	Concrete segments

Both bridges have the standard abutment and elastomeric bearings with laterally strains on one side of the abutments. The middle pier connections are fixed bolted connections to the pier crossheads. Since drawings are not available for the Bumbu Bridge assumption, the bridge's foundation is similar to the Butibam pile foundation.

Table 3-5: General Bridge Information – Bridge Pier Data

Bridge Pier Data							
No	Bridge Name	Pier Type	Pier Material	Pier Foundation Type	Bearing Type - Piers	Restraint Type - Piers	Scour Protection - Piers
1	Butibam	Multiple Columns	Concrete/ Steel	Not Known	Elastomeric	Hinge	Gabions
2	Bumbu	Single Columns	Concrete/ Steel	Not Known	Plate	Pinned	Gabions/ Concrete

Butibam has three (3) column concrete piers while Bumbu has a single column pier.

Table 3-6: General Bridge Information – Bridge Approach & Miscellaneous Data

General Bridge Data													
No	Bridge Name	APPROACH DATA				WATERWAY DATA			MISCELLANEOUS DATA				
		Guard Railings	Fender Type	Road		River Training Type	River Training Material	River Type	Loading	Drawing		Flood Clearance	Speed Limit
				Sealed Surface?	Is approach on bend?					Design Available?	As-Built Available?	Free Board (m)	Safe or Legal Speed (km/h)
1	Butibam	Rails	Concrete	Yes	Slight bend	None	Other	Straight	Safe or legal load (tonnes)	Yes	Yes	N/A	25
2	Bumbu	Rails	Concrete	Yes	Slight bend	Wall	Steel	Meanderi	Safe or legal load (tonnes)	No	No	N/A	25

3.2 Steel Girder Bridge Condition Assessment (SGBCA) Method

The SGBCA study workflow in Figure 3-1 is categorized into three levels: Level 1 Routine Inspection and Condition Assessment, Level 2 Bridge Structure Detailed Inspection and Condition Rating, and Level 3 Engineering Analysis and Safety Evaluation. It clearly shows the levels of visual inspection undertaken for SGBCA in Levels 1st, 2nd and the 3rd level of engineering analysis and safety evaluation. The SGBCA levels were adopted and implemented after the Australian State Bridge Inspection Manuals literature review, including VicRoads Roads Structures Inspection Manual (2011).

This study developed its forms from the reviewed inspection data collection sheets from VicRoads and DOW. The schematic diagram in Figure 3-2 shows the conceptualization process of SGBCA Forms for this study.

Figure 3-4: Development process of SGBCA Forms

As emphasised in the literature review, VicRoads is one of Australia's top asset owners from the eight regional road authorities. VicRoads manages more bridge and culvert structures than the others. Because of that, it has an inspection process, which helps in reviewing and auditing to build an up-to-date inventory of its structures. Moreover, it helps proactively plan for maintenance and repair or replacing of deterioration members and, most importantly, identify work requirements. VicRoads Road Structure Condition Inspection Manual evolved from the "PONTIS" Bridge Management System developed by American State Road Authorities and was developed in 1995. It uses the Road Asset System (RAS), a computerised inventory system to store structural inspection and inventory data. VicRoads in Australia has its policy for road structure inspection and uses several data sheets in bridge inspection and condition rating. VicRoads has separate forms for each parameter, such as bridge data and photographic records, condition rating, structure defect sheet, etc.

Table 3-7: Shows the parameters identified and selected for SGBCA of Bumbu and Butibam Bridge

					VicRoads	DOW	New Forms
Bridge Inspection Levels					3	None	3
Bridge Inspection forms					>4	1	3
Bridge General Information							
	Bridge Name				√	√	√
	Bridge ID				√	√	√
	Road Name				√	√	√
	Road Number				√	√	√
	Latitude & Longitude				√	√	√
	Overall Length				√	√	√
	Number of spans				√	√	√
	Kerb to kerb width (m)				√	√	√
	Estimated vehicles per day				√	√	√
	Age of bridge				√	√	√
	Bridge Type				√	√	√
	Soil Type					√	√
Bridge Span Data						√	√
Bridge Abutment Data						√	√
Bridge Pier Data						√	√
Bridge Miscellaneous Data						√	√
Bridge Condition Checklist							√

Bridge Condition Rating			√	√	√
Element/Component Name			√	√	√
Units of measurements			√		√
Identify structural defects			√	√	√
Condition rating of bridge elements			√		√
Overall Structure Condition Index (OSCI)			√		√
Structural Health Index (SHI)					√
Priority Index (PI)					√
Identify structures/components for further inspection			√	√	√
Recommend further engineering analysis			√	√	√
Recommend maintenance/repairs			√	√	√
Photographic record			√	√	√

The newly developed assessment forms identified key parameters included in the VicRoads Road Infrastructure Inspection Manual and the DOW Bridge Inspection Data Collection Form. Table 3-1 above presents key parameters from the two forms. The newly developed form incorporates all the desired parameters as outlined, but most importantly, the document includes several new features for bridge condition rating. These new parameters are the OSCI, SHI, and PI. The researcher adopted the new parameters used in the study from Rashidi and Gibson (2011), which illustrates a sound methodology for developing an element based structural index where the OSCI value would help decision-makers understand and compare the conditions of bridges in a network. And that kind of bridge condition assessment is most applicable to bridges under this study as well as all other bridges in Lae City and PNG.

The bridge condition inspections were conducted on the following dates shown in Table 3.2 including the type of inspection that was carried out.

Table 3-8: Bumbu and Butibam Bridge Visual Inspection Dates

Inspection No.	Inspection Dates					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Inspection Level 1	3 rd of December, 2014	19 th of April, 2015	11 th of November, 2015	18 th of February, 2017	16 th of November, 2017	14 th of February, 2018
	7	8	9	10	11	
	15 th of November, 2018	13 th of February, 2019	21 st of August, 2019	12 th of February, 2020	19 th of August, 2020	

Inspection No.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Inspection Level 2	10 th of December, 2014	18 th of November, 2015	24 th of November, 2017	22 nd of August, 2018	28 th of August, 2019	26 th of August, 2020

The Level 1 inspection assessment form was assessed at a frequency of 6 months. While Level 2 was conducted at 12 months (once per year). The Researcher did the inspections from December 2014 to August 2020. There were eleven (11) Level 1 and six (6) Level 2 visual inspections and monitoring during this period. There was no inspection done in the year 2016 because of a boycott and strike at the University, which disrupted the monitoring schedule.

The following sub-sections discuss the three (3) bridge inspection and condition assessment levels in detail. Furthermore, how the SGBCA Forms were developed for the first and second levels of the SGBCA System, including the condition rating parameters involved, plus how the results were analysed in the third level using the instruments and software are all discussed herein.

3.2.1 Bridge Inspection and Condition Assessment Form Level 1

The first level of visual inspection frequency is for six months for routine maintenance issues and possible further inspection. The first Level of SGBCAF records the general bridge information, structural condition and features of the initial condition state of the bridge. The general bridge information, including span, abutment, pier and other miscellaneous data, is recorded in this form. Furthermore, handrails and kerbs, expansion joints, bearings, concrete, driveway surface, the ground around footings, piers, and abutments are visually inspected and assessed for any immediate repair or replacement. Also, the general condition of scuppers, signs, guardrails, road approaches, vegetation, and damaged members due to traffic were all recorded in Level 1 form. Most importantly, the assessment of the overall bridge condition is done, and recommendations are included for the required Level 2 inspection on a specific component.

The scope of Level 1 inspection is dependent on Bumbu and Butibam Bridge. Visible defects such as cracks on structural components and non-structural components were noted and recorded for further assessment. The form was formulated to inspect all structural components and associated infrastructures to identify significant visible signs of damage or unusual behaviour. These visible structural components include the bridge deck, beams, bearings, piers and abutments, foundations, waterways and approaches roads at the bridge site. The form recorded significant signs of deterioration, distress, damage or any unusual defect due to vehicle impact, human action and flood.

SGB Condition Assessment and Condition Rating Level 1

The condition assessment of SGB is the evaluation of differences between the as-designed, as-built, and as-is state of the bridge structures. That includes the bridge component, a group of similar elements within a span, or in all spans, members, and eventually the entire bridge structure. Yanev (2007) stated that the outcome determines the sufficiency of monitoring and maintenance and the effects of traffic and the environment, including defining the present and future needs. Although bridges are complex structures, BMS uses the evaluation of members or elements as input to calculate the overall structural reliability (Yanev, 2007). Thus, current bridge monitoring practices reveal the need for a unified condition rating procedure to collect access data during inspections and to account for any uncertainty and complexity issues associated with the detailed visual inspection process (Abu Dabous and Alkass, 2010).

Following most bridge inspection practices; the study used the element level index based on four condition states defined in the New South Wales Road and Traffic Authority. The bridge element condition ranges from 1 to 4 in rising order, and the general description of the four condition states for steel girder bridge elements is presented in Table 3-9. The bridge elements in this study are divided by superstructure, including deck, substructure, foundation, accessories and other miscellaneous items.

Table 3-9: Condition states for L1 SGBCA Elements (Adapted from RTA, 2007)

Condition State	Defect Description
1, 0%<d<25%	The element shows no deterioration. It may have discoloration or superficial cracks without effect on strength or serviceability
2, 26%<d<50%	Minor rust or damage in the steel elements requiring minor service. Minor cracks or spalls in concrete elements but no evidence of corrosion on non-prestressed reinforcements or deterioration of prestressed system
3, 51%<d<75%	Major corrosion and minor structural damage in steel components. Some delamination, wide cracks at critical locations may be present. No evidence of corrosion on prestressed reinforcements. The strength of the bridge is not significantly affected, but requires service
4, 76%<d<100%	Major structural damage on steel elements. Corrosion and spalls on non-prestressed elements are prevalent. There is enough concern to require detailed analysis of the strength and serviceability of the bridge. Major maintenance is required.

The condition rating and units of measurement for each component are adopted from the part three of VicRoads Road Structure Inspection Manual (2011). The unit of measurement is presented for each component for percentage calculation as shown in the Level 2 form. The Table 3-9 outlines the general condition rating for the two bridges, and the condition rating for each component is measured as a percentage of the whole component observed and the percentage in each condition (1, 2, 3, and 4) adds up to 100%. For each element, it is calculated as follows:

- Number of units making up the component (each)
- Length of the component (linear m)
- Area of the component (m²)

The components and percentage in each condition are based on total component that was observed. For example, if a component with unit of measurement in meters, then the percentage (%) is equal to length in condition state divided by the total length of component and likewise to other units as well. Equation 3-1 shows how percentage is calculated for a unit measurement of length in linear meters:

$$\%(\text{Each Condition State}) = \frac{\text{Length in Each Condition State}}{\text{Total Length of Component}} \times 100\% \quad (3.1)$$

For example, on second level calculation for condition rating, if there are 4 beams as in Bumbu Bridge and the two side beams have small areas of

condition 4 and 2 with the remainder in condition 1, then, the overall assessment is:

- Condition 4 = 50 % (i.e. 2 beams)
- Condition 3 = 0 %
- Condition 2 = 0 %
- Condition 1 = 50 % (i.e. 2 beams)

3.2.2 Bridge Structure Detailed Inspection and Condition Rating Form Level 2

The second level of visual inspection form is a detailed assessment and condition rating of the bridge structure and its components. The Level 2 inspections were done at a frequency of 12 months intervals. This level of inspection includes verification of the causes of defects and vulnerability of the bridge based on other known hazards like floods and earthquakes that would severely affect the bridge monitored. The bridge design plans and construction documents for Butibam and Bumbu Bridge were unavailable to assist this evaluation further. Due to the non-availability of construction documents, and depending on the results of the second level monitoring, the third level, in this case, study, is deemed the most appropriate for further evaluation. The third level is adopted to judge the bridge's vulnerability against known deteriorating defects that threaten the bridge's structural stability and integrity.

Nevertheless, engineers, in some cases, would tend to go directly to the third level of monitoring after the first level if, at the beginning of the monitoring and evaluation process, the plans and related construction documents would be difficult to produce, as in the case of older in-service bridges. In this case study, the construction documents were not available, so the third level was considered the most appropriate for both bridges.

The second level evaluation and condition rating are critical for this study because it determines each bridge component's overall structural condition index and provides a structural health index that may be utilised in bridge asset

management. The results determined from condition assessment and diagnosis in the second level may greatly help bridge management decisions to prioritise bridges for fund allocation. Most of the existing approaches are commonly based on subjective structural condition assessment where parameters such as functionality and client preferences may not be specifically addressed. Therefore, one of the methodologies used for this study is an integrated index for the bridge rating. The developing condition rating method described for this case study is an essential step toward this aim and adds more holism and objectivity to the current techniques practised in PNG.

SGB Condition Assessment and Rating Level 2

Firstly, the condition state or Element Structural Condition Index (ESCI) for each structural and non-structural component is determined independently and then the overall Structural Health Index (SHI) for the whole bridge is obtained. The element condition index is calculated as the current value divided by the initial value of the bridge element. The overall condition status of structural elements, *ESCI* is given by:

$$ESCI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 c_i q_i}{nI} \quad (3.2)$$

Where q_i is the quantity of elements reported in condition index (c_i) is the condition of sub-elements and $c_i \in (1, 2, 3, 4)$. In this ESCI estimation process, for each of the four condition states, deterministic values were used as an approximation for element value. According to Aboudabus and Alkass (2010), this approximation may not be reliable, as the data collected through the inspection process is usually associated with subjectivity and uncertainty. However, assumptions were made on certain components like the concrete deck, where the damaged area may be larger than the visible cracks and spalls. Recording specific data relating to the overall measurements, a number of key components, and photographs. The condition state descriptions for each element describe possible problems found on-site for those elements. However, it does not necessarily represent all defects found.

The following example illustrates the calculation process used in Level 2 SGBHMF to evaluate the Overall Structural Condition Index OSCI for both Butibam and Bumbu bridges. From the data recorded during the inspections, the result of steel girder with a total area of 185 m² is shown below in Table 3-10.

Table 3-10: Steel Girder Condition Rating Result (Level 2)

L2 BRIDGE STRUCTURE EVALUATION & CONDITION RATING DATA COLLECTION FORM								LEVEL 2 BRIDGE MONITORING			
BRIDGE COMPONENT				CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS							
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				Refer Condition Rating Criteria			ESCI*Si*M
				1	2	3	4	ESCI	Si	Mi	
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK											
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)	185	m ²	100.0	60.0	25.0	0.0	1.59	4	1	6.38
2	Concrete-Deck Slab	555	m ²	333.0	194.3	27.8	0.0	1.45	4	2	11.60
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members	37.8	m	30.2	7.6	0.0	0.0	1.20	4	1	4.80

The overall condition for the steel girders:

$$ESCI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 c_i q_i}{nl} = \frac{(100 \times 1) + (60 \times 2) + (0 \times 3) + (0 \times 1)}{1 \times 185} = 1.59$$

According to Austroads (2004) and Valenzuela (2010), the material factor is an important parameter that should be considered in structural assessment of bridge elements. Material factor is based on the vulnerability of different materials and ranges from 1 for steel) to 4 for pre-cast concrete as presented in the table below. The higher material vulnerability has a greater M_i value.

Table 3-11: Material Vulnerability Factor (M_i) (Adapted from Rashidi & Gibson, 2011)

Material of Structural Element	Material Vulnerability Factor, M_i
Steel	1
Reinforced Concrete	2
Precast Concrete	3
Prestressed Concrete	4
Other Materials	5

According to Rashidi M and Gibson P (2011) and Samsal and Ramajaneyulu (2008), the structural significance factor is another vital parameter introduced in

the overall structural assessment because some particular elements may cause inaccuracies. For instance, a minor component with a worse condition may unreasonably raise the rating value of that element under which the component is grouped. That is why the structural significance factor can take care of such problems. Visual inspection incorporates many parameters and human judgments, which may cause imprecise and uncertainties. The research by Tee et al. (1988), Melhem and Aturaliya (1996), Samsal and Ramanjaneyulu (2008) and Abu Dabous and Alkass (2010) all attempted to implement a systematic approach to quantify the structural importance of various bridge elements. Based on survey results responded by 46 bridge inspector experts, Tee et al. (1998) say that structural significance is defined as the role of an element compared to the other components and quantified this factor for different elements at different condition ratings. Abu Dabous and Alkass (2010) described the structural importance of a bridge component as the level the component contributed to the overall structural safety and integrity of the bridge and proposed the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to estimate the value of that parameter. Rashidi M and Gibson P (2011) established an Element of Structural Significance after conducting field interviews with bridge engineers and inspectors. This study adopted the outcome of summarised results from these reviewed researches as shown in Table 3-12. The higher numbers represent superior importance.

Table 3-12: Structural Importance Factor, S_i Adapted from Rashidi & Gibson, 2011

Element	Structural Significance Factor, S_i
Barrier, Footway, kerb, joints	1
Foundation, Abutments, Wingwall	2
Deck, Bearings	3
Beams, Headstocks, Piers	4

Casual Factor of SGB Condition Assessment

The rate of deterioration for in-service steel girder bridge elements depends on various parameters. The casual factors included in bridge structural condition assessment are age, environmental, road, and inspection factors. Since

bridges are designed to withstand fatigue loading, which increases with time, the age of bridges is significant as they are designed for at least a maximum life expectancy of 65 years as per PNG and Australian design codes. The bridge service life ends when one of the key components fails to function as designed. The other factor is the environment. Exposure of a bridge to different environmental conditions can cause chemical and physical deterioration in bridge components. For example, the Butibam and Bumbu bridges are closer to the sea and are more exposed to alkalinity, resulting in corrosion of the steel components.

Moreover, the usage and importance of bridges to the road network where the bridge is located, such as rural or urban, and the features it crosses like roads or waterways is also a significant factor in bridge condition assessment and rating. The quality and frequency of inspection play a vital role in the structural reliability of bridges. Four factors were applied in this case study, and the rating of these factors is shown below in Table 3-13.

Table 3-13: SGBHM Casual Factor Ratings Adapted from Rashidi & Gibson, 2011

Rating	Age Factor	Road Class	Environment	Inspection Quality
1	New	Minor	Low	Very High
2	Recently Built	Local Access	Medium	High
3	Old	Collectors	High	Medium
4	Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low

To find the priority vector of the contributed factors, an Analytical Hierarchy Process developed by Saaty (1980) was adopted in this study. According to Rashidi and Gibson (2011), a casual factor ranging from 1 to 4 is calculated as follows:

$$CF = 0.411A + 0.120E + 0.107R + 0.362I \quad (3.3)$$

Where:

- *A* - Age Factor
- *E* - Environmental Factor
- *R* - Road Type Factor
- *I* - Inspection factor

Finally, the Structural Health Index *SHI* that integrates all the above-mentioned parameters that influence the structural efficiency is calculated by equation (3.4):

$$SHI = \frac{CF \sum S_i \cdot M_i \cdot ESCI_i}{n} \quad (3.4)$$

Where:

- *CF* - Causal Factor
- *S_i* - Structural Importance Factor
- *M_i* - Material Vulnerability Factor
- *ESCI_i* - Element Structural Condition Index
- *n* - Number of Element Types

The SHI value ranges from 1 to 256, where the index may be applied to prioritise bridges in a network, and the priority of remedial actions increases as the number rises. The identical upper limit (4) and lower limit (1) of all parameters and the uniformity of quantity ranges according to the condition of an entire structural element are introduced as the Overall Structural Condition Index, *OSCI*, which has been re-rated based on SHI and defined as:

- *OSCI* = 1, when *SHI* = 1
- *OSCI* = 2, when $1 < SHI \leq 16$
- *OSCI* = 3, when $16 < SHI \leq 81$
- *OSCI* = 4 when $81 < SHI \leq 256$

The re-rated rating number for *OSCI* is applicable for prioritisation and also selecting the major remedial strategies such as repair, strengthening and replacement.

3.3 Engineering Analysis and Modelling Level 3

After the second level of monitoring, the major or specific issues concerning the structural integrity of the bridges were further assessed and analysed by methods described herein. The tools and software used in the third level are Micro-Strand structural analysis software to assess the load rating for Butibam Bridge, surveying equipment including theodolite for deflection monitoring, *Rensensys Sensors* for Tilt Monitoring, and SolidWorks modelling and simulation for Bumbu Bridge.

3.3.1 Microstran Bridge Structural Analysis and Assessment

The software that was used to model and analyse Butibam Bridge is the Micro-Strand structural analysis software. MicroStran is leading-edge software for analysing civil engineering structures with in-built steel members and connection designs. MicroStran features powerful modelling commands, several commonly used analysis methods, exceptionally fast solvers, and interoperability with a number of other engineering file formats. Micro-Strand can analyse any structure, including a bridge that is exposed to static loading, dynamic response, wind, earthquake and moving loads.

3.3.2 Deflection Monitoring Using Optical/Direct Levelling Survey

The different ways of measuring bridge deflection and a more convenient method available are the Optical Survey. A technical person from the Lands and Survey department helped collect data during the following dates for the Bumbu Bridge in Lae City. A benchmark BM is a fixed position with a known elevation taken as a starting spot level in surveying. The tripod with the automatic level is set up between the BM and the first point on the grid where the elevation is determined. Figure 3-5 shows leveling methods and dates of inspection.

	Inspection Dates					
Inspection	1	2	3	4	5	6
Inspection Level 3	December 3, 2014	April 19, 2015	November 11, 2015	February 18, 2017	November 16, 2017	February 14, 2018

Figure 3-5: A sample procedure for direct levelling (Adapted from Aki & Roberson, 2005)

The procedure of the activity is: the first reading is taken at the BM called the backsight BS, and then the second reading is recorded facing the first spot level

as the foresight FS. The tripod is then moved to a point between the FS and the subsequent desired spot level where the elevation is required. The tripod has always been located midway between the FS and BS, considering the instrument errors and errors due to curvature and refraction of the instruments. The FS becomes the backsight, and the next spot level becomes the FS. The step repeats for the entire distance surveyed for the required intermediate elevation points and closes with FS back on the BM. The correction for the instrument errors, the run closes at another BM or returns to the original BM. Errors and minor discrepancies are distributed proportionately to all the elevations, and the survey runs. This study adopted the direct levelling approach for Bumbu Bridge deflection monitoring during the research period. This method is easy to adopt and suitable for periodic monitoring.

Figure 3-6: Equipment for Deflection Monitoring

The total station as shown in Figure 3-6, is an instrument that consists of a theodolite with a built-in distancer that measures angles and distances simultaneously. It measures the horizontal distance height difference, the coordinates are calculated automatically, and all additional information and measurements are recordable. This study used a total station to monitor the elevation of the points on the bridge to determine the positions or heights of the desired points. The points were marked and painted to get the readings on the same spot in the following monitoring. The distance and right-angle setting of the bridge traverse profiles of desired points were also determined with the surveying level after the total station readings. The level has an accuracy of 0.1 - 0.3 metres. Both are used to record the data.

This monitoring intends to find the elevation difference of the two mid-spans, points above the side girder on the downstream side of the river, before and afterwards the monitoring period. Aki (2005) used this method. The difference between the RLs' initial and subsequent readings is the deflection values for the girder or the bridge. The focus is on a girder, G1, on the downstream side of the bridge, as shown on the sketched plan view Figure 3.7, and the mid spots for the first span G1-2 and second span G1-5. The instruments used in monitoring the deflection of the steel girders include total station, surveying level, levelling staff, surveying tripod, prism, prism rod, field books and umbrella for shades. A bush knife was used to cut vegetation blocking sight of reading, a ladder to access the north abutment of Butibam Bridge to check bearings (the south abutment was inaccessible), a camera to collect photographs and a GPS to get the location of the bridge.

Figure 3-7 also shows the spots on the bridge where the readings are taken under static conditions and with the bridge loaded by parked heavy trucks. The Benchmark BM locations, station 1 and station 2, are established at 100 m elevation, and the readings were taken from the known BM, STN1 and STN2. The desired points are almost above girder G1. The differences in RLs from the two levelling surveys are evaluating the deflections and the settlement of the girders and abutments over four years. The value of such evaluations is minimal because the dynamic conditions are totally ignored. However, static evaluations are a good indicator of the performance decline and invite to more advanced simulation and evaluation of the bridge performance.

Figure 3-7: Sketch Plan Location of Survey Points and Point Numbers for Bumbu Bridge

3.3.3 Tilt Monitoring Using Resensys SenSpot Sensors

The equipment used for monitoring the health of the Bumbu Bridge is from the American company Resensys LLC, www.resensys.com. As shown in figure 3.8, it consists of a SenSpot™ Wireless High-Resolution 2D Inclination/Tilt, which is an Ultra-Low-Power Precision Sensing & Wireless Communication device, a SeniMax™ Data Logger and the Gateway and the SenScope™ Real-time Monitoring Software.

Figure 3-8: Resensys Remote Tilt Monitoring Equipment

SenScope software package designed for Resensys SenSpot and SeniMax system that conducts real-time monitoring and long-term structural health diagnosis was used to monitor the tilt. It can convert large volumes of data into specific structural diagnostics information. The information generated by SenScope™ facilitates decision-making and accelerates the course of action for maintenance/repair. Its key features are listed below:

- SenScope is used in visualizing data. It shows the data from the remote server or the local SenSpot/SeniMax in a user-friendly working panel.

- SenScope provides an automated alert generation and notification when the measured quantity exceeds the threshold. It automatically generates an alert in the system and notifies the user with email or text messages.
- Data Processing Service: SenScope shows selected data's statistical and spectrum properties and the relationship between two different quantities.
- SenScope Report Automation: It exports the data of several SenSpot sensors in the form of images and spreadsheets according to the user's need.
- SenScope Data Hosting stores data in Resensys's secured cloud servers periodically backed up. Data access is using the Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) from anywhere. The data can be exported to Excel, TXT, CSV, and XML formats.

SenSpot is easy to install, scalable solution for distributed structural integrity monitoring. Its inclination/tilt uses Resensys's proprietary technology for reliable and accurate measurement, large-scale sensing, wireless synchronization, and ultra-energy-efficient wireless communication. It is designed to operate maintenance-free for more than a decade. It does not need calibration after installation. The battery replacement or any other maintenance for at least ten years. SenSpot sensors can be applied easily to as many critical spots on a structure as needed, with minimal installation effort due to their small size and lightweight. As part of Resensys solution for integrity monitoring system, SenSpot™ inclination/tilt can be used to monitor the smallest movements of structural components such as piers, decks, and bearings on a highway bridge. In addition, SenSpot™ inclination/tilt monitors changes in these quantities as the structure expands or contracts due to temperature variations. In addition to bridges, SenSpot inclination/tilt can be used in various other structures.

The need to monitor the Bumbu River Bridge arose due to increased scouring at the mid-span pier and abutment at its south end. Resensys 2D HRT SenSpot Sensor was used to detect instability and settling on piers and abutments. SenScope sensors were attached to the bridge girders as shown in the Figure 3-9.

Figure 3-9: Installation of Sensors at Bumbu Bridge Site

There are three different modes in which SenScope can process data, live mode, local mode and remote mode. It creates a local minimum system in the local mode, where data can be viewed in on the computer's hard drive local database and accessible even after SenScope has been closed. However, any data is deleted in live mode after the SenScope is closed. The SenScope software was installed on a laptop and operated in local mode. Both SenScope sensors were installed on Girders 1 and 3 and close to the north abutment, where it was easy to access them. The monitored data from the sensors were retrieved on the laptop transmitted by the SeniMax gateway.

Figure 3-10: A screen shot of the live mode showing the charge

3.3.4 SolidWorks Simulation and Finite Element Analysis

Only a few exact analytical solutions of the partial differential equations that govern the behaviour of deformable bodies are available, and those available are limited in applicability. The solutions are generally obtainable only for regions with regular geometric shapes and only for restricted boundary conditions. The need for results for more complex structures leads to approximate methods. Several approximate methods have been introduced since the beginning of the twentieth century. One of the earliest replaces the goal of obtaining a continuously varying solution distribution by getting values at a finite number of discrete grid or nodal points. The differential equations are replaced by finite difference equations, which, together with appropriate boundary conditions expressed in different form, yield a set of simultaneous linear equations for the nodal values.

An alternative approximate method, the Rayleigh-Ritz method, introduced almost simultaneously, seeks to expand the solution of the differential equations in a linear series of known functions. The coefficients multiplying these functions are obtained by requiring the satisfaction of the equivalent variational formulation of the problem and are, once more, the solution of a set of simultaneous linear equations. These methods have extended the range of problems that may be considered but have been found to be limited by the high difficulty involved in applying them to even more complex shapes.

The need to analyse the complicated wing structures of high-speed aircraft was the impetus leading to the development of the finite element method. In the traditional analysis of complicated building structures, it is common to divide them into small 3D components whose behaviour under general states of deformation or loading is more readily available. The 3D components are then reattached subject to conditions of equilibrium or compatibility. The slope-deflection method is statically indeterminate rigid-frame analysis is an example of such an approach. Attempts at a rational analysis of wing structures initially took the same physically motivated path, but with the improvements of matrix formulations and the use of electronic digital computers.

Based on Castigliano's theorems to calculate flexibility matrices for obtaining deflections from forces and stiffness matrices to determine forces from displacements. The former matrices were used in force analysis methods, while the latter was used in displacement methods. An explosion in the development of the finite element methods occurred after 1960 when it was realized that the method, whether based on forces or displacements, could be interpreted as an application of the Rayleigh-Ritz method. The approach was first suggested for 2D continua by Courant, who proposed the division of a domain into triangular regions with the desired functions continuous over the entire domain replaced by piecewise continuous approximations within the triangles.

The use of flexibility matrices was found to imply the implementation of the principle of minimum complementary energy, while stiffness matrices imply the principle of minimum potential energy. This approach permits the investigation of such topics as the continuity requirements for the piecewise approximations and convergence rates obtained with increasing numbers of elements or the increasing complexity of functional representation. It also allows flexibility or stiffness matrices to be calculated from a more straightforward mathematical viewpoint while indicating the possibility of using variational principles. Both forces and displacements are varied to produce hybrid elements. Despite the possible advantage of mixed elements for some problems, solutions based upon the principle of minimum potential energy and displacement approximations have become dominant because the associated computer software is more universally applicable and requires the least interaction between machine and operator.

The finite element method has been applied beyond structural analysis and includes fluid flow and thermal simulations in recent years. For example, the large deformation geometric nonlinearity or material property nonlinearity has been extended to allow nonlinear and linear problems solutions. The finite element methods are extensively used to provide answers to problems that would have been unsolvable in the recent past.

After building a 3D model, there is a need to verify its efficient performance in the field. It can only be answered by performing expensive and time-consuming product development cycles without analysis tools. The steps of a product development cycle include are:

- Building the 3D model
- Creating a design prototype;
- Testing the prototype in the field
- Evaluating the results of the field tests
- Modifying the design based on the field test results

The iteration continues until a satisfactory solution is reached. The Finite Element Method can help in accomplishing the following tasks:

- Reduce cost by simulating the testing of the 3D model on the computer instead of expensive field tests.
- Reduce time to market by reducing the number of product development cycles.
- Improve products by quickly testing many concepts and scenarios before making a final decision.

SolidWorks Simulation uses the Finite Element Method - numerical technique for analysing engineering designs. FEM is accepted as the standard analysis method due to its generality and suitability for computer implementation. FEM divides the model into many small pieces of simple shapes called elements, effectively replacing a complex problem by many simple problems that need to be solved simultaneously.

Elements share common points called nodes, and a process of dividing the model into small pieces is called meshing. This activity is called the finite element method, which uses elements with different shapes under all possible support and load scenarios. The behaviour of each element is well-known and is fully described by several parameters. Of course, the element's analysis type

depends on that response at any point interpolated at the element nodes. The thermal analysis fully describes its response to the temperature of a node. For structural analyses, degrees of freedom or DOFs are a node's descriptive response generally by three translations and three rotations. Finite Element Analysis or FEA is an analysis using FEM (Finite Element Method).

The software formulates the equations governing the behaviour of each element, taking into consideration its connectivity to other elements. These equations relate the response to known material properties, restraints, and loads. Next, the program organizes the equations into a large set of simultaneous algebraic equations and solves for the unknowns. For example, the solver finds the displacements at each node in stress analysis, and then the program calculates strains and stresses.

Chapter 4 : Results and Discussions

4.1 Introduction

Chapter 4 discusses and presents the condition assessment results of the steel girder bridge under the Bumbu and Butibam Bridge case study of Lae City. The workflow in chapter 3 (Figure 3-1) aims to achieve the objective outlined in the first chapter, including a literature review to develop visual inspection and condition assessment forms. The study considers the bridges along the Bumbu River. The bridge's site was inspected, and the bridge elements' defects were noted and recorded using the condition assessment forms. The bridge components' conditions were rated qualitatively using Level 1 and 2 visual inspection forms and then a quantitative method in Level 3 using structural analysis software and engineering tools. The study was undertaken in three different levels of inspection and condition assessment and ratings, as discussed in Chapter 3. The third engineering analysis or load assessment and deflection monitoring were to check the serviceability (deflection) and the ultimate limits (shear and moments) as in Butibam Bridge. Photographic records were taken for the defects identified. Summary results of steel girder bridge condition assessments are presented in tabular or graphical forms.

4.2 Development of the SGB Condition Assessment Forms

In this case study, the bridge condition assessment referred to the evaluation of differences between the as-designed, as-built, and as-is states. Bridge design and as-built drawings were unavailable for the Bumbu and Butibam bridges to compare the structures. The condition evaluation for bridge structures denoted a bridge component, a group of similar structural elements within and in all spans, and eventually the entire bridge. The evaluation outcome determined the sufficiency of assessment and maintenance and the effects of traffic and the environment and defined the present and future needs (Yanev, 2007).

The members or elements were added into the forms to be evaluated to calculate the overall structural reliability. Moreover, the bridge assessment forms were developed in a unified condition rating that it catered for uncertainty and complexity issues associated with the visual inspection. The element level index was used with bridge element conditions ranging from 1 to 4 to be consistent with most bridge inspection practices worldwide, as presented in Table 3-9 in Chapter 3. The steel girder bridge was divided into elements: superstructure, substructure, foundations, accessories, and miscellaneous, including others. The quantities of each bridge element were estimated with correct units and recorded for each condition state independently. The units used for the deck, pier, and pile were in square meters, the units used for joints and railings were meters, and bearing pads, including waterways, were either each or item. These can be seen in the developed forms for this study.

The forms developed for this study are most reliable and applicable for steel girder bridge elements in PNG because of three important parameters considered in developing the forms. The first important parameter incorporated in the evaluation is the material vulnerability factor, which ranges between 1 (steel) and 4 (precast concrete), including 5 (other materials), as discussed in Chapter 3, Table 3-11. The other significant parameter is the structural significance factor. For instance, a minor component with a worse condition may unreasonably raise the rating value of that element. This kind of problem was dealt with with the introduction of element structural significance, which prevailing condition of components was not dependent to it (Samal and Ramajaneyulu, 2008). The third parameter incorporated in the forms is the causal factor, which contributes to the structural efficiency of the steel girder bridge. The structural elements of a steel girder bridge deteriorate over time, and the rate of deterioration depends on various parameters. These parameters include the environment the structure is located in, the number of years in-service (Age), the function the structure is required to perform (Road Class), and the quality of inspection and assessment. The developed form is shown in Figure 4-1, Level 1- Bridge Inspection & Condition Assessment Form.

Moreover, after extensive literature review on bridge inspection and condition assessment practices around the globe, and specifically Australia, this study

developed steel girder bridge condition assessment forms as shown in the schematic diagram in Figure 3-2

There were two condition level assessment forms developed for Level 1: bridge condition assessment and condition rating. The first form was used to collect general information on the two bridges since no bridge data was available. The second form was used to rate the condition of the identified states of the bridge component using the condition rating criteria. The Level 1 forms were used to check out the initial condition status of structural and non-structural bridge components, and any visible damages such as cracks, material deterioration, and foundation settlement were recorded. The condition checklist results from this form were able to tell if a repair, replacement or maintenance (minor or major) was required or not with the assistance of the second form as shown in Figure 4-2, Level 1 Bridge Structural Condition Rating (ESCR) Form.

Moreover, depending on the visible defects and maintenance issues, the bridge structure was assigned a condition rating of 1 (generally in good condition) to 4 (critical condition). To make a most reasonable accuracy of the bridge condition state, further evaluation of the condition of each bridge component to create a better recommendation, that is, if the bridge was to proceed into the next stage of assessment and evaluation. The Level 1 inspection forms were intended for use at a frequency of 6 months.

The new parameters introduced in the forms provided reliable results for the Bumbu and Butibam. As indicated in the results presented below, the Butibam bridge was recently reconstructed, and most of the bridge elements are below the ESCR value of 2, which confirms, according to the form, that it stopped at Level 1 and did not proceed into the next stage of the condition assessment. On the other hand, the Bumbu bridge had the majority of the bridge elements of ESCR value more than 2, with an overall condition rating of 2.11. Hence, the bridge was recommended for the next stage of assessment. Therefore, the validity of the proposed assessment forms was proved by the results obtained from the condition assessment forms that the parameters used are reliable for the steel girder bridge of Bumbu and Butibam bridge of Lae City.

BRIDGE COMPONENT		CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS						
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				Element Structural Condition (ESCR)
				1	2	3	4	
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK								
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)		ea					
2	Concrete-Deck Slab		m ²					
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members		m ²					
SUBSTRUCTURE								
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)		m ²					
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)		m ²					
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls		m ²					
FOUNDATIONS								
7	Piles & Footings		item					
8	Ground around footings		item					
ACCESSORIES								
9	Expansion Joints		m					
10	Deck Drains		ea					
Bearings:								
11	Elastomeric Bearing Pad		ea					
12	Metal Fixed Bearing		ea					
Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):								
13	Metal Railing		m					
14	Miscellaneous Railing including Guardfence		m					
15	Railing Paint work		m					
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS								
16	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway		item					
17	Bridge Approach Barriers		m					
18	Signs		item					
19	Embankment Erosion		m ²					
20	Riverbed Scour		item					
21	General Cleaning		ea					
L1 CONDITION RATING: Note: See further condition rating criteria.				Overall Condition Rating: (without condition factors)				
1 In good condition 2 Minor defects 3 Moderate defects. 4 Critical Condition				$\sum \text{ESCR}/n = $ 0.00				
RECOMMENDATION								
Status of Bridge Health Monitoring?								
<input type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP at L1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level. <input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring								
L2 DETAILED INSPECTION REQUIRED? : <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO								
L2 ACTION REQUIRED								
Detailed Structural Evaluation Required? Detailed Nonstructural Evaluation Required?								
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, construction details not available <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, nonstructural hazards indentified that should be evaluated <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, condition rating more than cut-off <input type="checkbox"/> No, nonstructural hazards exist that may require mitigation, but a detailed evaluation is not necessary <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, other hazards present <input type="checkbox"/> No, no nonstructural hazards identified <input type="checkbox"/> DNK								
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data <u>OR</u> DNK = Do Not Know								
CONDITION RATING CRITERIA								
Condition State	Description of defects							
1 (0%<d<25%)	The element shows no distress/deterioration. There may be discolouration, efflorescence and/or superficial cracking but without effect on strength and/or serviceability.							
2 (26%<d<50%)	Minor rust/damage in the steel elements and require minor work. Concrete elemets has minor cracks and spalls may be present but there is no evidence of corrosion of non-prestressed reinforcement or							
3 (51%<d<75%)	Major rust and minor structural damage in steel components. Some delaminations and/or spalls may be present including wide cracks at critical locations. No evidence of deterioration of the prestress system. Corrosion of non-prestressed reinforcement may be present both loss of section is minor and does not significantly affect the							
4 (76%<d<100%)	Major structural damage and missing parts to steel parts. Delaminations, spalls and corrosion of non-prestressed reinforcement are prevalent. There may be also be exposure and deterioration of the prestress system (manifested by loss of bond, broken strands or wire, failed and anchorages, etc). There is sufficient concern to warrant an analysis to ascertain the impact on the strength and/or serviceability of either the element or the bridge. Note: Qty (%) This is quantity measured as percentage (%) of the component requiring the specified major maintenance.							

Figure 4-2: Level 1 Bridge Element Structural Condition Rating (ESCR) Form

The newly developed Level 2 inspection and assessment form is called the Bridge Structure Evaluation and Condition Rating Form. This form was used to further evaluate and assess in detail the defects identified in Level 1 condition assessment forms. In the second Level, the bridge components were measured and the quantity of element in each condition state was determined. The second level of inspection also verified the causes of defects, and vulnerability of the assessed bridge based from known hazards like floods or earthquake. The Level 2 evaluation and condition rating is very critical and important for this study because it determined the Overall Structural Condition Index (OSCI) for each bridge component including provision of a Structural Health Index (SHI) and Priority Index (PI) that could be utilized in bridge asset management. The Level 2 monitoring form is shown in Figure 4-3

L2 BRIDGE STRUCTURE EVALUATION & CONDITION RATING DATA COLLECTION FORM							LEVEL 2 BRIDGE MONITORING																													
BRIDGE COMPONENT					CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS																															
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				ESCR	SI	Mi	ESCR*SI*Mi																									
				1	2	3	4																													
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK																																				
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
2	Concrete-Deck Slab		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
SUBSTRUCTURE																																				
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
FOUNDATIONS																																				
7	Piles & Footings		m					0.00			0.00																									
8	Ground around footings		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
ACCESSORIES																																				
9	Expansion Joints		m					0.00			0.00																									
10	Deck Drains		ea					0.00			0.00																									
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed)		ea					0.00			0.00																									
12	Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):		m					0.00			0.00																									
13	Railing Paint work		m					0.00			0.00																									
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS																																				
14	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway		ea					0.00			0.00																									
15	Bridge Approach Barriers		m					0.00			0.00																									
16	Signs		item					0.00			0.00																									
17	Embankment Erosion		m ²					0.00			0.00																									
18	Riverbed Scour		item					0.00			0.00																									
19	General Cleaning		item					0.00			0.00																									
Σ(ESCR*SI*Mi)											0.00																									
CF = 0.411A + 0.120E + 0.107R + 0.362I											3.10																									
Parameters: Adapted from Rashidi & Gibson 2011 A - Age of bridge E - Environmental factor R - Road factor I - Inspection Table of Casual Factors <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>A</th> <th>R</th> <th>E</th> <th>I</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1 Recently Built</td> <td>Minor</td> <td>Low</td> <td>Very High</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 New</td> <td>Local access</td> <td>Medium</td> <td>High</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 Old</td> <td>Collectors</td> <td>High</td> <td>Medium</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>4 Very Old</td> <td>Arterials</td> <td>Very High</td> <td>Low</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>								A	R	E	I	1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High		2 New	Local access	Medium	High		3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium		4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low		STRUCTURAL HEALTH INDEX (SHI): $SHI = CF * \sum(ESCR * Si * Mi) / n$			0.00	
	A	R	E	I																																
1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High																																	
2 New	Local access	Medium	High																																	
3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium																																	
4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low																																	
L2 OVERALL STRUCTURE CONDITION RATING (OSCR): OSCI = 1, when SHI = 1 OSCI = 2, when 1 < SHI ≤ 16 OSCI = 3, when 16 < SHI ≤ 81 OSCI = 4, when 81 < SHI ≤ 256							=																													
RECOMMENDATION Status of Bridge Health Monitoring? <input type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP at L1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge <input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level.							L3 DETAILED INSPECTION REQUIRED? : <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO																													
L1 OVERALL CONDITION RATING? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO																																				
L3 ACTION/OR FURTHER ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION REQUIRED What general properties of the bridge would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Climatic Conditions (e.g. wind speed/humidity, temperature, air pressure) <input type="checkbox"/> Acceleration/Vibration (using accelerometers) <input type="checkbox"/> Load <input type="checkbox"/> Displacements - Using what type of sensor/system? <input type="checkbox"/> Tilt/Slope (using tiltmeters or slope indicators) <input type="checkbox"/> DNK <input type="checkbox"/> Scour (using pneumatic tubes & filters) <input type="checkbox"/> Ground Velocity																																				
What properties of the concrete bridge components would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in concrete, steel reinforcing bar, etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (e.g., in concrete and <input type="checkbox"/> Concrete Cracking (e.g., flexural, shear, shrinkage, D-cracking or spalling/crushing) <input type="checkbox"/> Locating Rebar/Voids or Delaminations <input type="checkbox"/> Concrete Strength (Thermistor or Schid)																																				
What properties of the steel bridge components would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in plates, rolled sections, connections, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (portable ultrasonic gusset plate thickness measurements) <input type="checkbox"/> Fracture (e.g., brittle, ductile, or fatigue) <input type="checkbox"/> Others? specify <input type="checkbox"/> Crack Growth <input type="checkbox"/> DNK																																				
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data OR DNK = Do Not Know																																				

Figure 4-3: Level 2 - Bridge Structure Evaluation and Condition Rating Form

4.3 Application of SGB Condition Assessment Forms

The newly developed SGBHMFs were applied in the case study of the Butibam and Bumbu bridge of Lae City. As per the study workflow, the SGBHM was undertaken in three (3) different Levels, where the forms were used in the first and second Levels. As discussed in Chapter 3, the inspection dates are shown in Table 3-2, where the Level 1 inspection was done 11 times, and Level 2 inspection was conducted six times (once in a year) during the period from December 2014 to August 2020, excluding the year 2016. The results obtained from the forms in both Levels 1 and 2 were then verified by structural analysis and solid works modelling and simulation software in Level 3. The results from the first and second Levels of SGBHMFs for Butibam and Bumbu Bridge are presented in the sub-sections below.

4.3.1 SGB Condition Assessment Results - Butibam Bridge

Butibam Bridge was recently reconstructed in 1997 and is approximately 23 years old. According to PNG and Australian bridge design codes, bridges can be in service for 60 or 75 years. Even though the bridge is not close to its effective life span, it was monitored because it became part of the major road network connection of industrial centres located at the northern end to the main Lae City. The results obtained in Level 1 and Level 2 for Butibam Bridge are presented below.

Figure 4-4: Butibam Bridge: Aerial View on Left, Side View from Southern End on Right

• Bridge Inspection & Condition Assessment Results Level 1

L1 ROUTINE MONITORING INSPECTION & CONDITION ASSESSMENT DATA COLLECTION FORM		LEVEL 1 BRIDGE MONITORING
BRIDGE NAME & LOCATION		General Bridge Information
Bridge Name: <u>BUTIBAM BRIDGE</u> Bridge ID: <u>B_ND 4201_060</u> Road Name: <u>BUTIBAM</u> Road Number: <u>DNK</u> Latitude: <u>6.53'44"</u> Longitude: <u>147.0'56"</u> Altitude: <u>55 m</u> Map Reference: <u>DNK</u> Province: <u>MOROBE</u> District: <u>LAECITY</u> Weather: <u>FINE/SUNNY</u> Date: <u>3/12/2014</u> Inspector's Name: <u>G. WANTEPE</u>		Bridge construction type: <u>STANDARD</u> Year of construction: <u>1997</u> Inspection Type: <u>L1 Routine Monitoring Inspection</u> Overall Length (m): <u>81.5 m</u> Number of Spans: <u>3</u> Waterway Clearance (m): <u>9.4 m</u> Kerb to kerb width (m): <u>12.1 m</u> Clear Vehicle Width (m): <u>10.8 m</u> Walkway Width (m): <u>1.5 m</u> Estimated Vehicles per day: <u>201 - 1000</u>
SPAN DATA		ABUTMENT DATA:
Main Member Type: <u>Girder</u> Secondary Member Type: <u>Girder</u> Other Member Type: <u>Bracing</u> Deck Material: <u>Concrete</u> Deck Wearing Surface (DWS): <u>Bitumen</u> Deck Drainage: <u>Deck Crossfall</u> Parapet: <u>Rails/posts</u> Expansion Joint Type: <u>Rubber extrusion</u>		Abutment Type: <u>Reinforced Earth</u> Abutment Material: <u>Concrete</u> Abutment Foundation: <u>DNK (assumption - driven piles)</u> Bearing Type - Abutment: <u>Steel plate/Elastomeric</u> Restraint Type - Abutment: <u>Not Known</u> Scour Protection - Abutment: <u>Gabions</u> Bank/Slope Protection: <u>Concrete/ Gabions</u>
PIER DATA		MISCELLANEOUS DATA
Pier Type: <u>Multiple Columns</u> Pier Material: <u>Concrete</u> Pier Foundation Type: <u>DNK (assumption - driven piles)</u> Piers Bearing Type: <u>Not Known</u> Piers Restraint Type: <u>Not Known</u> PIER Scour Protection: <u>None</u>		Design Load (Tonnes): <u>44 T</u> Safe Speed Limit (km/h): <u>DNK</u> Posted Load Limit (Tonnes): <u>DNK</u> Guardrailings: <u>Rails/Posts</u> River Training Type: <u>None</u> Soil Type: <u>Stiff Soil</u> Embankment/Riverbed (erosion/ scour/landslid): Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DNK
BRIDGE CONDITION CHECKLIST		
Condition of Steel Girders <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Minor Corrosion Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Major Corrosion Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Level 2 Inspection Condition of Concrete <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Minor Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Major Deterioration - Level 2 Inspection Required Condition of Piers, Abutments and Wings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Back Slabs Gaping <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Minor Repairs <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Repair or Correction (give details) Condition of Handrail and Kerbs <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Tightening or Straightening <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Painting <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Minor replacement (give details). <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Replacement (give details). Condition of Guard Fencing or Guardrails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Painting <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repairs <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement	Condition of Ground Around Footings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Fire Hazard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Debris Requires Removal <input type="checkbox"/> Scour (give details) Debris on Deck Surface <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Debris/Rubbish Removal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Sweeping/Cleaning Condition of Expansion Joints <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable Condition of D.W.S (drive way surface) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Patching <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Replacement (give details). <input type="checkbox"/> Nil <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Tingling and replacement Condition of Nameboards/Signs/Depth Markers <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Required	Condition of Vegetation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Spraying <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Removal Condition of Scuppers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Blocked Requires Cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement Condition of Bearings <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Level 2 Inspection <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repair <input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable Condition of Approaches <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Premix <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Repairs (give details) Traffic Damaged Members <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (give details) <input type="checkbox"/> No <i>Damaged guard fencing and rails damaged and requires repair.</i>
Level 1 Condition Rating of the whole structure by inspection? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 Generally in good condition <input type="checkbox"/> 2 Minor defects <input type="checkbox"/> 3 Moderate defects <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Critical condition		Remarks: <i>Generally in good condition with only routine maintenance issues.</i>
Requires Further Detailed Condition Monitoring? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. <input type="checkbox"/> No.		Remarks: <i>A further Level 2 condition rating is required for this study.</i>
PHOTO LOG		
No.	Photo Description	File Name
	Damaged guard rails	L1 Butibam Bridge - 03-12-2014
L2 ACTION REQUIRED		
Detailed Structural Evaluation Required? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes, construction details not available <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, condition rating more than cut-off <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, other hazards present		Detailed Nonstructural Evaluation Required? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, nonstructural hazards identified that should be evaluated <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No, nonstructural hazards exist that may require mitigation, but a detailed evaluation is not necessary <input type="checkbox"/> No, no nonstructural hazards identified <input type="checkbox"/> DNK
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data DR DNK = Do Not Know		

Figure 4-5: Level 1 SGBCA Result for Butibam Bridge 3rd December, 2014

BRIDGE COMPONENT			CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS					
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				Element Structural Condition (ESCR)
				1	2	3	4	
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK								
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)	8	ea	8	0	0	0	1.00
2	Concrete-Deck Slab	985	m ²	900	0	0	0	0.91
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members	780	m ²	780	0	0	0	1.00
SUBSTRUCTURE								
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)	20	m ²	20	0	0	0	1.00
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)	38.4	m ²	4	2	0	0	0.21
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls	70	m ²	70	0	0	0	1.00
FOUNDATIONS								
7	Piles & Footings	48	item	48	0	0	0	1.00
8	Ground around footings	4	item	4	0	0	0	1.00
ACCESSORIES								
9	Expansion Joints	16.5	m	16.5	0	0	0	1
10	Deck Drains	10	ea	5	5	0	0	1.5
Bearings:								
11	Elastomeric Bearing Pad	8	ea	8	0	0	0	1.00
12	Metal Fixed Bearing	8	ea	8	0	0	0	1.00
Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):								
13	Metal Railing	400	m	140	110	150	0	2.03
14	Miscellaneous Railing including Guardfence	1020	m	500	500	20	0	1.53
15	Railing Paint work	1200	m	0	800	400	0	2.33
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS								
16	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway	160	item	90	50	20	0	1.56
17	Bridge Approach Barriers	40	m	30	10	0	0	1.25
18	Signs	4	item	0	0	2	2	3.50
19	Embankment Erosion	985	m ²	905	80	0	0	1.08
20	Riverbed Scour	2	item	0	2	0	0	2.00
21	General Cleaning	3	ea	0	3	0	0	2.00
L1 CONDITION RATING:				Note: See further condition rating criteria.				Overall Condition Rating:
1 In good condition 2 Minor defects 3 Moderate defects. 4 Critical Condition								(without condition factors)
								Σ ESCR)/n = 1.44

Figure 4-6: Level 1 Butibam Bridge Element Structural Condition Rating (ESCR)

Figure 4-7: Photos of Butibam Bridge

According to the Level 1 results, the general assessment of the bridge is reasonable, where most conditions of the components are satisfactory or require minor maintenance and repair or painting. Majority of the bridge components' condition were satisfactory as shown below in Table 4-1, and a condition rating of 1 in the graph in Figure 4-8, which means the bridge is generally in good condition.

Table 4-1: Level 1 Condition Assessment of Butibam Bridge

Component Name	Condition of Components
Steel Girders	Satisfactory
Handrails & Kerbs	Satisfactory, requires painting
Expansion Joints	Satisfactory
Bearings	Satisfactory
Concrete	Satisfactory
Drive way surface	Satisfactory
Ground around footings	Satisfactory, debris requires removal
Piers, Abutments, Wings	Satisfactory
Debris on Deck Surface	Debris/rubbish removal, requires sweeping/cleaning
Scuppers	Satisfactory
Nameboards, signs	None, required
Guard Fencing or Guardrails	Satisfactory, requires painting
Vegetation	Satisfactory
Approaches	Satisfactory, requires repairs
Traffic Damaged Members	Yes, requires repair

As mentioned earlier, the level 1 monitoring was conducted at a frequency of 6 months, and from the results presented, it can be noted that the bridge condition is generally good all throughout the period of monitoring except for minor maintenance and repair of road approaches and guard fencing or railings.

Figure 4-8: Level 1 - Butibam Bridge Overall Structure Condition Rating from December 2014 to August 2020.

The graph in Figure 4-8 shows the summary of Level 1 overall condition rating for Butibam during the period of inspection and assessment from December 2014 to August 2020. During that period of inspection and assessment, it was noted that the results improved when there was a repair and maintenance of the bridge miscellaneous components. It was also concluded that these maintenance practices can have an impact on the overall bridge structure condition rating. The overall condition rating for Butibam Bridge was below 2 during the assessment period as shown in Figure 4-9, Level 2 SGBCA Result for Butiban Bridge on 10th December 2014. This shows that not much deterioration or damages done to the bridge except for minor routine maintenance, repair and replacement works.

L2 BRIDGE STRUCTURE EVALUATION & CONDITION RATING										LEVEL 2																						
DATA COLLECTION FORM										BRIDGE MONITORING																						
BRIDGE NAME: BUTIBAM BRIDGE		WEATHER: FINE/ SUNNY																														
INSPECTOR(S) NAME: GRACE WANTEPE		DATE: 10/12/2014																														
BRIDGE COMPONENT				CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS																												
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				(Refer Condition Rating Criteria)			ESCI*Si*Mi																					
				1	2	3	4	ESCI	Si	Mi																						
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK																																
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)	8	m ²	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.00	4	1	4.00																					
2	Concrete-Deck Slab	880.2	m ²	792.2	88.0	0.0	0.0	1.10	3	2	6.60																					
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members	780	m	780.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.00	4	1	4.00																					
SUBSTRUCTURE																																
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)	25	m ²	25.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.00	4	2	8.00																					
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)	47.5	m ²	47.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.00	4	2	8.00																					
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls	30	m ²	18.0	12.0	0.0	0.0	1.40	2	2	5.60																					
FOUNDATIONS																																
7	Piles & Footings	48	m	38.4	9.6	0.0	0.0	1.20	2	2	4.80																					
8	Ground around footings	4	m ²	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.00	2	2	4.00																					
ACCESSORIES																																
9	Expansion Joints	22	m	19.8	2.2	0.0	0.0	1.10	1	3	3.30																					
10	Deck Drains	16	ea	16.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	1.25	3	3	11.25																					
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed)	16	ea	16.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.00	3	3	9.00																					
12	Parapets (kerbs/trails & barriers):	163	m	114.1	48.9	0.0	0.0	1.30	1	1	1.30																					
13	Railing Paint work	1400	m	700.0	700.0	0.0	0.0	1.50	1	3	4.50																					
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS																																
14	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway	2	ea	1.4	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.30	1	3	3.90																					
15	Bridge Approach Barriers	40	m	20.0	20.0	0.0	4.0	1.90	1	1	1.90																					
16	Signs/Nameboards	4	ea	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.0	3.50	1	3	10.50																					
17	Embankment Erosion	2	m ²	1.4	0.4	0.2	0.0	1.40	1	1	1.40																					
18	Riverbed Scour	2	ea	1.2	0.4	0.4	0.0	1.60	1	5	8.00																					
19	General Cleaning	7	ea	0.0	6.3	0.0	0.7	2.20	1	3	6.60																					
Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)				Average ESCI				1.41	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		106.65																					
CF = 0.411A + 0.120E + 0.107R + 0.362I				A = 2	E = 3	R = 3	I = 3					2.59																				
Parameters: Adapted from Rashidi & Gibson 2011 A - Age of bridge E - Environmental factor R - Road factor I - Inspection Quality				STRUCTURAL HEALTH INDEX (SHI): SHI = CF * Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)/n							14.53																					
Table of Casual Factors <table style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <th>A</th> <th>R</th> <th>E</th> <th>I</th> </tr> <tr> <td>1 Recently Built</td> <td>Minor</td> <td>Low</td> <td>Very High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 New</td> <td>Local access</td> <td>Medium</td> <td>High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 Old</td> <td>Collectors</td> <td>High</td> <td>Medium</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4 Very Old</td> <td>Arterials</td> <td>Very High</td> <td>Low</td> </tr> </table>				A	R	E	I	1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High	2 New	Local access	Medium	High	3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium	4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low	L2 OVERALL STRUCTURE CONDITION INDEX (OSCI):							OSCI = 2	
A	R	E	I																													
1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High																													
2 New	Local access	Medium	High																													
3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium																													
4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low																													
RECOMMENDATION																																
Element Structural Condition Index (ESCI) or Average ESCI of Bridge Health Monitoring? 1.41				L3 ENGINEERING ANALYSIS REQUIRED? :																												
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP. <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level. <input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level.				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO																												
L3 ACTION/OR FURTHER ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION REQUIRED																																
What general properties of the bridge would you like to monitor?																																
<input type="checkbox"/> Climatic Conditions (e.g. wind speed/humidity, temperature, air pressure)				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acceleration/Vibration (using accelerometers)				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Load																								
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Displacements - Using what type of sensor/system?				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tilt/Slope (using tiltmeters or slope indicators)				<input type="checkbox"/> DNK																								
<input type="checkbox"/> Scour (using pneumatic tubes & filters)				<input type="checkbox"/> Ground Velocity																												
What properties of the concrete bridge components would you like to monitor?																																
<input type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in concrete, steel reinforcing bar, etc)				<input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (e.g., in concrete and reinforcing)																												
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Concrete Cracking (e.g., flexural, shear, shrinkage, D-cracking or spalling/crushing)				<input type="checkbox"/> Locating Rebar/Voids or Delaminations																												
				<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete Strength (Thermistor or Schid Hammer)																												
What properties of the steel bridge components would you like to monitor?																																
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in plates, rolled sections, connections, etc.				<input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (portable ultrasonic gusset plate thickness measurements)																												
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fracture (e.g., brittle, ductile, or fatigue)				<input type="checkbox"/> Others? specify																												
<input type="checkbox"/> Crack Growth				<input type="checkbox"/> DNK																												
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data OR DNK = Do Not Know																																
ADDITIONAL COMMENTS ON REQUIRED ACTIONS & LOCATIONS ON STRUCTURE																																
Structural Health Index (SHI) is 14.53 L2 Overall Structure Condition Index (OSCI) is 2 Further analyze the structure using Structural Analysis Software and Modelling.																																

Figure 4-9: Level 2 SGBCA Result for Butibam Bridge on 10th December, 2014

SGBHM Level 2 Bridge Structure Evaluation

Figure 4-10: Level 2 Butibam Bridge Structure Evaluation & Condition Rating

To determine the SHI for the bridge, the CF value 2.59 was multiplied to the sum (of result obtained from $ESCI \cdot Si \cdot Mi$), which is 106.65. The CF value was calculated from Equation 3-3 and the SHI was calculated using Equation 3-4. The SHI value for Butibam Bridge is 14.53, where the values range from 1–256. This index may be applied for prioritisation of bridge remedial actions. The priority of remedial actions increases as the number rises. However, as stated in the methodology in Chapter 3, an entire structural element is introduced as OSCI, where the Level 2 OSCI value for Butibam Bridge is 2 since the SHI value 14.53 falls in the range of OSCI 2. This validates that the bridge is still new. All the Level 2 bridge structure evaluation and condition assessment results for Butibam Bridge from December 2014 to August 2020 are presented in the Appendix.

Table 4-2: Level 2 SGBCA Evaluation of the Overall Structural Condition Index (OSCI) for Butibam Bridge

No. Description of Bridge Element		L2 Element Structural Condition Index (ESCI)																							
		10 December 2014				18 November 2015				24 November 2017				22 August 2018				28 August 2019				26 August 2020			
		ESCI	Si	Mi	ESCI*Si*Mi	ESCI	Si	Mi	ESCI*Si*Mi	ESCI	Si	Mi	ESCI*Si*Mi	ESCI	Si	Mi	ESCI*Si*Mi	ESCI	Si	Mi	ESCI*Si*Mi	ESCI	Si	Mi	ESCI*Si*Mi
1	Steel - Beam/Girder	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0
2	Concrete-Deck Slab	1.1	3	2	6.6	1.1	3	2	6.6	1.1	3	2	6.5	1.1	3	2	6.5	1.1	3	2	6.5	1.1	3	2	6.5
3	Steel - Bracing	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0	1.0	4	1	4.0
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0	1.0	4	2	8.0
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls	1.4	2	2	5.6	1.4	2	2	5.6	1.9	2	2	7.6	1.9	2	2	7.6	1.9	2	2	7.6	1.9	2	2	7.6
7	Piles & Footings	1.2	2	2	4.8	1.2	2	2	4.8	1.2	2	2	4.7	1.2	2	2	4.7	1.2	2	2	4.7	1.2	2	2	4.7
8	Ground around footings	1.0	2	2	4.0	1.0	2	2	4.0	1.0	2	2	4.0	1.0	2	2	4.0	1.0	2	2	4.0	1.0	2	2	4.0
9	Expansion Joints	1.1	1	3	3.3	1.1	1	3	3.3	1.1	1	3	3.3	1.1	1	3	3.3	1.1	1	3	3.3	1.1	1	3	3.3
10	Deck Drains	1.3	3	3	11.3	1.3	3	3	11.3	1.1	3	3	10.1	1.1	3	3	10.1	1.1	3	3	10.1	1.1	3	3	10.1
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed)	1.0	3	3	9.0	1.0	3	3	9.0	1.0	3	3	9.0	1.0	3	3	9.0	1.0	3	3	9.0	1.0	3	3	9.0
12	Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):	1.3	1	1	1.3	1.3	1	1	1.3	1.3	1	1	1.3	1.3	1	1	1.3	1.3	1	1	1.3	1.3	1	1	1.3
13	Railing Paint work	1.5	1	3	4.5	1.5	1	3	4.5	1.6	1	3	4.8	1.6	1	3	4.8	1.6	1	3	4.8	1.6	1	3	4.8
14	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway	1.3	1	3	3.9	1.3	1	3	3.9	1.5	1	3	4.5	1.5	1	3	4.5	1.0	1	3	3.0	1.0	1	3	3.0
15	Bridge Approach Barriers	1.9	1	1	1.9	1.9	1	1	1.9	2.4	1	1	2.4	2.4	1	1	2.4	1.5	1	1	1.5	1.5	1	1	1.5
16	Signs	3.5	1	3	10.5	3.5	1	3	10.5	3.5	1	3	10.5	3.5	1	3	10.5	3.5	1	3	10.5	3.5	1	3	10.5
17	Embankment Erosion	1.4	1	1	1.4	1.4	1	1	1.4	1.4	1	1	1.4	1.4	1	1	1.4	1.3	1	1	1.3	1.3	1	1	1.3
18	Riverbed Scour	1.6	1	5	8.0	1.6	1	5	8.0	3.2	1	5	16.0	3.2	1	5	16.0	3.2	1	5	16.0	3.2	1	5	16.0
19	General Cleaning	2.2	1	3	6.6	2.2	1	3	6.6	2.7	1	3	8.1	2.7	1	3	8.1	2.7	1	3	8.1	2.7	1	3	8.1
Agerage ESCI		1.41	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		106.65	1.41	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		106.65	1.58	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		118.23	1.58	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		118.23	1.50	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		115.73	1.50	Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)		115.73
CF = 0.411A + 0.120E + 0.107R + 0.362I		A=2, E=3, R=3, I=3			2.589	A=2, E=3, R=3, I=3			2.589	A=2, E=3, R=3, I=3			2.589	A=2, E=3, R=3, I=3			2.589	A=2, E=3, R=3, I=3			2.589	A=2, E=2, R=3, I=3			2.589
SHI = CF *Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)/n		SHI = 3.12*106.65/(19)			14.532	SHI = 3.12*106.65/(19)			14.532	SHI = 3.12*118.23/(19)			16.110	SHI = 3.12*118.23/(19)			19.414	SHI = 3.12*115.73/(19)			15.769	SHI = 3.12*115.73/(19)			15.770
OSCI = 1, when SHI = 1 OSCI = 2, when 1<SHI≤16 OSCI = 3, when 16<SHI≤81 OSCI = 4, when 81<SHI≤256		16<SHI≤81			OSCI = 2	16<SHI≤81			OSCI = 2	16<SHI≤81			OSCI = 3	16<SHI≤81			OSCI = 3	16<SHI≤81			OSCI = 2	16<SHI≤81			OSCI = 2

4.3.2 SGBHCA - Bumbu Bridge Results

Bumbu Bridge is one of the three bridges along the Bumbu River built-in 1973. According to Atkins and Walsh (1985), a major flood occurred in the Bumbu River in September 1983, affecting the peaceful coexistence of the river and Lae City. The Bumbu River drains an area of approximately 100 km². The river's catchment is 22 km long, and urban development has taken place over the past four decades along the lower 10 km. It is close to the end of its life span and requires close inspection and monitoring.

Figure 4-11: Photos of Bumbu Bridge in August 2020: Aerial View on Left, Longitudinal View on Right

The Figure 4-11, Photos of Bumbu Bridge in August 2020: Aerial View on Left, Longitudinal View on Right shows the aerial view and longitudinal view of the Bumbu Bridge. The pile caps are already exposing the piles due to the erosion constantly happening in the Bumbu river.

The Figure 4-12, Level 1 SGBCA Result for Bumbu Bridge in December, 2014 shows the result of the routine inspection using the Condition Assessment Level 1 Form. The Figure 4-13, Bumbu Bridge Element Structural Condition Rating (ESCR) shows the condition rating of the Bumbu bridge per condition assessment on its structural health.

● Routine Monitoring Inspection & Condition Assessment Level 1

L1 ROUTINE MONITORING INSPECTION & CONDITION ASSESSMENT		LEVEL 1
DATA COLLECTION FORM		BRIDGE MONITORING
BRIDGE NAME & LOCATION		General Bridge Information
Bridge Name: <u>BUMBU BRIDGE</u> Bridge ID: <u>B_NI 4201_080</u> Road Name: <u>MILFORHAVEN ROAD</u> Road Number: <u>DNK</u> Latitude: <u>6.42'23"</u> Longitude: <u>146.59'56"</u> Altitude: <u>55 m</u> Map Reference: <u>DNK</u> Province: <u>MOROBE</u> District: <u>LAE CITY</u> Weather: <u>FINE/CLOUDY</u> Date: <u>3/12/2014</u> Inspector's Name: <u>G. WANTEPE</u>		Bridge construction type: <u>STANDARD</u> Year of construction: <u>1973</u> Inspection Type: <u>L1 Routine Monitoring Inspection</u> Overall Length (m): <u>50 m</u> Number of Spans: <u>2</u> Waterway Clearance (m): <u>7.3 m</u> Kerb to kerb width (m): <u>8.2 m</u> Clear Vehicle Width (m): <u>7.5 m</u> Walkway Width (m): <u>1.5 m</u> Estimated Vehicles per day: <u>201 - 1000</u>
SPAN DATA		ABUTMENT DATA:
Main Member Type: <u>Girder</u> Secondary Member Type: <u>Girder</u> Other Member Type: <u>Bracing</u> Deck Material: <u>Concrete</u> Deck Wearing Surface (DWS): <u>Bitumen</u> Deck Drainage: <u>Scuppers</u> Parapet: <u>Rails/posts</u> Expansion Joint Type: <u>Steel (Open)</u>		Abutment Type: <u>Reinforced Earth</u> Abutment Material: <u>Concrete</u> Abutment Foundation: <u>DNK (assumption - driven piles)</u> Bearing Type - Abutment: <u>Steel plate/Elastomeric</u> Restraint Type - Abutment: <u>Lateral</u> Scour Protection - Abutment: <u>Steel Sheets</u> Bank/Slope Protection: <u>Steel Pile/Sheets</u>
PIER DATA		MISCELLANEOUS DATA
Pier Type: <u>Single Columns</u> Pier Material: <u>Concrete</u> Pier Foundation Type: <u>DNK (assumption - driven piles)</u> Piers Bearing Type: <u>Not Known</u> Piers Restraint Type: <u>Not Known</u> PIER Scour Protection: <u>None</u>		Design Load (Tonnes): <u>44 T</u> Safe Speed Limit (km/h): <u>DNK</u> Posted Load Limit (Tonnes): <u>DNK</u> Guardrailings: <u>Rails/Posts</u> River Training Type: <u>None</u> Soil Type: <u>Avg. Rock</u> Embankment/Riverbed (erosion/ scour/landslide): <u>Yes</u> No / DNK
BRIDGE CONDITION CHECKLIST		
Condition of Steel Girders <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Minor Corrosion Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Major Corrosion Deterioration <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Level 2 Inspection Condition of Concrete <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Minor Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Major Deterioration - Level 2 Inspection Required Condition of Piers, Abutments and Wings <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Back Slabs Gaping <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Minor Repairs <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Repair or Correction (give details) Condition of Handrail and Kerbs <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Tightening or Straightening <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Painting <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Minor replacement (give details). <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Replacement (give details). Condition of Guard Fencing or Guardrails <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Painting <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Repairs <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement	Condition of Ground Around Footings <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Fire Hazard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Debris Requires Removal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scour (give details) Debris on Deck Surface <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Debris/Rubbish Removal <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Sweeping/Cleaning Condition of Expansion Joints <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable Condition of D.W.S (drive way surface) <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Patching <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Replacement (give details). <input type="checkbox"/> Nil <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Tingling and replacement Condition of Nameboards/Signs/Depth Markers <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Required	Condition of Vegetation <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Spraying <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Removal Condition of Scuppers <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blocked Requires Cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement Condition of Bearings <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Requires Level 2 Inspection <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repair <input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable Condition of Approaches <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Premix <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repairs (give details) Traffic Damaged Members <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes (give details) <input type="checkbox"/> No <i>Damaged guard fencing and rails damaged and requires repair.</i>
Level 1 Condition Rating of the whole structure by inspection? <input type="checkbox"/> 1 Generally in good condition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 Minor defects <input type="checkbox"/> 3 Moderate defects <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Critical condition		Remarks: <i>A lot of routine maintenance works required</i>
Requires Further Detailed Condition Monitoring? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes. <input type="checkbox"/> No.		Remarks: <i>A Level 2 condition rating is required to further assess its condition.</i>
PHOTO LOG		
No.	Photo Description	File Name
	Longitudinal view from upstream	L1 Bumbu Bridge - 03-12-2014
	Corrosion of steel girders	L1 Bumbu Bridge - 03-12-2014
	Damaged guard rails	L1 Bumbu Bridge - 03-12-2014
L2 ACTION REQUIRED		
Detailed Structural Evaluation Required? Detailed Nonstructural Evaluation Required? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes, construction details not available <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, nonstructural hazards identified that should be evaluated <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, condition rating more than cut-off <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No, nonstructural hazards exist that may require mitigation, but a detailed evaluation is not necessary <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, other hazards present <input type="checkbox"/> No, no nonstructural hazards identified <input type="checkbox"/> DNK		
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data DR DNK = Do Not Know		

Figure 4-12: Level 1 SGBCA Result for Bumbu Bridge in December, 2014.

BRIDGE COMPONENT				CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS				
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				Element Structural Condition (ESCR)
				1	2	3	4	
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK								
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)	4	m	60	40	0	0	1.4
2	Concrete-Deck Slab	555	m ²	300	150	105	0	9.15
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members	27	m	80	20	0	0	1.2
SUBSTRUCTURE								
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)	12	m ²	66	33	1	0	1.35
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)	1	m ²	70	30	0	0	1.3
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls	20	m ²	40	30	30	0	1.9
FOUNDATIONS								
7	Piles & Footings	17	item	25	35	20	20	2.35
8	Scouring of foundations	3	item	15	30	25	30	2.7
ACCESSORIES								
9	Expansion Joints	33	m	60	40	0	0	1.4
10	Deck Drains	8	ea	25	50	25	0	2
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed Bearings)	8	ea	10	25	25	40	2.95
12	Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):	8	ea	80	20	0	0	1.2
13	Railing Paint work	700	m	25	50	25	0	2
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS								
14	Bridge Approach Carriageway	2	item	20	30	50	0	2.3
15	Bridge Approach Barriers	40	m	20	30	40	10	2.4
16	Signs (Miscellaneous attachments)	4	item	0	0	50	50	3.5
17	Embankment Erosion	985	m ²	80	20	0	0	1.2
18	Riverbed Scour	2	item	0	10	60	30	3.2
19	General Cleaning	3	item	0	40	50	10	2.7
L1 CONDITION RATING: Note: See further condition rating criteria.				Overall Condition Rating: (without condition factors)				
1 In good condition 2 Minor defects 3 Moderate defects. 4 Critical Condition				$\sum \text{ESCR}/n = $ 2.43				
RECOMMENDATION								
Status of Bridge Health Monitoring?								
<input type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP at L1.								
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level.								
<input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring								
L2 DETAILED INSPECTION REQUIRED? : <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO								

Figure 4-13: Bumbu Bridge Element Structural Condition Rating (ESCR)

The general assessment of the bridge is fair, with most components requiring minor maintenance, repairs or painting. The majority of the bridge components are not in satisfactory shape, as shown in Table 4-3, Level 1 condition assessment of Bumbu Bridge below.

Table 4-3: Level 1 condition assessment of Bumbu Bridge

Component Name	Condition of Components
Steel Girders	Requires Level 2 Inspection
Handrails & Kerbs	Requires Painting and Minor Replacements

Expansion Joints	Requires Cleaning
Bearings	Requires Level 2 Inspection
Concrete	Minor Deterioration
Drive way surface	Requires Replacement
Ground around footings	Requires Debris Removal
Piers, Abutments, Wings	Requires Minor Repairs
Deck Surface	Debris/Rubbish Removal, Sweeping/Cleaning
Scuppers	Blocked Requires Cleaning
Nameboards, signs	None Required
Guard Fencing or Guardrails	Requires Repairs
Vegetation	Requires Cutting/Spraying
Approaches	Requires Repairs
Traffic Damaged Members	Requires Handrails/Guard Fencing on Both Sides

During the inspection on 3rd December 2014, the majority of the elements of the bridge were not in good condition. Handrails and guard fencing on both sides of the bridge were damaged by traffic as shown in the photos show in Figure 4-14 below.

Damaged Kerb on Guard Fence

Damaged Handrails

Scoring around Mid-Span Pier Foundation

Corrosion of Bolt Connection at North Abutment

Scour at South Abutment

Damage by Plant Growth on Side Girder

Figure 4-14: Photos showing condition of Bumbu Bridge in 2015

The level 1 inspection and condition assessment were conducted at a frequency of approximately 6 months. The form in Figure 4-19 presents the Level 1 results from the first inspection of Bumbu Bridge. The subsequent condition assessment results are included in Appendix.

The graph below shows the results for level 1 routine inspection and condition assessment between December 2014 and August 2020 at Bumbu Bridge. The overall bridge structure condition rating is 2. Some maintenance works is required for minor repairs, including non-loading bridge elements.

Figure 4-15: Summary Results for Bumbu Bridge Level 1 Condition Rating

- **Bridge Structure Evaluation and Condition Rating Level 2**

Similar to Butibam Bridge, the elemental structural condition index for Bumbu Bridge has been evaluated considering the parameters mentioned in Chapter 3. Figure 4-17 presents the result for the first Level 2 inspection on 10th of December 2014. The CF value for Bumbu Bridge is 3.00 and when multiplied by 172.20 - sum of result obtained from $ESCI * Si * Mi$, it gives an SHI value of 27.27. As stated in the methodology in Chapter 3, an entire structural element is introduced as OSCI, where the Level 2 OSCI value for Bumbu Bridge is 3 since the SHI value 27.27 falls in the range of OSCI 3 when $16 < SHI \leq 81$. This validates that the bridge is quite old and requires further attention.

L2 BRIDGE STRUCTURE EVALUATION & CONDITION RATING											LEVEL 2																					
DATA COLLECTION FORM											BRIDGE MONITORING																					
BRIDGE NAME: <u>BUMBU BRIDGE</u>				WEATHER: <u>FINE/ SUNNY</u>																												
INSPECTOR(S) NAME: <u>GRACE WANTEPE</u>				DATE: <u>10/12/2014</u>																												
BRIDGE COMPONENT				CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS																												
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				(Refer Condition Rating Criteria)			ESCI*Si*Mi																					
				1	2	3	4	ESCI	Si	MI																						
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK																																
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)	185	m ²	101.8	55.5	27.8	0.0	1.60	4	1	6.40																					
2	Concrete-Deck Slab	555	m ²	305.3	166.5	83.3	0.0	1.60	3	2	9.60																					
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members	37.8	m	20.8	11.3	5.7	0.0	1.60	4	1	6.40																					
SUBSTRUCTURE																																
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)	12	m ²	8.4	1.8	1.2	0.6	1.50	4	2	12.00																					
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)	14	m ²	9.8	2.8	1.4	0.0	1.40	4	2	11.20																					
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls	20	m ²	10.0	6.0	4.0	0.0	1.70	2	2	6.80																					
FOUNDATIONS																																
7	Piles & Footings	17	m	7.7	4.3	3.4	2.6	2.15	2	2	8.60																					
8	Ground around footings	3	m ²	1.2	0.6	0.6	0.6	2.20	2	2	8.80																					
ACCESSORIES																																
9	Expansion Joints	33	m	0.0	16.5	9.9	6.6	2.70	1	3	8.10																					
10	Deck Drains	8	ea	0.0	2.8	1.6	3.6	3.10	3	3	27.90																					
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed)	8	ea	2.0	2.4	2.0	1.6	2.40	3	3	21.60																					
12	Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):	140	m	28.0	42.0	42.0	28.0	2.50	1	1	2.50																					
13	Railing Paint work	700	m	175.0	210.0	175.0	140.0	2.40	1	3	7.20																					
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS																																
14	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway	2	ea	0.8	0.5	0.4	0.3	2.10	1	3	6.30																					
15	Bridge Approach Barriers	40	m	18.0	12.0	10.0	0.0	1.80	1	1	1.80																					
16	Signs/Nameboards	4	item	0.0	0.8	1.2	2.0	3.30	1	3	9.90																					
17	Embankment Erosion	985	m ²	443.3	246.3	197.0	147.8	2.15	1	1	2.15																					
18	Riverbed Scour	2	item	0.9	0.6	0.5	0.0	1.80	1	5	9.00																					
19	General Cleaning	3	item	1.4	0.8	0.6	0.5	2.15	1	3	6.45																					
Σ(ESCI*Si*Mi)								2.11			172.70																					
CF = 0.411A + 0.120E + 0.107R + 0.362I									A=3	E=3	R=3	I=3	3.00																			
Parameters: Adapted from Rashidi & Gibson 2011 A - Age of bridge E - Environmental factor R - Road factor I - Inspection Quality				STRUCTURAL HEALTH INDEX (SHI): $SHI = CF * \Sigma(ESCI*Si*Mi) / n$							27.27																					
Table of Casual Factors <table border="1" style="font-size: small; width: 100%;"> <thead> <tr> <th>A</th> <th>R</th> <th>E</th> <th>I</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1 Recently Built</td> <td>Minor</td> <td>Low</td> <td>Very High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 New</td> <td>Local access</td> <td>Medium</td> <td>High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 Old</td> <td>Collectors</td> <td>High</td> <td>Medium</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4 Very Old</td> <td>Arterials</td> <td>Very High</td> <td>Low</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				A	R	E	I	1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High	2 New	Local access	Medium	High	3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium	4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low	L2 OVERALL STRUCTURE CONDITION INDEX (OSCI): OSCI = 1, when SHI = 1 OSCI = 2, when 1 < SHI ≤ 16 OSCI = 3, when 16 < SHI ≤ 81 OSCI = 4, when 81 < SHI ≤ 256							OSCI = 3	
A	R	E	I																													
1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High																													
2 New	Local access	Medium	High																													
3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium																													
4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low																													
RECOMMENDATION																																
Element Structural Condition Index (ESCI) or Average ESCI of Bridge Health Monitoring? 2.11				<input type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge <input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge				L3 ENGINEERING ANALYSIS REQUIRED? : <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO																								
L3 ACTION/OR FURTHER ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION REQUIRED																																
What general properties of the bridge would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Climatic Conditions (e.g. wind speed/humidity, temperature, air pressure) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Acceleration/Vibration (using accelerometers) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Load <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Displacements - Using what type of sensor/system? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tilt/Slope (using tiltmeters or slope indicators) <input type="checkbox"/> DNK <input type="checkbox"/> Scour (using pneumatic tubes & filters) <input type="checkbox"/> Ground Velocity																																
What properties of the concrete bridge components would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in concrete, steel reinforcing bar, etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (e.g., in concrete and reinforcing bar, etc) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Concrete Cracking (e.g., flexural, shear, shrinkage, D-cracking or spalling/crushing) <input type="checkbox"/> Locating Rebar/Voids or Delaminations <input type="checkbox"/> Concrete Strength (Thermistor or Schid Hammer)																																
What properties of the steel bridge components would you like to monitor? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in plates, rolled sections, connections, etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (portable ultrasonic gusset plate thickness measurements) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fracture (e.g., brittle, ductile, or fatigue) <input type="checkbox"/> Others? specify <input type="checkbox"/> Crack Growth <input type="checkbox"/> DNK																																
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data OR DNK = Do Not Know																																
ADDITIONAL COMMENTS ON REQUIRED ACTIONS & LOCATIONS ON STRUCTURE																																
Structural Health Index (SHI) is 27.27 L2 Overall Structure Condition Index (OSCI) is 3 Further analyze the structure using Structural Analysis Software and Modelling.																																

Figure 4-17: SGBCA Level 2 Result for Bumbu Bridge December, 2014

Moreover, the graph below represents the summary of condition index results from 2014 to 2020 is shown in Figure 4-18.

Figure 4-18: Graph showing the summary of condition index of Bumbu Bridge

According to the inspection and condition assessment results, Bumbu Bridge had an average ESCI value of 2 for all years of inspection, a low SHI of 26.38 and a high SHI of 28.33. However, an OSCI is 3 which means that the Bridge requires further attention to evaluate its structural integrity, its repair and maintenance requirements. All Level 2 bridge structure evaluations and condition assessment results for Butibam Bridge from December 2014 to August 2020 are shown in Table 4-4, Level 2 SGBCA Evaluation of the Overall Structural Condition Index (OSCI) for Bumbu Bridge.

4.4 Engineering Analysis & Safety Evaluation Results Level 3

As mentioned in Chapter 3, various methodologies may be considered as third-level evaluation for bridge health monitoring. For this case study, after the first and second Levels of inspection and condition assessment, the structural integrity is analysed further per the specific issues concerning the bridge's structural health for Butibam and Bumbu Bridges. Their results are presented in the following sub-sections.

4.4.1 Evaluation and Analysis of Butibam Bridge for a 110T Load

Further analysis for the Butibam Bridge with Micro-Strand structural analysis software is made. In the analysis, a load of 110T was used instead of the normal bridge design load of 44T. The heavy load is of a combined gas turbine unit and trailer supposed to transport the gas turbine by PNG Power to one of its substations situated on the other side of the bridge. Because of the heavy load, the request was made to the Department of Works, which the Department engaged a consultant bridge engineering team. The results are presented in Table 4-5, Breakdown from Applied Loads in Main Longitudinal Girders, Department of Works, 2014 and discussed below.

Table 4-5: Breakdown from Applied Loads in Main Longitudinal Girders, Department of Works, 2014

Load Type	Hogging Moment, kNm	Sagging Moment, kNm	Shear Force, kN
Steel Self-Weight	154	60	29
Concrete Self-Weight	659	266	118
Water Pipe	12	14	1
Creep Shrinkage	803	160	34
Live Load	760	682	164
Total	2388	862	346

The maximum ultimate limit hogging moment occurred over the pier in the fourth girder when the live load was driven down the centreline of the bridge. The maximum ultimate limit state sagging moment occurred at the end span in the fifth girder from the downstream side of the bridge. Moreover, a maximum shear force for the ultimate limit state occurred in the fourth girder from the

downstream side of the bridge adjacent to the pier on the centre span side. The table below shows the breakdown of applied loads that contributed to the maximum effects in the main longitudinal girder section.

In 2014, an independent engineering team hired by the Department of Works established an ultimate limit state moment of 2226 kNm for critical hogging moment over intermediate pier. This moment favourably compares to the moment Hogging Moment of 2388 kNm given in Table 4-5 above and confirms that this is the ultimate load effect expected to occur at the pier locations. For the concrete deck slab, the global effects combined with the local effects where the local effects from the concrete self-weight and the wheel loads of the moving loads applied to a transverse frame model. The Table 4-6 Breakdown from Applied Loads in Transverse Deck Slab below shows breakdown from applied loads for deck slab spanning transversely between adjacent beams.

Table 4-6: Breakdown from Applied Loads in Transverse Deck Slab

Load Type	Relative Hogging Moment	Relative Sagging Moment
Concrete Self-Weight	0.5	1.0
Water Pipe	0.3	0.1
Creep Shrinkage	0.0	-0.1
Live Load – Global	8.9	2.2
Live Load - Local	17.5	9.1
Total	27.2	12.3

Selected printouts from Micro-Strand showing the vehicle position on the grillage for the maximum hogging moment, traverse bending moment from live loads and the maximum traverse moment are shown in the following images.

Figure 4-19: Applied Load in grillage for maximum hogging moment, kNm

The Figure 4-19 above shows the position of the vehicle loads for the maximum hogging bending moment, and the Figure 4-20 below shows the traverse bending moment from the local vehicle loads with a maximum value of 10.6 kNm.

Figure 4-20: Live Load, Traverse Bending Moment, kNm

Figure 4-21: Live Load, Longitudinal Bending of Beam 5.

The diagram in Figure 4-21 shows the maximum hogging bending moment in the longitudinal section for the live load. The moment value is 394 kNm. The ultimate limit loads from static and dynamic loads are summarised in the Table 4-7 below.

Table 4-7: Maximum Applied Loads and Section Capacities, Department of Works, 2014

Design Parameter	Maximum Applied ULS Load	Acceptable Loads
Beam Sagging Moment	862 kNm	1617 kNm
Beam Hogging Moment	2388 kNm	4224 kNm
Beam Shear	346 kNm	1332 kNm
Transverse Deck Sagging Moment	12.3 kNm/m	67 kNm/m
Transverse Deck Hogging Moment	27.2 kNm/m	42 kNm/m

The conclusion derived from the results tabulated in the above table, Table 4-7 means that Butibam Bridge has adequate capacity to transport the 110T load of the combined gas turbine unit and trailer. The Bridge is in good condition, and is validated by the results obtained from the condition assessment and evaluation.

4.4.2 Evaluation and Assessment of Bumbu Bridge

The third Level evaluation for Bumbu Bridge was in three different ways for the specific requirement to assess the structural integrity and capability of the bridge. Firstly, the deflection at the mid-span was monitored using Direct Levelling Survey. Secondly, Resensys 2D HRT SenSpot (Sensor) was used to monitor the inclination/tilt movement of the Bumbu Bridge to see if there was any movement due to the scouring at the mid-span foundation exposing the steel piles. And finally, SolidWorks simulation was used to determine or locate any possible location of failure of the bridge due to stress. As discussed earlier in Chapter 3 and the results are discussed in the following subsequent section.

4.4.2.1 Direct Levelling Survey – Deflection Assessment

The literature review and methodology outlined the steps in recording reduced level readings for desired point elevations on the bridge and according to in Chapter 3 it shows the overall points that were taken on the bridge plan. Elevation readings for Girder, G1, were only used for analysis because the

points on G1 were the only ones recorded during normal traffic. The table below, Table 4-8 presents the results collected on the different days in each month with the initial reading in December 2014.

Table 4-8: Elevation Readings of Desired Spots on G1

		REDUCED LEVEL (RL) READINGS FOR GIRDER 1 (G1)					
DATES	17/12/2014	21/01/2015	4/03/2015	18/03/2015	19/05/2015	5/08/2015	24/09/2015
CODES	Initial Readings	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6
STN 1	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000	100.000
STN 2	99.812	99.816	99.816	99.760	99.797	99.814	99.797
G1-1	99.814	99.818	99.818	99.803	99.816	99.818	99.816
G1-2	99.821	99.799	99.801	99.774	99.795	99.799	99.795
G1-3	99.830	99.823	99.830	99.795	99.818	99.826	99.818
G1-4	99.801	99.866	99.839	99.803	99.828	99.834	99.828
G1-5	99.799	99.801	99.804	99.761	99.795	99.803	99.794
G1-6	99.811	99.815	99.824	99.771	99.808	99.818	99.808

The differences in RLs are calculated by subtracting each day's readings from initial readings. The differences are presented below in Table 4-9. Note that ST1 and STN 2 are not included.

Table 4-9: Difference in Reduced Levels (RLs) for Each Day

	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6
STN 1	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
STN 2	0.004	0.004	0.052	0.015	0.002	0.015
G1-1	-0.004	-0.004	0.011	-0.002	-0.004	-0.002
G1-2	0.022	0.020	0.047	0.026	0.022	0.026
G1-3	0.007	0.000	0.035	0.012	0.004	0.012
G1-4	-0.065	-0.038	-0.002	-0.027	-0.033	-0.027
G1-5	-0.002	-0.005	0.038	0.004	-0.004	0.005
G1-6	-0.004	-0.013	0.040	0.003	-0.007	0.003

Table 4-10: Elevation Readings During Normal Traffic on Each Point, mm

	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6
G1-1	-4.00	-4.00	11.00	-2.00	-4.00	-1.56
G1-2	22.00	20.00	47.00	26.00	22.00	24.46
G1-3	7.00	0.00	35.00	12.00	4.00	11.56
G1-4	-65.00	-38.00	-2.00	-27.00	-33.00	-26.96
G1-5	-2.00	-5.00	38.00	4.00	-4.00	5.38
G1-6	-4.00	-13.00	40.00	3.00	-7.00	3.09

Figure 4-22: Displacement Plots for Each Spot-on Girder G1 for 6 Days.

The maximum and minimum deflection for each day is shown in the graphs below. The maximum deflection for Day 1 is 65mm downwards and 22 mm upwards.

Figure 4-23: Graphs showing deflection monitoring readings for Six Consecutive Days at Bumbu Bridge

The experimental results in Figure 4-23 show that the displacements are well below the acceptable limit of 200 mm.

4.4.2.3 Bridge Modelling and Simulation in SolidWorks

- 3D Model of Bumbu Bridge

A SolidWorks model consists of 3D geometry that defines its edges, faces, and surfaces and allows the design of models quickly and precisely. The models are defined by 3D design and based on components. The design process involves the following steps:

- Identify the model requirements
- Conceptualize the model based on the identified needs
- Develop the model based on the concepts.
- Analyze the model
- Prototype the model
- Construct the model
- Edit the model, if needed

The design method selected for modeling the bridge consists in the following steps:

- Creation of fully constrained sketches for all parts
- Creation of 3D parts by applying the appropriate 3D features
- Creation of assembly by mating the parts

Figure 4-24: Compact and Exploded 3D Model of Bumbu Bridge

- Static Finite Element Analysis

Assessing failure requires an accurate and thorough stress analysis in which the largest stresses - principal stresses - that occur at a critical point in the structure under evaluation must be estimated. In addition to defining the principal stresses, one must also be aware of the type of material they are working with. Ductile and brittle materials will typically fail differently, and various theories predict their failure.

Under the most complicated loading conditions, a machine component may be subjected to forces and moments produced by various combinations of direct axial loads, bending loads, direct or transverse shearing loads, torsional loads, and/or surface contact loads. No matter how complicated the geometry of the part or how many different external forces and moments are being applied, the force system can always be resolved into just three resultant forces and three resultant moments, each defined with respect to an arbitrarily chosen x - y - z coordinate system.

Under the most complicated loading conditions, a machine component may be subjected to forces and moments produced by various combinations of direct axial loads, bending loads, direct or transverse shearing loads, torsional loads, and/or surface contact loads. The force system can always be resolved into just three resultant forces. The three resultant moments no matter how complicated the figure of the part or how many different external forces and moments are being applied, each element is defined with respect to an arbitrarily chosen x - y - z coordinate system.

It can be shown that if the selected x - y - z coordinate axes, together with the elemental volume of material, are rotated in three-dimensional space: about the fixed origin, a unique new orientation may be found for which the shearing stress components vanish on all faces of the newly oriented elemental volume. This unique orientation, for which the shearing stress components on all faces of the elemental cube are zero, is called the principal orientation. For the principal orientation, the three mutually perpendicular planes of zero shears are called principal planes and the normal stresses on these principal planes –

planes of zero shears - are called principal normal stresses, or just principal stresses.

The importance of principal stresses lies in the fact that among them will be the largest normal stress that can occur on any plane passing through the point, for the given loading. The principal stresses are usually designated σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_3 . There are always three principal stresses, but some of them may be zero.

There is a second special orientation of coordinate axes that may be found, for which the shearing stresses on the faces of the rotated volume element reach extreme values. Of the three extreme values, one is a maximum, one is a minimum, and the third is a minimum or maximum value. This orientation is called the principal shearing orientation, and the shearing stresses on these three mutually perpendicular principal shearing planes are called principal shearing stresses. The principal shearing planes may have nonzero normal stresses acting on them, depending upon the type of loading, but normal stresses on planes of principal shear are not principal stresses. The importance of principal shearing stresses lies in the fact that among them will be the largest or maximum shearing stress that can occur on any plane passing through the point, for the given loading. The principal shearing stresses are usually designated τ_1 , τ_2 , τ_3 .

Depending upon whether its material behaves in a *brittle* or a *ductile* manner, failure at the governing critical point of a machine component is dependent upon the principle normal stresses, the principal shearing stresses, or some combination of these. In any event, it is important for a designer to be able to calculate principal normal stresses and principal shearing stresses for any combination of applied loads. To do this, the *general stress cubic equation* may be employed to find the principal stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_3 and as a function of the readily calculable components of stress σ_x , σ_y , σ_z , τ_{xy} , τ_{yz} , τ_{zx} relative to any selected x-y-z coordinate system.

The general stress cubic equation, developed from equilibrium concepts, is:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^3 - \sigma^2(\sigma_x + \sigma_y + \sigma_z) + \sigma(\sigma_x\sigma_y + \sigma_y\sigma_z + \sigma_z\sigma_x - \tau_{xy}^2 - \tau_{yz}^2 - \tau_{zx}^2) - \\ - (\sigma_x\sigma_y\sigma_z + 2\tau_{xy}\tau_{yz}\tau_{zx} - \sigma_x\tau_{yz}^2 - \sigma_y\tau_{zx}^2 - \sigma_z\tau_{xy}^2) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

Since all normal and shearing stress components are real numbers, all three roots of the general stress cubic equation are real. These three roots are the principal normal stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_3 . It is also possible to find the directions of principal stress vectors and principal shearing stress vectors if necessary.

Furthermore, it can be shown that the magnitudes of the principal shearing stresses may be calculated from:

$$|\tau_1| = \left| \frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2} \right|, \quad |\tau_2| = \left| \frac{\sigma_3 - \sigma_1}{2} \right|, \quad |\tau_3| = \left| \frac{\sigma_1 - \sigma_2}{2} \right| \quad (4.2)$$

To summarize, if loads and geometry are known for a machine component, a designer may identify the critical point, arbitrarily select a convenient x - y - z coordinate system, and calculate the resultant six stress components σ_x , σ_y , σ_z , τ_{xy} , τ_{yz} , τ_{zx} . The above equations may then be solved to find the principal normal stresses and the principal shearing stresses. This procedure works for all cases. If the case is biaxial, one of the principal stresses will be zero, and if it is uniaxial, two principal stresses will be zero.

Just as stress is an important measure of loading severity, strain may also be an important parameter in assessing failure potential in a system component. Strain is the term used to define the intensity and direction of the deformation at a given critical point, with respect to a specified plane or set of planes passing through the critical point. Analogous to state of stress, the state of strain at a point may be fully defined by six components of strain relative to any selected x - y - z coordinate system: three normal strain components and three shearing strain components. The normal strain components are usually designated as ε_x , ε_y , ε_z and the shearing strain components as γ_x , γ_y , γ_z . Just as the state of stress may be completely defined in terms of three principal stresses and their directions, the state of strain may be completely defined in terms of three principal strains and their directions. The principal strains may be determined

from a general strain cubic equation analogous to the general stress cubic equation and the strain cubic equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^3 - \varepsilon^2(\varepsilon_x + \varepsilon_y + \varepsilon_z) + \varepsilon \left(\varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y + \varepsilon_y \varepsilon_z + \varepsilon_z \varepsilon_x - \frac{1}{4}(\gamma_{xy}^2 + \gamma_{yz}^2 + \gamma_{zx}^2) \right) - \\ - \left(\varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y \varepsilon_z + \frac{1}{4}(\gamma_{xy} \gamma_{yz} \gamma_{zx} - \varepsilon_x \gamma_{yz}^2 - \varepsilon_y \gamma_{zx}^2 - \varepsilon_z \gamma_{xy}^2) \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

This equation is formally the same as the stress cubic equation except that the normal strains and the shearing strains divided by two, replace the normal stresses and shearing stresses. The three solutions of the strain equation are the three principal normal strains $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$.

SolidWorks Simulation employs the matrix approach for evaluating stresses and strains on structures and machine components simply because various algorithms are efficiently implemented in operating systems environments.

The simulation plug-in installed under SolidWorks – CosmosM – considers the stress vector $\vec{\tau}$ at a point in the body is a function of the orientation of the plane on which it acts and is related to the components of the stress vectors on three perpendicular planes passing through the point. The set of nine components, called the stress matrix, defines the state of stress at a point. In Cartesian coordinates these nine components are:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & \sigma_{xy} & \sigma_{xz} \\ \sigma_{yx} & \sigma_{yy} & \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{zx} & \sigma_{zy} & \sigma_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

In CosmosM the deformation state at a point in a deformed body is defined by the strain matrix:

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} & \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{xy} & \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{xz} \\ \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{yx} & \varepsilon_{yy} & \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{yz} \\ \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{zx} & \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{zy} & \varepsilon_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.4)$$

For static simulation, both abutments and the pier are fixed. The loads applied to the model are its own gravity and uniformly distributed pressure of 1000 N/m² as per constructor requirements. Fine standard mesh is applied as shown in Figure 4.25. The result is shown in Figure 4-26, Static Stresses and Displacements on Bridge Model.

Figure 4-25: Fixtures, Loads and Mesh on Bridge Model

Figure 4-26: Static Stresses and Displacements on Bridge Model

- Frequency Analysis

A structure initially disturbed from a rest state will continue in motion without the application of force. For small deformations, this motion can be expressed as the superposition of vibration modes, each of which has a sinusoidal time variation with a distinct frequency. Such motions are called free harmonic vibrations. The modes of vibration are orthogonal, a fact which renders them useful in solving problems of the response of structures under time dependent loading as well as under specified initial conditions.

The variational principle for determination of vibration modes and frequencies is given by:

$$\delta(U + V) = 0 \quad (4.5)$$

The parameter U is the strain energy stored in the body given by:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T C \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} dv \quad (4.6)$$

The kinetic energy V of the body is given by:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V \rho \left[\left(\frac{\partial u_x}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u_y}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] \quad (4.7)$$

For plates and shells the displacements are given by:

$$u_x = \bar{u}_x(x, y, t) + z \Psi_y(x, y, t)$$

$$u_y = \bar{u}_y(x, y, t) - z \Psi_x(x, y, t)$$

$$u_z = \bar{u}_z(x, y, t)$$

With integration over the area of the middle surface, the kinetic energy equation becomes:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \iint_A \left[\rho \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_x}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_y}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_z}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \frac{\rho h^3}{12} \left(\left(\frac{\partial \Psi_x}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_y}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right) \right] dA \quad (4.8)$$

The displacements are expressed as the product of a function of space and a harmonic function of time:

$$u_x = \bar{u}_x(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t}$$

$$u_y = \bar{u}_y(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t}$$

$$u_z = \bar{u}_z(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t}$$

The use of the notations $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \begin{Bmatrix} \bar{u}_x \\ \bar{u}_y \\ \bar{u}_z \end{Bmatrix}$ and $\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ for the strain matrix yields the

variational equation:

$$\delta \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \iiint_V [\bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^T C \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \omega^2 \rho \bar{\mathbf{u}}^T \bar{\mathbf{u}}] dv \right\} = 0 \quad (4.9)$$

The usual finite element approximations then lead to a set of homogeneous simultaneous equations of the form $[K - \omega^2 M]\{q\} = \{0\}$, where K is the static stiffness matrix of the structure and M is a mass matrix. If the interpolation functions for displacements are used to determine the mass matrix M , the result will be banded. It is called the consistent mass matrix since it is consistent with the assumptions used to determine K . Sometimes a diagonal matrix M , called a lumped mass matrix, is used. This implies that the mass of the structure is concentrated at nodal points. There are no terms in the mass matrix for those equations corresponding to minimization with respect to nodal displacement derivatives so that nodal displacement derivatives may be expressed in terms of nodal displacements and eliminated from the equations. Diagonalization of the mass matrix may also be obtained by using a diagonal value which is the sum of all of the mass matrix elements in a given row and avoids the elimination of nodal displacement derivatives.

For values of q other than zero to exist, the matrix of coefficients of $[K - \omega^2 M]\{q\} = \{0\}$ must be singular. Under such requirements the characteristic equation for the vibration frequencies ω is given by:

$$\det |K - \omega^2 M| = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

The corresponding nodal values q which determine the vibration mode shapes are obtained by eliminating one of $[K - \omega^2 M]\{q\} = \{0\}$ equations and solving for $N-1$ of the elements of q in terms of the N^{th} element. The vibration modes may be normalized to satisfy the weighted orthogonality condition:

$$\{q_i\}^T [M] \{q_i\} = \delta_{ij} \quad (4.11),$$

Where:

$$\delta_{ij} = 0 \text{ If } i \neq j$$

$$\delta_{ij} = 1 \text{ If } i = j$$

The column vectors of the matrix V are generated so that each is orthogonal to the two preceding vectors. From the definition $AV = VT$ the following relationship can be derived:

$$AV_i = \beta_{i-1}V_{i-1} + \alpha_iV_i + \beta_{i+1}V_{i+1} \quad (4.13)$$

The parameter V_i is the i^{th} column vector of V and satisfies the relation $V_i^T V_j = \delta_{ij}$. If V_i and V_{i+1} are known, then $\alpha_i = V_i^T AV_i$ and $\beta_i = \sqrt{W_i^T W_i}$, with $W_i = AV_i - \beta_{i-1}V_{i-1} - \alpha_iV_i$ and $V_{i+1} = \frac{1}{\beta_i}W_i$. The sequence of operations is

started by using the first column of the unit vector as V_1 and β_0 taken as zero.

After a number of steps, the Lanczos vectors V_i may lose orthogonality because of truncation of the number of eigenvalues and will require reorthogonalization.

Every structure has the tendency to vibrate at certain frequencies, called natural or resonant frequencies. Each natural frequency is associated with a certain shape, called mode shape that the model tends to assume when vibrating at that frequency. When a structure is properly excited by a dynamic load with a frequency that coincides with one of its natural frequencies, the structure undergoes large displacements and stresses. This phenomenon is known as resonance. For un-damped systems, resonance theoretically causes infinite motion. Damping, however, puts a limit on the response of the structures due to resonant loads.

If the model is subjected to dynamic environments, static studies cannot be used to evaluate the response. Frequency studies can help you avoid resonance and design vibration isolation systems. They also form the basis for evaluating the response of linear dynamic systems where the response of a system to a dynamic environment is assumed to be equal to the summation of the contributions of the modes considered in the analysis. A real model has an infinite number of natural frequencies. However, a finite element model has a finite number of natural frequencies that is equal to the number of degrees of freedom considered in the model. Only the first few modes are needed for most purposes. The natural frequencies and corresponding mode shapes depend on the geometry, material properties, and support conditions. The computation of

natural frequencies and mode shapes is known as modal, frequency, and normal mode analysis.

When building the geometry of a model in Solidworks, you usually create it based on the undeformed shape of the model. The structure's own weight can cause considerable effects on the shape of the structure and its modal properties. The loads affect the modal characteristics of a body. The effect can be ignored because the induced deflections are small in many cases. In general, the compressive loads decrease resonant frequencies and tensile loads increase them. It is demonstrated by changing the tension on a violin string: the higher the tension, the higher the frequency. The designer must use the Direct Sparse solver to include the effect of loading on the resonant frequencies. If the Solver option is set to Automatic, the Direct Sparse solver will be used if loads are defined for a frequency study.

In order to perform frequency analysis in SolidWorks the following steps are implemented:

- Creation of a frequency study. Right-click the top icon in the Simulation study tree and select Properties. Define the Properties of the study to set the number of frequencies. The program calculates the lowest five modes by default. If the program detects rigid body modes, it lists them first. In this case, you need to increase the number of modes to let the program calculate the non-rigid body modes.
- Define material for each solid, shell, and beam. To define a material for a solid, shell, or beam, right-click its icon in the Simulation study tree and select Apply/Edit Material. Note that density is a required material property.
- If applicable, define appropriate restraints. For unrestrained or not adequately supported models, both the FFEPlus and Direct Sparse solvers detect rigid body modes automatically. If detected in rigid body modes, they are counted among the requested number of modes. For example, if the designer is interested in the first five elastic modes for an unsupported solid model, he must set the required modes to 11: six for

the rigid body modes and five for the elastic modes. Using the Direct Sparse solver, the designer must apply adequate restraints to stabilize the model. To stabilize the model option, it activates the Use soft spring. However, improper application of restraints can over-stiffen the model. It adversely affects the elastic modes. To overcome the singularity issue, ease the frequency shift option for frequency analysis as it cannot run due to singularity of the stiffness matrix. Increase the shift value gradually from zero until the Direct Sparse solver successfully calculates the requested frequencies. The Direct Sparse solver selectively calculates the requested number of frequencies if setting a higher value for the frequency shift, which is clustered around the shift value. Thus, it is possible to avoid the computation of lower range frequencies, which are of no interest to analysis and save computational time.

- Define loads if desired. Loads are not required but are used if defined. The Direct Sparse solver is required to solve frequency problems with defined loads. For assemblies and multi-body parts make sure to define the proper contact settings. Contact conditions other than free and bonded are not allowed in frequency studies.
- Mesh the model and run the study. Before running the study, you can use the Result Options to request generating plots for all mode shapes automatically. If you run a study before meshing it, the program meshes the study automatically before running it. You can also request to run the study by checking Run analysis after meshing in the Mesh Property Manager.

Figure 4-27: Modal Analysis Results

The mode number, natural frequencies and periods for the first five vibration modes alongside the amplitude plot for the first mode are listed and illustrated in figure 4.27.

At this point in simulation, the random vibration analysis of the bridge is critical, and such a study is derived from the frequency study discussed above. The bridge is subject to an acceleration PSD – Power Spectral Density – profile recommended by the American Society of Civil Engineers. The study is a stochastic process, generally viewed as a family of random variables or a collection of many records that describe a physical phenomenon. This records can be a function time $x_k(t)$ or frequency $x_k(f)$ and record is somewhat different from any other record. Therefore, include all possible records in the analysis. Each load in a random vibration study is a random process. A random process is described in terms of statistical properties. The response of a model to these loads is also a random process described in statistical terms.

Figure 4-28: Amplitude Plots for the First Five Modes

The Autocorrelation Function is defined as the expected value of the product of a random variable with a time-shifted version of itself. It is a random process that describes the correlation between the values in a record at different instants of time.:

$$R_x(\tau) = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\tau} \int_{-\frac{\tau}{2}}^{\frac{\tau}{2}} x(t)x(t+\tau)dt \tag{4.14}$$

The *Mean Square* value provides a measure of the energy associated with the random process and it is defined as the value of the autocorrelation function for $\tau = 0$:

$$E(x^2) = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_{-\frac{\tau}{2}}^{\frac{\tau}{2}} x^2(t)dt \tag{4.15}$$

The parameter $E(x^2)$ is called *Expectation Operator*. The positive square root of the mean value is known as the *Root Mean Square* or rms. Variance is the mean square value of a random process about its mean μ_x and is defined as:

$$\sigma_x^2 = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\tau} \int_{-\frac{\tau}{2}}^{\frac{\tau}{2}} [x(t) - \mu_x]^2 dt \quad (4.16)$$

The positive square root of the variance is known as *Standard Deviation*. Finally, the *Power Spectral Density* is defined as the Fourier transform of the autocorrelation function of a random process:

$$S_x(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} R_x(\tau) e^{-i\omega\tau} d\tau \quad (4.17)$$

The power spectral density describes how the energy of the random process is distributed in the frequency domain.

With the above definitions a random vibration study can be defined, run and interpreted. The bridge model is subject to a base excitation with a power spectral density $S_x(\omega) = 1g^2/Hz$ in vertical plane.

The selection of a proper damping coefficient is another important aspect in performing random vibration analysis because of damping ratio variations and the need to model internal structural damping. One approach – implemented in SolidWorks Simulation - is to employ the Rayleigh viscous damping model by introducing the system damping matrix C defined as:

$$C = \mu M + \lambda K \quad (4.18)$$

The significance of parameters involved in (4.18) is:

- μ - Mass Proportional Rayleigh Damping Coefficient
- λ - Stiffness Proportional Rayleigh Damping Coefficient
- M - System Structural Mass Matrix
- K - System Structural Stiffness Matrix

With this formulation the damping ratio is the same for axial, bending and torsional response. The Rayleigh damping results in different damping ratios for different response frequencies, according to the equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\mu}{\omega_i} + \lambda \omega_i \right) \quad (4.19)$$

In (4.19), ζ is the damping ratio and ω_i is the frequency response in rad/s. It can be noted that the mass proportionality term gives a damping ratio inversely proportional to the frequency response and the stiffness proportional term gives a damping ratio linearly proportional to response frequency, as shown in Figure 4-29 below.

Figure 4-29: Damping Ratio versus Frequency Response in Rayleigh Damping

Rayleigh Damping can also be expressed as:

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\mu}{\omega_i} + \lambda \omega_i \right) = \frac{\alpha}{2\omega_i} + \frac{\beta \omega_i}{2} \quad (4.20)$$

In (4.20), $\alpha = \zeta \frac{2\omega_i \omega_j}{\omega_i + \omega_j}$ and $\beta = \zeta \frac{2}{\omega_i + \omega_j}$. In the simulation discussed here, $\alpha = 0.2$ and $\beta = 0.4$. The simulation results are shown below.

Figure 4-30: RMS of the UY Component of the Bridge Model

Figure 4-31: Frequency Responses versus Mode Number

The maximum RMS of the UY component is 90.025 mm. Assuming a zero mean and Gaussian probability distribution:

- The probability that the magnitude of UY will not exceed 90.025 mm is 68.27%.
- The probability that the magnitude of UY will not exceed 2X90.025 mm or 2XRMS is 95.45%.
- The probability that the magnitude of UY will not exceed 3X 90.025 mm or 3*RMS is 99.73%.

The results are good match for the experimental evaluations on Bumbu bridge performed in the last 10 years and validate the simulation.

Chapter 5 : Conclusions

5.1 Summary

In the literature review, it was noted that bridge monitoring is not a new technology or trend. Since ancient times, engineers, architects and artisans have been keen on observing the behaviour of built structures to discover any sign of degradation and extend their knowledge and improve the design of future structures. Ancient builders would observe and record crack patterns in stone and masonry bridges, according to Levi and Salvadori (1992). Those failures and their analysis have led to new insight and improved design of future structures. Engineering curiosity and economic considerations drive this continued struggle to improve our structures. As for any engineering problem, obtaining reliable data is always the first and fundamental step toward finding a solution. Monitoring structures is our way to get qualitative or quantitative data about our bridges and help us make informed decisions about their health and destiny. Over the years, designers and researchers have been enhancing the safety and durability of bridges by monitoring through advanced systems in science and technology. Many recent researchers are developing various methods for BSHM, and these include M. Reda & J. (2005), Efstathiades, Boniotopoulos, Nazarko, L., & Stavroulakis (2007), Lu & Michaels (2005), and Ghoshal, Sundaresan, M.J.Schulz, & Pai (2000). Modal properties and quantities derived from these properties, such as curvature of mode shape and dynamic flexibility matrix indices, have been the principal features used to identify damage in bridge structures. However, challenges lie in the inconsistency of environment and operating condition of bridge monitoring application.

Bridge infrastructures are significant assets in any nation's modern road transport system, including PNG. The in-service bridges are constantly exposed to destructive effects of material aging, corrosion of structural steel elements, high traffic volume and heavy loading. These factors, combined with defects of design and construction or damage due to accidents speed the deterioration of structural bridge components resulting in the loss of load-carrying capacity and

is confirmed by Kekare, Huddedar, & Bagde (2014) and Dong & Song (2010). The current bridge inspection practice in PNG is inadequate, and bridge maintenance is often overlooked. It leads to bridge deterioration and collapse due to flooding or old age. This research looked at many methods and technologies practised in structural health monitoring worldwide. Given the time limitation and the conditions for applications, including considering the cost of purchasing various SHM equipment, the only method deemed reliable and applicable for bridges in the PNG context is a visual inspection and condition assessment. Visually inspecting and assessing the damages or defects is the first step in any bridge monitoring practice. Moreover, visual inspection and evaluation of any bridge structure at the earliest possible stage is vital because it is very costly to replace a bridge in Lae City or PNG.

Steel Girder Bridge is common on the national roads and highways of PNG because girders are easily designed and constructed to carry the maximum T44 vehicle load. The bridge may be in good condition, but monitoring the bridge components is essential because of various factors such as increased service loads, fatigue, corrosion deterioration, scouring and lack of proper maintenance that are contributing to the deterioration of the composite steel bridge. Steel girders are the main load-carrying members of the bridge structure that support the bridge deck and transfer loads to piers or abutments. These steel girders at different positions of the bridge suffer a different degree of damage and the main one being corrosion. Corrosion deterioration remains a major concern for the safety and durability of steel bridges near marine environments. Therefore, routine and scheduled monitoring of bridge structures and applying appropriate maintenance methods to rectify identified defects and damages at an early stage extends the life of a deficient bridge.

Bridge inspection and condition assessments are necessary to effectively manage bridge assets in Lae City and the country as a whole. Once structural integrity issues are identified in the bridge structure and components, they can be planned and programmed for maintenance and repair depending on the availability of funds. Bridge condition assessments will also improve knowledge and understanding of the structural behaviour of the material, detect damage at its onset, assures owners of the structure's strength and serviceability, reduces

downtime and results in improved maintenance practices and management of limited funds and resources. The thesis identified some common issues and problems affecting the service life of steel girder bridges in PNG. It also identified how visual inspection and condition assessment forms are applied to steel girder bridges to improve their condition. This study carried out a visual inspection and condition assessment of the Bumbu and Butibam steel girder bridge on three assessment levels. The methodology used in this case study for condition assessment of the two-steel girder bridge provides a common understanding of the bridge's current condition state. It is validated with bridge model simulations using Solid Works. Conclusions and results are briefly discussed below.

5.2 Conclusions and Results

This thesis aims to develop bridge condition assessment forms to improve the condition assessment of steel girder bridges through the three main goals. The first was to create a reliable and effective steel girder bridge condition assessment rating criteria that considered common factors contributing to the bridge damage and deterioration. A thorough review of the current concepts, methods and technologies in developed countries such as Australia was considered. The developed forms are unique because of the vital parameters and factors incorporated into evaluating the bridge's structural components. Hence, this case study developed bridge inspection and condition assessment forms for steel girder bridges. The forms were developed for three levels. There were two forms developed for Level 1 since no bridge information and data was available at the time of research.

Visual inspection and assessment of damages or defects of bridges at the earliest possible stage are vital because it is costly to replace a bridge. Hence, the second objective of this paper was to apply the bridge condition inspection and assessment form on steel girder bridges, Bumbu and Butibam, of Lae City, to validate the reliability of the developed forms. The two bridges have been chosen because both are on institutional roads where they connect major institutions and industries in the northern part of the city to the main city centre. The study applied the forms in three levels as specified in the conceptual

framework in Figure 3-1, and required data were collected during inspections. The final results obtained from applying the steel girder condition assessment of the Bumbu and Butibam bridges indicated the overall condition state of the bridges. The OSCI was expressed as numbers 1 to 4 to understand the condition and compare it with each other. OSCI value of 4 indicates the worst condition of a bridge that might require urgent attention, and an OSCI value of 1 represents a new bridge. The conclusions of the application of these forms are compelling. The condition rating for each bridge element eventually led to the overall bridge structure condition index, which can be utilized for planning and maintenance purposes. A list of significant results obtained is provided below.

- The first inspection results of the Butibam bridge showed the majority of the components to be satisfactory, with an ESCR value of 1.41 and an SHI value of 14.53. Since the SHI value was below 16, it was categorized under the OSCI value of 2. This result was reliable because the Butibam bridge was recently reconstructed in 1997 and has been in service for 23 years. The value was along the same range throughout the inspection and evaluation period.
- It was also observed from the results of the Butibam bridge that the ESCR value falls between the range of 1.41 to 1.58. Moreover, it had 4 times SHI value below 16 with an OSCI value of 2 and high 2 times SHI values more than 16 for and OSCI value of 3. It was also noted that during that period the OSCI value of 3 was because of maintenance that happened.
- The Microstran structural analysis of the Butibam also confirmed the structural integrity of the steel girders from a 110T (tonnes) load, which is more than the normal design load of the bridge, which is 44T (tonnes). Given the properties and size of the steel girders, the maximum loads applied were below the acceptable limits. For example, the maximum hogging moment of 2388 kN.m applied was below the 4224 kN.m acceptable loads.
- During the first inspection of Bumbu bridge, most of the bridge components required minor maintenance or repairs. There was corrosion all over the steel girders, and deep scouring of bridge center piers the southern end of the bridge embankment. The ESCI value was 2.11 from

the first condition assessment. Even throughout the inspections and evaluations, the ESCI values were all above 2, with a low ESCI of 2.02 to 2.06.

- Bumbu bridge had a low SHI value 26.38 to a high SHI value of 28.34 which implied that the bridge had a OSCI value of 3 all throughout the inspection and assessment period. This shows that the bridge requires further attention and the identified issues needed to be rectified soon.
- The midspan deflection of the Bumbu bridge was monitored from direct levelling surveying and the maximum deflection was 65 mm which was okay and below the acceptable limit of 200 mm.
- Therefore, the Bumbu bridge was further modelled using Solidworks software to evaluate the static stresses and displacements and other analysis including frequency/modal analysis, and amplitude plots for the modes. From the Solidworks analysis report from the applied loads, it showed that stress is high at the mid-spans and the overall results did not pose any bigger danger.
- According to the Level 1 inspection results, a recently constructed bridge like Butibam (23 years in service) does not pose much risk to the safety of the public and the risks are minor, as no structural integrity issues have been identified. However, Bumbu bridge being the oldest with almost 49 years of operation, found out to have more structural integrity issues. This is due to no proper routine maintenance, which is neglected for bridges in PNG.
- Bridge condition assessment and condition rating is very vital to evaluate the structures strength and serviceability, thus reducing downtime and result in improved maintenance practices and management of limited resources.
- According to the results, the member stiffness of the two bridges is ok, however, Bumbu Bridge is currently undergoing excessive vibration during normal traffic. The deflection values for Bumbu Bridge are below the maximum values of 197.8 mm for the whole bridge and 98.8 mm for the respective spans as per the general formula of length divided by 250 ($L/250$).

The third objective of this study was to conduct finite element analysis on the two (2) pilot bridges as supplement to the proposed assessment system. Nevertheless, Butibam bridge used the Microstran structural analysis software for the analysis to check its structural capability. The finite element analysis on Bumbu bridge using Solidworks software analysis proved the bridge to be in good condition, however, scouring on the pier and embankments should be monitored closely including the steel girders due to fatigue caused by corrosion.

In summary, it was found out that more accurate results should be obtained for deflection and damage detection, but when this is not present, the condition monitoring forms provides good results for the overall condition rating of the steel girders and the bridge elements.

5.3 Suggestions for Future Research

The in-service bridge structures and components are constantly exposed to destructive effects of fatigue and corrosion including hydraulic effects such as scouring of abutments and supports plus poor maintenance. Moreover, increased service loads and the environment where the bridge is located also contribute to the degradation and deterioration of the bridge structures and components. The Level 1 condition inspection and assessment of bridge infrastructures should do at an interval of 6 months. This study showed that, even after maintenance, accidents do occur where vehicle impacts of the parapets are most likely occurring. This is true and has been observed on several accidents happened at Bumbu Bridge soon after it was maintained in June 2014 and these deformations due to vehicle impacts were still not maintained.

There are a lot of opportunities for future research stemming from the work presented in this report for further improvements. Firstly, there are multiple additional aspects which could be investigated to incorporated into the methodology presented for the development of the forms for steel girder bridge condition assessment. Another most important thing to consider is the damage and deflection detection of the steel girders. This is because steel girders are

the main load carrying elements, and their structural integrity, reliability and capability should be monitored to better understand even the effects assessed in this thesis. Another option for future study, would be to include a greater variety of SHM system including wireless sensors and networks, vibration-based damage detection, fibre optic sensors, etc. to further evaluate and understand the issues posed by each damage on the bridge components.

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Appendix 1: Level 1 SGB Condition Assessment Forms (1 & 2)

L1 ROUTINE MONITORING INSPECTION & CONDITION ASSESSMENT DATA COLLECTION FORM		LEVEL 1 BRIDGE MONITORING	
BRIDGE LOCATION		General Bridge Information	
Bridge Name:	Bridge ID:	Bridge construction type:	Year of construction:
Road Name:	Road Number:	Inspection Type:	
Latitude:	Longitude:	Overall Length (m):	Number of Spans:
Altitude:	Map Reference:	Waterway Clearance (m):	
Province:	District:	Kerb to kerb width (m):	
Weather:	Date:	Clear Vehicle Width (m):	Walkway Width (m):
Inspector's Name:		Estimated Vehicles per day:	
SPAN DATA		ABUTMENT DATA:	
Main Member Type:		Abutment Type:	
Secondary Member Type:		Abutment Material:	
Other Member Type:		Abutment Foundation:	
Deck Material:		Bearing Type - Abutment:	
Deck Wearing Surface (DWS):		Restraint Type - Abutment:	
Deck Drainage:	Parapet:	Scour Protection - Abutment:	
Expansion Joint Type		Bank/Slope Protection:	
PIER DATA		MISCELLANEOUS DATA	
Pier Type:		Design Load (Tonnes):	Safe Speed Limit (km/h):
Pier Material:		Posted Load Limit (Tonnes):	
Pier Foundation Type:		Guardrailings:	
Piers Bearing Type:		River Training Type:	
Piers Restraint Type:		Soil Type:	
PIER Scour Protection:		Embankment/Riverbed (erosion/ scour/landslid):	Yes / No / DNK
BRIDGE CONDITION CHECKLIST			
Condition of Steel Girders <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Minor Corrosion Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Major Corrosion Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Level 2 Inspection Condition of Concrete <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Minor Deterioration <input type="checkbox"/> Major Deterioration - Level 2 Inspection Required Condition of Piers, Abutments and Wings <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Back Slabs Gaping <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Minor Repairs <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Repair or Correction (give details) Condition of Handrail and Kerbs <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Tightening or Straightening <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Painting <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Minor replacement (give details). <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Replacement (give details). Condition of Guard Fencing or Guardrails <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Painting <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repairs <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement		Condition of Ground Around Footings <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Fire Hazard <input type="checkbox"/> Debris Requires Removal <input type="checkbox"/> Scour (give details) Debris on Deck Surface <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Debris/Rubbish Removal <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Sweeping/Cleaning Condition of Expansion Joints <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable Condition of D.W.S (drive way surface) <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Patching <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Major Replacement (give details). <input type="checkbox"/> Nil <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Tingling and replacement Condition of Nameboards/Signs/Depth Markers <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> None <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement <input type="checkbox"/> Required	
Condition of Vegetation <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Spraying <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Removal Condition of Scuppers <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Blocked Requires Cleaning <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Replacement Condition of Bearings <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Level 2 Inspection <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repair <input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable Condition of Approaches <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Premix <input type="checkbox"/> Requires Repairs (give details) Traffic Damaged Members <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (give details) <input type="checkbox"/> No			
Level 1 Condition Rating of the whole structure by inspection? <input type="checkbox"/> 1 Generally in good condition <input type="checkbox"/> 2 Minor defects <input type="checkbox"/> 3 Moderate defects <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Critical condition		Remarks: _____ _____ _____	
Requires Further Detailed Condition Monitoring Inspection? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		Remarks: _____ _____ _____	
PHOTO LOG			
No.	Photo Description	File Name	
L2 ACTION REQUIRED			
Detailed Structural Evaluation Required? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, construction details not available <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, condition rating more than cut-off <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, other hazards present		Detailed Nonstructural Evaluation Required? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, nonstructural hazards identified that should be evaluated <input type="checkbox"/> No, nonstructural hazards exist that may require mitigation, but a detailed evaluation is not necessary <input type="checkbox"/> No, no nonstructural hazards identified <input type="checkbox"/> DNK	
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data OR DNK = Do Not Know			

L1 SGB CONDITION ASSESSMENT FORM DATA COLLECTION FORM						LEVEL 1 CONDITION ASSESSMENT				
BRIDGE COMPONENT						CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS				
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				Element Structural Condition (ESCR)		
				1	2	3	4			
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK										
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)		m						0	
2	Concrete-Deck Slab		m ²						0	
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members		m						0	
SUBSTRUCTURE										
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)		m ²						0	
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)		m ²						0	
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls		m ²						0	
FOUNDATIONS										
7	Piles & Footings		item						0	
8	Scouring of foundations		item						0	
ACCESSORIES										
9	Expansion Joints		m						0	
10	Deck Drains		ea						0	
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed Bearings)		ea						0	
12	Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):		ea						0	
13	Railing Paint work		m						0	
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS										
14	Bridge Approach Carriageway		item						0	
15	Bridge Approach Barriers		m						0	
16	Signs (Miscellaneous attachments)		item						0	
17	Embankment Erosion		m ²						0	
18	Riverbed Scour		item						0	
19	General Cleaning		item						0	
L1 CONDITION RATING: Note: See further condition rating criteria.						Overall Condition Rating: (without condition factors)				
1 In good condition 2 Minor defects 3 Moderate defects. 4 Critical Condition						$\sum \text{ESCR}/n =$				0.00
RECOMMENDATION										
Status of Bridge Health Monitoring?										
<input type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP at L1.										
<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level.										
<input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring										
L2 DETAILED INSPECTION REQUIRED? : <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO										
L2 ACTION REQUIRED										
Detailed Structural Evaluation Required?			Detailed Nonstructural Evaluation Required?							
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, construction details not available			<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, nonstructural hazards indentified that should be evaluated							
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, condition rating more than cut-off			<input type="checkbox"/> No, nonstructural hazards exist that may require mitigation, but a detailed evaluation is not necessary							
<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, other hazards present			<input type="checkbox"/> No, no nonstructural hazards identified <input type="checkbox"/> DNK							
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data <u>OR</u> DNK = Do Not Know										

Appendix 2: Level 2 SGB Structure Evaluation & Condition Rating Form

L2 BRIDGE STRUCTURE EVALUATION & CONDITION RATING										LEVEL 2																					
DATA COLLECTION FORM										BRIDGE MONITORING																					
BRIDGE NAME: _____					WEATHER: _____																										
INSPECTORS NAME: _____					DATE: _____																										
BRIDGE COMPONENT					CONDITION STATE FOR BRIDGE ELEMENTS																										
Element No.	Description of Element	Total Quantity	Units of Measurements	Estimated Quantity in Condition State				Refer Condition Rating Criteria			ESCR*Si*Mi																				
				1	2	3	4	ESCI	Si	MI																					
SUPERSTRUCTURE/DECK																															
1	Steel - Beam/Girder (Load Bearing)		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
2	Concrete-Deck Slab		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
3	Steel - Diaphragm/Bracing/Secondary Members		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
SUBSTRUCTURE																															
4	Concrete-Pier (Diaphragm/Headstock)		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
5	Concrete - Pier (excl. any Headstock or Piles)		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
6	Concrete-Abutment and Wingwalls		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
FOUNDATIONS																															
7	Piles & Footings		m					0.00			0.00																				
8	Ground around footings		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
ACCESSORIES																															
9	Expansion Joints		m					0.00			0.00																				
10	Deck Drains		ea					0.00			0.00																				
11	Bearings (Elastomeric/Metal Fixed)		ea					0.00			0.00																				
12	Parapets (kerbs/rails & barriers):		m					0.00			0.00																				
13	Railing Paint work		m					0.00			0.00																				
MISCELLANEOUS & OTHERS																															
14	Bridge Approach Road/Carriageway		ea					0.00			0.00																				
15	Bridge Approach Barriers		m					0.00			0.00																				
16	Signs		item					0.00			0.00																				
17	Embankment Erosion		m ²					0.00			0.00																				
18	Riverbed Scour		item					0.00			0.00																				
19	General Cleaning		item					0.00			0.00																				
Σ(ESCR*Si*Mi)											0.00																				
CF = 0.411A + 0.120E + 0.107R + 0.362I											A=3 E=4 R=3 I=3	3.10																			
Parameters: Adapted from Rashindi & Gibson 2011 A - Age of bridge E - Environmental factor R - Road factor I - Inspection							STRUCTURAL HEALTH INDEX (SHI): $SHI = CF * \Sigma(ESCR*Si*Mi) / n$				0.00																				
Table of Casual Factors <table border="1" style="width:100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th>A</th> <th>R</th> <th>E</th> <th>I</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>1 Recently Built</td> <td>Minor</td> <td>Low</td> <td>Very High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 New</td> <td>Local access</td> <td>Medium</td> <td>High</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 Old</td> <td>Collectors</td> <td>High</td> <td>Medium</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4 Very Old</td> <td>Arterials</td> <td>Very High</td> <td>Low</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>							A	R	E	I	1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High	2 New	Local access	Medium	High	3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium	4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low	L2 OVERALL STRUCTURE CONDITION RATING (OSCR): OSCR = 1, when SHI = 1 OSCR = 2, when 1 < SHI ≤ 16 OSCR = 3, when 16 < SHI ≤ 81 OSCR = 4, when 81 < SHI ≤ 256				=
A	R	E	I																												
1 Recently Built	Minor	Low	Very High																												
2 New	Local access	Medium	High																												
3 Old	Collectors	High	Medium																												
4 Very Old	Arterials	Very High	Low																												
RECOMMENDATION Status of Bridge Health Monitoring? <input type="checkbox"/> Green Green = 1 - 2 If Green then STOP at L1. <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow Yellow = 2.1 - 3 If Yellow then proceed on to Next Bridge <input type="checkbox"/> Red Red = 3.1 - 4 If Red then proceed on to Next Bridge Monitoring Level.						L3 DETAILED INSPECTION REQUIRED? : <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO																									
L1 OVERALL CONDITION RATING? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO																															
L3 ACTION/OR FURTHER ANALYTICAL INVESTIGATION REQUIRED What general properties of the bridge would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Climatic Conditions (e.g. wind speed/humidity, temperature, air pressure) <input type="checkbox"/> Acceleration/Vibration (using accelerometers) <input type="checkbox"/> Load <input type="checkbox"/> Displacements - Using what type of sensor/system? <input type="checkbox"/> Tilt/Slope (using tiltmeters or slope indicators) <input type="checkbox"/> DNK <input type="checkbox"/> Scour (using pneumatic tubes & filters) <input type="checkbox"/> Ground Velocity																															
What properties of the concrete bridge components would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in concrete, steel reinforcing bar, etc) <input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (e.g., in concrete and <input type="checkbox"/> Concrete Cracking (e.g., flexural, shear, shrinkage, D-cracking or spalling/crushing) <input type="checkbox"/> Locating Rebar/Voids or Delaminations <input type="checkbox"/> Concrete Strength (Thermistor or Schid)																															
What properties of the steel bridge components would you like to monitor? <input type="checkbox"/> Strain (e.g., in plates, rolled sections, connections, etc.) <input type="checkbox"/> Corrosion (portable ultrasonic gusset plate thickness measurements) <input type="checkbox"/> Fracture (e.g., brittle, ductile, or fatigue) <input type="checkbox"/> Others? specify <input type="checkbox"/> Crack Growth <input type="checkbox"/> DNK																															
Where information cannot be verified, Inspector shall note the following: EST = Estimated or unreliable data DNK = Do Not Know																															
ADDITIONAL COMMENTS ON REQUIRED ACTIONS & LOCATIONS ON STRUCTURE <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 100px;"></div>																															

Appendix 3: DOW Bridge Inspection Form (Pages 1, 2 & 3)

Bridge Name:		Principle:		Bridge ID:			
Inspector's Name:		Other:		Inspection Date:			
LOCATION							
Road Name:		Road No:					
Section Start Point:		Section ID:					
River Name:		Offset Distance:		m			
GPS Data:		Latitude	Longitude	Altitude (m)	Chainage:		
Low chainage end		S	E		Province:		
High chainage end		S	E		District:		
Note: All fields marked with an asterisk (*) must be completed							
GENERAL BRIDGE DATA				Comments/Notes			
Type of Bridge*		Bridge History*					
<input type="checkbox"/> Standard		Year of Construction					
<input type="checkbox"/> Special		Year of Last Major Maintenance					
<i>Special bridges are major or complex bridges that require additional inventory</i>							
Terrain Crossed							
<input type="checkbox"/> Creek/Stream		<input type="checkbox"/> River	<input type="checkbox"/> Swamp	<input type="checkbox"/> Estuary (salt water)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Sea (exposed)		<input type="checkbox"/> Road	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)				
Bridge Deck Construction Form							
<input type="checkbox"/> Fixed end		<input type="checkbox"/> Simply Supported		<input type="checkbox"/> Other			
<input type="checkbox"/> Continuous		<input type="checkbox"/> Cantilevered and suspended span					
Bridge Construction Type (BCT)*							
BCT ID:	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	BCT ID:	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3
Bailey	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Truss	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Girder	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Log	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Beam and slab	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Portal	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Most structures are of only one type of construction. Some bridges are of more than one type of construction; these shall be listed in order of importance.</i>							
Bridge Geometry							
Number of Lanes*		Number of Walkways*		Number of Spans*			
Spans							
Length (m)							
BCT ID							
Overall Length (m)*		Kerb to kerb width (m)*					
Vertical Overhead Clearance (m)		Clear Vehicle Width (m)*					
Waterway Clearance (m)		Walkway Width (m)					
Estimated Average Daily Traffic							
Vehicles per day		<input type="checkbox"/> 0-50		<input type="checkbox"/> 51-200			
		<input type="checkbox"/> 201-1,000		<input type="checkbox"/> > 1,000			
Alternative Route?							
Yes		No		Estimated detour Length			
<input type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>		Estimated detour time			
SPAN DATA							
Parapet							
<input type="checkbox"/> None							
<input type="checkbox"/> Rails		<input type="checkbox"/> Timber		<input type="checkbox"/> Steel			
<input type="checkbox"/> Posts		<input type="checkbox"/> Timber		<input type="checkbox"/> Steel			
<input type="checkbox"/> Wall		<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete		<input type="checkbox"/> Masonry			
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other			
Deck Wearing Surface*							
<input type="checkbox"/> Bitumen		<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete		<input type="checkbox"/> Timber planks			
<input type="checkbox"/> Other		<input type="checkbox"/> None		<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel			
Deck Material*							
<input type="checkbox"/> Timber		<input type="checkbox"/> Steel		<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete			
<input type="checkbox"/> Other		<input type="checkbox"/> None		<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel			
Deck Drainage							
<input type="checkbox"/> None							
<input type="checkbox"/> Scuppers		<input type="checkbox"/> Piped		<input type="checkbox"/> Deck crossfall			
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other			
Expansion Joint Type*							
<input type="checkbox"/> None							
<input type="checkbox"/> Air (open) gap		<input type="checkbox"/> Bitumen filled		<input type="checkbox"/> Rubber seal			
<input type="checkbox"/> Steel finger		<input type="checkbox"/> Sliding plate		<input type="checkbox"/> Rubber extrusion			
				<input type="checkbox"/> Not known			

Bridge Name: #Name?		Bridge ID: #Name?		
SPAN DATA			Comments/Notes	
Main Member Type*		Bailey Type*		
<input type="checkbox"/> Girder	<input type="checkbox"/> Through Truss	<input type="checkbox"/> Standard		<input type="checkbox"/> Not Applicable
<input type="checkbox"/> Beam	<input type="checkbox"/> Log	<input type="checkbox"/> Super		<input type="checkbox"/> Compact 200
<input type="checkbox"/> Deck Truss	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact 100		<input type="checkbox"/> Universal
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other
Main Member Material*				
<input type="checkbox"/> Timber	<input type="checkbox"/> Steel	<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete		<input type="checkbox"/> Other
Secondary Member Type				
<input type="checkbox"/> Girder	<input type="checkbox"/> Truss	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		<input type="checkbox"/> None
<input type="checkbox"/> Beam	<input type="checkbox"/> Log			
Other Member Type				
<input type="checkbox"/> Diaphragm	<input type="checkbox"/> Bracing	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> None	
ABUTMENT DATA				
Abutment Type*				
<input type="checkbox"/> Solid wall	<input type="checkbox"/> Pile bent	<input type="checkbox"/> Diaphragm wall		<input type="checkbox"/> Reinforced earth
<input type="checkbox"/> Spill through	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known		<input type="checkbox"/> None
Abutment Material*				
<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete	<input type="checkbox"/> Timber	<input type="checkbox"/> Gabions		<input type="checkbox"/> Earth
<input type="checkbox"/> Steel	<input type="checkbox"/> Masonry	<input type="checkbox"/> Other		
Abutment Foundation				
<input type="checkbox"/> Spread footing	<input type="checkbox"/> Driven pile	<input type="checkbox"/> Caisson		<input type="checkbox"/> Diaphragm wall
<input type="checkbox"/> Bored pile	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known		
Bearing Type - Abutments				
<input type="checkbox"/> Pot bearing	<input type="checkbox"/> Metal rocker	<input type="checkbox"/> Elastomeric	<input type="checkbox"/> PTFE coated plate	
<input type="checkbox"/> Steel plate	<input type="checkbox"/> Monolithic	<input type="checkbox"/> Roller	<input type="checkbox"/> Pinned	
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known	<input type="checkbox"/> None		
Restraint Type - Abutments				
	Lat	Long	Vert	
Concrete				
Steel				
Cables or bolts				
Scour Protection* - Abutments				
<input type="checkbox"/> Rip rap	<input type="checkbox"/> Mattresses	<input type="checkbox"/> Gabions	<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete	
<input type="checkbox"/> Sheet piling	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known	<input type="checkbox"/> None	
Bank/Slope Protection* - Abutments				
<input type="checkbox"/> Rip rap	<input type="checkbox"/> Mattresses	<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete	<input type="checkbox"/> Gabions	
<input type="checkbox"/> Stonepitch wall	<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known	<input type="checkbox"/> None	
PIER DATA				
None				
Pier Type*				
<input type="checkbox"/> Wall	<input type="checkbox"/> Single column	<input type="checkbox"/> Multiple columns		
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Single pile bent	<input type="checkbox"/> Multiple pile bent		
Pier Material*				
<input type="checkbox"/> Timber	<input type="checkbox"/> Steel	<input type="checkbox"/> Concrete		<input type="checkbox"/> Masonry
<input type="checkbox"/> Other				
Pier Foundation Type				
<input type="checkbox"/> Spread footing	<input type="checkbox"/> Bored piles	<input type="checkbox"/> Driven piles		<input type="checkbox"/> Caisson
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known			
Bearing Type - Piers				
<input type="checkbox"/> Pot bearing	<input type="checkbox"/> Metal rocker	<input type="checkbox"/> Elastomeric	<input type="checkbox"/> PTFE coated plate	
<input type="checkbox"/> Steel plate	<input type="checkbox"/> Monolithic	<input type="checkbox"/> Roller	<input type="checkbox"/> Pinned	
<input type="checkbox"/> Other	<input type="checkbox"/> Not known	<input type="checkbox"/> None		
Restraint Type - Piers				
	Lat	Long	Vert	
Concrete				
Steel				
Cables or bolts				

